

1º filtro de seleção

Base: Scopus

Total de artigos: 218

Artigos incluídos: 34 (CI1= 33, CI2= 1)

Artigos excluídos: 184 (CE1= 146, CE2= 0, CE3= 0, CE4= 1, CE5= 27, CE6= 10)

ID	Título	Resumo	CI	CE	Motivo exclusão
001	resistancebank.org, an open-access repository for surveys of antimicrobial resistance in animals	Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is a growing threat to the health of humans and animals that requires global actions. In high-income countries, surveillance systems helped inform policies to curb AMR in animals. In low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), demand for meat is rising, and developing policies against AMR is urgent. However, surveillance of AMR is at best nascent, and the current evidence base to inform policymakers is geographically heterogeneous. We present resistancebank.org, an online platform that centralizes information on AMR in animals from 1,285 surveys from LMICs. Surveys were conducted between 2000 and 2019 and include 22,403 resistance rates for pathogens isolated from chickens, cattle, sheep, and pigs. The platform is built as a shiny application that provides access to individual surveys, country-level reports, and maps of AMR at 10 × 10 kilometers resolution. The platform is accessed via any internet browser and enables users to upload surveys to strengthen a global database. resistancebank.org aims to be a focal point for sharing AMR data in LMICs and to help international funders prioritize their actions.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
002	Comparing machine learning algorithms for predicting ICU admission and mortality in COVID-19	As predicting the trajectory of COVID-19 is challenging, machine learning models could assist physicians in identifying high-risk individuals. This study compares the performance of 18 machine learning algorithms for predicting ICU admission and mortality among COVID-19 patients. Using COVID-19 patient data from the Mass General Brigham (MGB) Healthcare database, we developed and internally validated models using patients presenting to the Emergency Department (ED) between March-April 2020 (n = 3597) and further validated them using temporally distinct individuals who presented to the ED between May-August 2020 (n = 1711). We show that ensemble-based models perform better than other model types at predicting both 5-day ICU admission and 28-day mortality from COVID-19. CRP, LDH, and O ₂ saturation were important for ICU admission models whereas eGFR <60 ml/min/1.73 m ² , and neutrophil and lymphocyte percentages were the most important variables for predicting mortality. Implementing such models could help in clinical decision-making for future infectious disease outbreaks including COVID-19.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
003	COVID-19 deep classification network based on convolution and deconvolution local enhancement	Computer Tomography (CT) detection can effectively overcome the problems of traditional detection of Corona Virus Disease 2019 (COVID-19), such as lagging detection results and wrong diagnosis results, which lead to the increase of disease infection rate and prevalence rate. The novel coronavirus pneumonia is a significant difference between the positive and negative patients with asymptomatic infections. To effectively improve the accuracy of doctors' manual judgment of positive and negative COVID-19, this paper proposes a deep classification network model of the novel coronavirus pneumonia based on convolution and deconvolution local enhancement. Through convolution and deconvolution operation, the contrast between the local lesion region and the abdominal cavity of COVID-19 is enhanced. Besides, the middle-level features that can effectively distinguish the image types are obtained. By transforming the novel coronavirus detection problem into the region of interest (ROI) feature classification problem, it can effectively determine whether the feature vector in each feature channel contains the image features of COVID-19. This paper uses an open-source COVID-CT dataset provided by Petuum researchers from the University of California, San Diego, which is collected from 143 novel coronavirus pneumonia patients and the corresponding features are preserved. The complete dataset (including original image and enhanced image) contains 1460 images. Among them, 1022 (70%) and 438 (30%) are used to train and test the performance of the proposed model, respectively. The proposed model verifies the classification precision in different		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto. Utiliza base de dados open-source.

		convolution layers and learning rates. Besides, it is compared with most state-of-the-art models. It is found that the proposed algorithm has good classification performance. The corresponding sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), negative predictive value (NPV), and precision are 0.98, 0.96, 0.98, and 0.97, respectively.			
004	Multilingual conversational systems to drive the collection of patient-reported outcomes and integration into clinical workflows	Patient-reported outcomes (PROs) and their use in the clinical workflow can improve cancer survivors' outcomes and quality of life. However, there are several challenges regarding efficient collection of the patient-reported outcomes and their integration into the clinical workflow. Patient adherence and interoperability are recognized as main barriers. This work implements a cancer-related study which interconnects artificial intelligence (spoken language algorithms, conversational intelligence) and natural sciences (embodied conversational agents) to create an omni-comprehensive system enabling symmetric computer-mediated interaction. Its goal is to collect patient information and integrate it into clinical routine as digital patient resources (the Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources). To further increase convenience and simplicity of the data collection, a multimodal sensing network is delivered. In this paper, we introduce the main components of the system, including the mHealth application, the Open Health Connect platform , and algorithms to deliver speech enabled 3D embodied conversational agent to interact with the cancer survivors in five different languages. The system integrates cancer patients' reported information as patient gathered health data into their digital clinical record. The value and impact of the integration will be further evaluated in the clinical study.	CII		
005	Proteo: A framework for serious games in telerehabilitation	Within the context of telerehabilitation, serious games have a significant role, but creating software for serious games is resource demanding. We present Proteo, a modular and open-source framework for developing serious games from scratch. We also present two serious game implementation examples with analysis of end user and therapist/researcher satisfaction. By involving a group of 11 specialized therapists and 9 end users we analyzed the Proteo's user satisfaction. We found that both groups scored high for the level of involvement, and the therapists scored also high for the level of suitability. More in depth, both groups showed significant differences between positive and negative feelings, with positive feelings scoring higher than negative ones. Finally, the user level of suitability was reported as high while the difficulty of the system and the difficulty of the task were reported as low. Proteo has proven to be a useful tool to develop serious games for telerehabilitation and has been well accepted by the users involved in the evaluation tests.	CII		
006	Multi-domain clinical natural language processing with MedCAT: The Medical Concept Annotation Toolkit	Electronic health records (EHR) contain large volumes of unstructured text, requiring the application of information extraction (IE) technologies to enable clinical analysis. We present the open source Medical Concept Annotation Toolkit (MedCAT) that provides: (a) a novel self-supervised machine learning algorithm for extracting concepts using any concept vocabulary including UMLS/SNOMED-CT; (b) a feature-rich annotation interface for customizing and training IE models; and (c) integrations to the broader CogStack ecosystem for vendor-agnostic health system deployment. We show improved performance in extracting UMLS concepts from open datasets (F1:0.448–0.738 vs 0.429–0.650). Further real-world validation demonstrates SNOMED-CT extraction at 3 large London hospitals with self-supervised training over ~8.8B words from ~17M clinical records and further fine-tuning with ~6K clinician annotated examples. We show strong transferability (F1 > 0.94) between hospitals, datasets and concept types indicating cross-domain EHR-agnostic utility for accelerated clinical and research use cases.	CII		
007	A collaborative learning health system agent-based model. Computational and face validity.	Introduction: Improving the healthcare system is a major public health challenge. Collaborative learning health systems (CLHS) - network organizations that allow all healthcare stakeholders to collaborate at scale - are a promising response. However, we know little about CLHS mechanisms of actions, nor how to optimize CLHS performance. Agent-based models (ABM) have been used to study a variety of complex systems. We translate the conceptual underpinnings of a CLHS to a computational model and demonstrate initial computational and face validity. Methods: CLHSs are organized to allow stakeholders (patients and families, clinicians, researchers) to collaborate, at scale, in the production and distribution of		CE6	Duplicated Pubmed

		information, knowledge, and know-how for improvement. We build up a CLHS ABM from a population of patient- and doctor-agents, assign them characteristics, and set them into interaction, resulting in engagement, information, and knowledge to facilitate optimal treatment selection. To assess computational and face validity, we vary a single parameter - the degree to which patients influence other patients - and trace its effects on patient engagement, shared knowledge, and outcomes. Results: The CLHS ABM, developed in Python and using the open-source modeling framework Mesa, is delivered as a web application. The model is simulated on a cloud server and the user interface is a web browser using Python and Plotly Dash. Holding all other parameters steady, when patient influence increases, the overall patient population activation increases, leading to an increase in shared knowledge, and higher median patient outcomes. Conclusions: We present the first theoretically-derived computational model of CLHSs, demonstrating initial computational and face validity. These preliminary results suggest that modeling CLHSs using an ABM is feasible and potentially valid. A well-developed and validated computational model of the health system may have profound effects on understanding mechanisms of action, potential intervention targets, and ultimately translation to improved outcomes.			
008	Investigating the P300 Response as a Marker of Working Memory in Virtual Training Environments	Conventional performance metrics fail to offer high-resolution evaluation of learning and memory during training tasks; the P300 component of the event-related potential (ERP) is a promising tool for enhancing the assessment of training quality in virtual environments, but this technique is yet to be investigated. A driver training simulator and scenario were developed to explore the capability of the P300 for this purpose. A user study was conducted with 32 participants divided into two groups objectively determined by driving performance scores, thus enabling observations of the P300 response to be equated to varying levels of learning and memory. Participant electroencephalogram data were recorded during the procedure, which was postprocessed to filter and extract ERPs to capture neural responses to specific events in the virtual training scenario. These were combined to produce a result for each participant, which was then grand averaged to create an overall ERP for each group. Across the eight electrode sites, statistically significant differences were found between the grand average waveforms of the two groups, with high memory retention producing significantly greater peak-to-peak amplitude ($U = 9.00$, $p = 0.045$), peak latency ($U = 0.00$, $p < 0.001$), and positive area ($U = 13.00$, $p = 0.05$) of the waveform than low memory retention. The evidenced relationship between the P300 response and working memory in this context suggests that it has the potential for monitoring learning and memory in stimulus-driven virtual training systems.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
009	Evaluating service-oriented and microservice architecture patterns to deploy eHealth applications in cloud computing environment	This article proposes a new framework for a Cloud-based eHealth platform concept focused on Cloud computing environments, since current and emerging approaches using digital clinical history increasingly demonstrate their potential in maintaining the quality of the benefits in medical care services, especially in computer-assisted clinical diagnosis within the field of infectious diseases and due to the worsening of chronic pathologies. Our objective is to evaluate and contrast the performance of the architectural patterns most commonly used for developing eHealth applications (i.e., service-oriented architecture (SOA) and microservices architecture (MSA)), using as reference the quantitative values obtained from the various performance tests and their ability to adapt to the required software attribute (i.e., versatile high-performance). Therefore, it was necessary to modify our platform to fit two architectural variants. As a follow-up to this activity, corresponding tests were performed that showed that the MSA variant functions better in terms of performance and response time compared to the SOA variant; however, it consumed significantly more bandwidth than SOA, and scalability in SOA is generally not possible or requires significant effort to be achieved. We conclude that the implementation of SOA and MSA depends on the nature and needs of organizations (e.g., performance or interoperability).		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
010	A hierarchical feature-based methodology to perform cervical	Prevention of cervical cancer could be performed using Pap smear image analysis. This test screens pre-neoplastic changes in the cervical epithelial cells; accurate screening can reduce deaths caused by the disease. Pap smear test analysis is exhaustive and repetitive work performed visu-ally by a cytopathologist. This		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-

	cancer classification	article proposes a workload-reducing algorithm for cervical cancer detection based on analysis of cell nuclei features within Pap smear images. We investigate eight traditional machine learning methods to perform a hierarchical classification. We propose a hierarchical classification methodology for computer-aided screening of cell lesions, which can recommend fields of view from the microscopy image based on the nuclei detection of cervical cells. We evaluate the performance of several algorithms against the Herlev and CRIC databases, using a varying number of classes during image classification. Results indicate that the hierarchical classification performed best when using Random Forest as the key classifier, particularly when compared with decision trees, k-NN, and the Ridge methods.			aberto.
011	Augmented ehr. Enrichment of ehr with contents from semantic web sources	This work presents methods to combine data from the Semantic Web into existing EHRs, leading to an augmented EHR. An existing EHR extract is augmented by combining it with additional information from external sources, typically linked data sources. The starting point is a standardized EHR extract described by an archetype. The method consists of combining specific data from the original EHR with contents from the external information source by building a semantic representation, which is used to query the external source. The results are converted into a standardized EHR extract according to an archetype. This work sets the foundations to transform Semantic Web contents into normalized EHR extracts. Finally, to exemplify the approach, the work includes a practical use case in which the summarized EHR is augmented with drug-drug interactions and disease-related treatment information.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
012	Bsf-ehr. Blockchain security framework for electronic health records of patients	In the current epoch of smart homes and cities, personal data such as patients' names, diseases and addresses are often violated. This is frequently associated with the safety of the electronic health records (EHRs) of patients. EHRs have numerous benefits worldwide, but at present, EHR information is subject to considerable security and privacy issues. This paper proposes a way to provide a secure solution to these issues. Previous sophisticated techniques dealing with the protection of EHRs usually make data inaccessible to patients. These techniques struggle to balance data confidentiality, patient demand and constant interaction with provider data. Blockchain technology solves the above problems since it distributes information in a transactional and decentralized manner. The usage of blockchain technology could help the health sector to balance the accessibility and privacy of EHRs. This paper proposes a blockchain security framework (BSF) to effectively and securely store and keep EHRs. It presents a safe and proficient means of acquiring medical information for doctors, patients and insurance agents while protecting the patient's data. This work aims to examine how our proposed framework meets the security needs of doctors, patients and third parties and how the structure addresses safety and confidentiality concerns in the healthcare sector. Simulation outcomes show that this framework efficiently protects EHR data.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
013	Identification of a minimal 3-transcript signature to differentiate viral from bacterial infection from host genome-wide host na biomarkers: A multi-cohort analysis	The fight against the spread of antibiotic resistance is one of the most important challenges facing health systems worldwide. Given the limitations of current diagnostic methods, the development of fast and accurate tests for the diagnosis of viral and bacterial infections would improve patient management and treatment, as well as contribute to reducing antibiotic misuse in clinical settings. In this scenario, analysis of host transcriptomics constitutes a promising target to develop new diagnostic tests based on the host-specific response to infections. We carried out a multi-cohort meta-analysis of blood transcriptomic data available in public databases, including 11 different studies and 1209 samples from virus-(n = 695) and bacteria-(n = 514) infected patients. We applied a Parallel Regularized Regression Model Search (PReMS) on a set of previously reported genes that distinguished viral from bacterial infection to find a minimum gene expression bio-signature. This strategy allowed us to detect three genes, namely BAFT, ISG15 and DNMT1, that clearly differentiate groups of infection with high accuracy (training set: area under the curve (AUC) 0.86 (sensitivity: 0.81; specificity: 0.87); testing set: AUC 0.87 (sensitivity: 0.82; specificity: 0.86)). BAFT and ISG15 are involved in processes related to immune response, while DNMT1 is related to the preservation of methylation patterns, and its expression is modulated by pathogen infections. We successfully tested this three-transcript signature in the 11 independent studies, demonstrating its high performance under different scenarios.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.

		The main advantage of this three-gene signature is the low number of genes needed to differentiate both groups of patient categories.			
014	Visual analytics for electronic health records: A review	The increasing use of electronic health record (EHR)-based systems has led to the generation of clinical data at an unprecedented rate, which produces an untapped resource for healthcare experts to improve the quality of care. Despite the growing demand for adopting EHRs, the large amount of clinical data has made some analytical and cognitive processes more challenging. The emergence of a type of computational system called visual analytics has the potential to handle information overload challenges in EHRs by integrating analytics techniques with interactive visualizations. In recent years, several EHR-based visual analytics systems have been developed to fulfill healthcare experts' computational and cognitive demands. In this paper, we conduct a systematic literature review to present the research papers that describe the design of EHR-based visual analytics systems and provide a brief overview of 22 systems that met the selection criteria. We identify and explain the key dimensions of the EHR-based visual analytics design space, including visual analytics tasks, analytics, visualizations, and interactions. We evaluate the systems using the selected dimensions and identify the gaps and areas with little prior work.		CE5	Revisão sistemática da literatura
015	Systematic delimitation of media polarity on COVID-19 vaccines in Africa: Computational linguistic modeling study	Background: The global onset of COVID-19 has resulted in substantial public health and socioeconomic impacts. An immediate medical breakthrough is needed. However, parallel to the emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic is the proliferation of information regarding the pandemic, which, if uncontrolled, cannot only mislead the public but also hinder the concerted efforts of relevant stakeholders in mitigating the effect of this pandemic. It is known that media communications can affect public perception and attitude toward medical treatment, vaccination, or subject matter, particularly when the population has limited knowledge on the subject. Objective: This study attempts to systematically scrutinize media communications (Google News headlines or snippets and Twitter posts) to understand the prevailing sentiments regarding COVID-19 vaccines in Africa. Methods: A total of 637 Twitter posts and 569 Google News headlines or descriptions, retrieved between February 2 and May 5, 2020, were analyzed using three standard computational linguistics models (ie, TextBlob, Valence Aware Dictionary and Sentiment Reasoner, and Word2Vec combined with a bidirectional long short-term memory neural network). Results: Our findings revealed that, contrary to general perceptions, Google News headlines or snippets and Twitter posts within the stated period were generally passive or positive toward COVID-19 vaccines in Africa. It was possible to understand these patterns in light of increasingly sustained efforts by various media and health actors in ensuring the availability of factual information about the pandemic. Conclusions: This type of analysis could contribute to understanding predominant polarities and associated potential attitudinal inclinations. Such knowledge could be critical in informing relevant public health and media engagement policies.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
016	The impact of quality on hospital choice: Which information affects patients' behavior for colorectal resection or knee replacement?	Abstract: Quality competition among hospitals, induced by patients freely choosing their hospital in a price regulated market, can only be realized if quality differences between hospitals are transparent, understandable, and thus influence patients' hospital choice. We use data from ~145,000 German patients and ~ 900 hospitals for colorectal resections and knee replacements to investigate whether patients value quality and specialization when choosing their hospital. Using a random utility choice model, we estimate patients' marginal utilities, willingness to travel and change in hospital demand for quality improvements. Patients respond to service quality and specialization and thus, quality competition seems to be present. Colorectal resection patients are willing to travel longer for more specialized hospitals (+9% for procedure volume, +9% for certification). Knee replacement patients travel longer for hospitals with better service quality (+6%) and higher procedure volume (+12%). However, clinical quality indicators, often difficult to access and interpret, barely play a role in patients' hospital choice. Furthermore, we find that competition on quality for colorectal resection is rather local, whereas for knee replacement we observe regional competition patterns.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
017	W-COVID: A COVID-19	The current SARS-CoV-2, better know as COVID-19, has emerged as a serious pandemic with life-threatening clinical manifestations and a high mortality rate.		CE1	Não deixa explícito

	symptom detection and patient monitoring framework using WiFi	<p>One of the major complications of this disease is the rapid and dangerous pulmonary deterioration that can lead to critical pneumonia conditions, resulting in death. The current healthcare system around the world faces the potential problem of lacking resources to assist a large number of patients at the same time; then, the non-critical patients are mostly referred to perform self-isolation/quarantine at home. This pandemic has placed new demands on the health systems world, asking for novel, rapid and secure ways to monitor patients in order to detect and quickly report patient's symptoms to the healthcare provider, even if they are not in the hospital. While tremendous efforts have been done to develop technologies to detect the virus, create the vaccine, and stop the spread of the disease, it is also important to develop IoT technologies that can help track and monitor diagnosed COVID-19 patients from their homes. In this paper, we explore the possibility of monitoring respiration rates (RR) of COVID-19 patients using a widely-available technology at home – WiFi. Using the at-home WiFi signals, we propose Wi-COVID, a non-invasive and non-wearable technology to monitor the patient and track RR for the healthcare provider. We first introduce the currently available applications that can be done using WiFi signals. Then, we propose the framework scheme for an end-to-end non-invasive monitoring platform of the COVID-19 patients using WiFi. Finally, we present some preliminary results of the proposed framework. We envision the proposed platform as a life-changing technology that leverages WiFi technology as a non-wearable and non-invasive way to monitor COVID-19 patients at home.</p>			o uso de código aberto.
018	COVID-19 open source data sets: a comprehensive survey	<p>In December 2019, a novel virus named COVID-19 emerged in the city of Wuhan, China. In early 2020, the COVID-19 virus spread in all continents of the world except Antarctica, causing widespread infections and deaths due to its contagious characteristics and no medically proven treatment. The COVID-19 pandemic has been termed as the most consequential global crisis since the World Wars. The first line of defense against the COVID-19 spread are the non-pharmaceutical measures like social distancing and personal hygiene. The great pandemic affecting billions of lives economically and socially has motivated the scientific community to come up with solutions based on computer-aided digital technologies for diagnosis, prevention, and estimation of COVID-19. Some of these efforts focus on statistical and Artificial Intelligence-based analysis of the available data concerning COVID-19. All of these scientific efforts necessitate that the data brought to service for the analysis should be open source to promote the extension, validation, and collaboration of the work in the fight against the global pandemic. Our survey is motivated by the open source efforts that can be mainly categorized as (a) COVID-19 diagnosis from CT scans, X-ray images, and cough sounds, (b) COVID-19 case reporting, transmission estimation, and prognosis from epidemiological, demographic, and mobility data, (c) COVID-19 emotional and sentiment analysis from social media, and (d) knowledge-based discovery and semantic analysis from the collection of scholarly articles covering COVID-19. We survey and compare research works in these directions that are accompanied by open source data and code. Future research directions for data-driven COVID-19 research are also debated. We hope that the article will provide the scientific community with an initiative to start open source extensible and transparent research in the collective fight against the COVID-19 pandemic.</p>		CES	Survey
019	Mr. images, brain lesions, and deep learning	<p>Medical brain image analysis is a necessary step in computer-assisted/computer-aided diagnosis (CAD) systems. Advancements in both hardware and software in the past few years have led to improved segmentation and classification of various diseases. In the present work, we review the published literature on systems and algorithms that allow for classification, identification, and detection of white matter hyperintensities (WMHs) of brain magnetic resonance (MR) images, specifically in cases of ischemic stroke and demyelinating diseases. For the selection criteria, we used bibliometric networks. Of a total of 140 documents, we selected 38 articles that deal with the main objectives of this study. Based on the analysis and discussion of the revised documents, there is constant growth in the research and development of new deep learning models to achieve the highest accuracy and reliability of the segmentation of ischemic and demyelinating lesions. Models with good performance metrics (e.g., Dice similarity coefficient, DSC: 0.99) were</p>		CES	Revisão da literatura.

		found; however, there is little practical application due to the use of small datasets and a lack of reproducibility. Therefore, the main conclusion is that there should be multidisciplinary research groups to overcome the gap between CAD developments and their deployment in the clinical environment. Outcomes of embedded athletic training services within united states air force basic military training			
020	Outcomes of embedded athletic training services within united states air force basic military training	Context: Musculoskeletal injury is the leading cause of attrition from military training. Objective: To assess the effect of an embedded athletic training musculoskeletal care model within a basic military training unit. Design: Cluster randomized trial. Setting: United States Air Force Basic Military Training, Joint Base San Antonio—Lackland. Patients or Other Participants: Military recruits randomly assigned to 1 of 3 training squadrons, 2 control and 1 experimental, between January 2016 and December 2018. Intervention(s): A sports medicine care model was established in 1 squadron by embedding 2 certified athletic trainers overseen by a sports medicine fellowship-trained physician. The athletic trainers diagnosed and coordinated rehabilitation as the primary point of contact for recruits and developed interventions with medical and military leadership based on injury trends. Main Outcome Measure(s): Recruit attrition from basic training due to a musculoskeletal injury. Secondary outcomes were all-cause attrition, on-time graduation, rates of lower extremity injury and stress fracture, rates of specialty care appointments, and fiscal costs. Results: Recruits in the athletic training musculoskeletal care arm experienced 25% lower musculoskeletal-related attrition (risk ratio ¼ 0.75 [95% CI ¼ 0.64, 0.89]) and 15% lower all-cause attrition (risk ratio ¼ 0.85 [95% CI ¼ 0.80, 0.91]), translating to a net saving of more than \$10 million. The intervention reduced the incidence of lower extremity stress fracture by 16% (rate ratio ¼ 0.84 [95% CI ¼ 0.73, 0.97]). Conclusions: An embedded athletic training musculoskeletal care model outperformed usual care across operational, medical, and fiscal outcomes.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
021	Immunization calculation engine: An open source immunization evaluation and forecasting system	Introduction: The immunization calculation engine (ICE) is a free, open-source immunization forecasting evaluation and software system whose default immunization schedule supports all routine childhood, adolescent, and adult immunizations based on the recommendations of the Advisory Committee on Immunization Practices (ACIP). ICE utilizes its immunization rules and patient data to evaluate and return the validity of each immunization in the patient's history along with one or more evaluation reasons. It also returns a recommendation for each vaccine group along with one or more recommendation reasons. Methods: In January 2020, ICE was first released as a Docker image along with the traditional zip archive file which had been used up to that point. Docker enables software providers to easily distribute their software so that it can be run “out of the box” in the user's local environment. Software running in Docker containers drastically reduces the complexity of software distribution and set up. Results: Clinical systems of many types use ICE. The project began within the public health arena as a feature of Immunization Information Systems (IIS), but electronic health records (EHR) and personal health records (PHR) have also deployed ICE. While it is not possible to identify the specific impact of ICE on clinical care without additional research, it should be pointed out that once deployed within an IIS, EHR, or PHR the display of ICE results is performed for every patient viewed by a user and often for every patient appearing on a report. In a typical month, thousands if not millions of evaluations and forecasts are performed by ICE and displayed to the users. Conclusions: The ICE Project believes in minimizing the barriers to installing and using ICE anywhere. To that end, there is no registration required to download the source code or runtime code for the ICE service and its default rule. Similarly, the Project created a Docker image of ICE to facilitate easy and seamless implementation.	CII		
022	EOM-NPOSES: Emergency Ontology Model Based on Network Public Opinion Spread Elements	The construction of an emergency ontology model plays an important role in emergency management, which is an important basis for emergency public opinion management and decision-making. Integration of network public opinion spread elements into the emergency ontology model is crucial for realizing knowledge sharing in the field of emergency and public opinion responses. In this study, we crawl a large amount of emergency data from different data sources and construct an emergency dataset. Based on this dataset, we analyze the public opinion		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.

		elements of emergencies and propose an emergency ontology model based on network public opinion spread elements (EOM-NPOSESs). Thereafter, we consider the coronavirus disease (COVID-19) emergency as an example to construct the EOM-NPOSESs. Finally, we design some strategies to realize rule reasoning and present the COVID-19 emergency application based on the constructed EOM-NPOSESs and the geographic information system platform. The results demonstrate that EOM-NPOSESs can not only describe the semantic relationship between emergencies and emergency elements but also perform semantic logical reasoning on different emergencies.			
023	Applying and Understanding an Advanced Novel Deep Learning Approach: A Covid-19 Text-Based Emotions Analysis Study	The pandemic COVID 19 has altered individuals' daily lives across the globe. It has led to preventive measures such as physical distancing to be imposed on individuals and led to terms such as 'lockdown,' 'emergency,' or curfew' to emerge in various countries. It has affected society, not only physically and financially, but in terms of emotional wellbeing as well. This distress in the human emotional quotient results from multiple factors such as financial implications, family member's behavior and support, country-specific lockdown protocols, media influence, or fear of the pandemic. For efficient pandemic management, there is a need to understand the emotional variations among individuals, as this will provide insights into public sentiment towards various government pandemic management policies. From our investigations, it was found that individuals have increasingly used different microblogging platforms such as Twitter to remain connected and express their feelings and concerns during the pandemic. However, research in the area of expressed emotional wellbeing during COVID 19 is still growing, which motivated this team to form the aim: To identify, explore and understand globally the emotions expressed during the earlier months of the pandemic COVID 19 by utilizing Deep Learning and Natural language Processing (NLP). For the data collection, over 2 million tweets during February–June 2020 were collected and analyzed using an advanced deep learning technique of Transfer Learning and Robustly Optimized BERT Pretraining Approach (RoBERTa). A Reddit-based standard Emotion Dataset by Crowdflower was utilized for transfer learning. Using RoBERTa and the collated Twitter dataset, a multi-class emotion classifier system was formed. With the implemented methodology, a tweet classification accuracy of 80.33% and an average MCC score of 0.78 was achieved, improving the existing AI-based emotion classification methods. This study explains the novel application of the Roberta model during the pandemic that provided insights into changing emotional wellbeing over time of various citizens worldwide. It also offers novelty for data mining and analytics during this challenging, pandemic era. These insights can be beneficial for formulating effective pandemic management strategies and devising a novel, predictive strategy for the emotional well-being of an entire country's citizens when facing future unexpected exogenous shocks.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
024	Health research networks based on National CV platforms in Brazil and Uruguay	Collaborations are an essential part of the research process. In the health area, these involve a great diversity of actors in various scientific and health subsystems. The study of collaborations has been developed mostly from the analysis of co-authorship in articles indexed in international platforms. However, these sources present some limitations to capture the production of knowledge in Latin American countries. This paper seeks to diversify the sources of information and the units of analysis for the study of collaborations in health research, by exploring data from two original and little-used sources of information in national and public Curriculum Vitae (CV) platforms: LattesCv (Brazil) and CVUy (Uruguay). Based on a wide sample of research projects extracted from CVs, networks for knowledge production are analyzed at micro (researchers) and meso (institutions) levels in each country. This preliminary analysis allows us not only to generate evidence on the nature and evolution of health research networks, but also to evaluate the advantages and limitations of CVs as a new source for the study of collaborative networks.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
025	Effect of mobile-based voice therapy on the voice quality of patients with	Purpose: Mobile-based voice therapy (MBVT) has the advantage of being cheaper and more flexible for patients and clinicians compared to traditional PC-based voice therapy. The purpose of this study was to investigate the effect of MBVT on the voice quality of patients with dysphonia. Methods: Forty-five patients with benign vocal fold lesions were randomly allocated to either the experimental		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de

	dysphonia	(N=25) or control (N=20) group. The experimental group received MBVT, while the control group received traditional voice therapy (TRVT). Both groups participated in 40 minutes of the intervention per session, once per week, for 8 weeks. Voice evaluation measures included cepstral analysis, acoustic voice quality index, acoustic breathiness index, auditory-perceptual ratings, and a self-rated questionnaire. Analyses compared the voice quality and subjective variables before and after each therapy, as well as between each type of therapy (MBVT vs. TRVT). Results: The results showed that voice quality and patient satisfaction improved in both therapies compared to before therapy, indicating recovery ($p < 0.01$). Therefore, similar to TRVT, MBVT was effective for voice rehabilitation. Conclusions: MBVT could have a positive effect on voice recovery for patients with dysphonia. Therefore, the mobile-based approach is useful to restore pathological voice and allows for a greater number of patients to easily access voice therapy.			um sistema.
026	A new approach for physical human activity recognition based on co-occurrence matrices	In recent years, it has been observed that many researchers have been working on different areas of detection, recognition and monitoring of human activities. The automatic determination of human physical activities is often referred to as human activity recognition (HAR). One of the most important technology that detects and tracks the activity of the human body is sensor-based HAR technology. In recent days, sensor-based HAR attracts attention in the field of computers due to its wide use in daily life and is a rapidly growing field of research. Activity recognition (AR) application is carried out by evaluating the signals obtained from various sensors placed in the human body. In this study, a new approach is proposed to extract features from sensor signals using HAR. The proposed approach is inspired by the Gray Level Co-Occurrence Matrix (GLCM) method, which is widely used in image processing, but it is applied to one-dimensional signals, unlike GLCM. Two datasets were used to test the proposed approach. The datasets were created from the signals obtained from the accelerometer, gyro and magnetometer sensors. Heralick features were obtained from co-occurrence matrix created after 1D-GLCM (One (1) Dimensional-Gray Level Co-Occurrence Matrix) was applied to the signals. HAR operation has been carried out for different scenarios using these features. Success rates of 96.66 and 93.88% were obtained for two datasets, respectively. It has been observed that the new approach proposed within the scope of the study provides high success rates for HAR applications. It is thought that the proposed approach can be used in the classification of different signals.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código aberto.
027	Uncovering generative mechanisms of information use for project monitoring in humanitarian health management information systems	Humanitarian medical organizations rely on information on and from the ground to evaluate their effectiveness and accountability. Related digitalization efforts within health information systems assume an instrumental rationality in the use of data. However, previous research identified a multitude of factors influencing actual information use for evidence-based decision-making for healthcare delivery. This case study, anchored by critical realism philosophy, unpacks these nuances against the backdrop of a globally operating organization (Médecins Sans Frontières). It aims to highlight the contextual conditions and structures that enact the contingent mechanisms at work in project monitoring within humanitarian health management information systems. By applying an affordance-based causal analysis, three mechanisms are identified: first, an analytics service provides templated analysis modalities resulting in user-producer-provider relationships; second, the rationalization and synchronization of content and software artifacts gives rise to the standardization strategy of flexible generification; third, the study uncovers the potential for increased internal social discourse and advocacy through collaborative and mobile data analysis. This paper proposes that mechanism-based explanations can be useful for theory-building in information systems research as well as for providing insights to practitioners in the humanitarian health sector.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
028	Epidemiologic evolution platform using integrated modeling and geographic information system	At the international level, a major effort is being made to optimize the flow of data and information for health systems management. The studies show that medical and economic efficiency is strongly influenced by the level of development and complexity of implementing an integrated system of epidemiological monitoring and modeling. The solution proposed and described in this paper is addressed to all public and private institutions involved in the fight against the COVID-19 pandemic, using recognized methods and standards in this field. The Green-Epidemio is a platform adaptable to the specific features of any public institution		CII	

		for disease management, based on open-source software, allowing the adaptation, customization, and further development of "open-source" applications, according to the specificities of the public institution, the changes in the economic and social environment and its legal framework. The platform has a mathematical model for the spread of COVID-19 infection depending on the location of the outbreaks so that the allocation of resources and the geographical limitation of certain areas can be parameterized according to the number and location of the real-Time identified outbreaks. The social impact of the proposed solution is due to the planned applications of information flow management, which is a first step in improving significantly the response time and efficiency of people-operated response services. Moreover, institutional interoperability influences strategic societal factors.			
029	The prediction of the lifetime of the new coronavirus in the USA using mathematical models	The World Health Organization (WHO) on December 31, 2019, was informed of several cases of respiratory diseases of unknown origin in the city of Wuhan in the Chinese Province of Hubei, the clinical manifestations of which were similar to those of viral pneumonia and manifested as fever, cough, and shortness of breath. And, the disease caused by the virus is named the new coronavirus disease 2019 and it will be abbreviated as 2019-nCoV and COVID-19. As of January 30, 2020, the WHO classified this epidemic as a global health emergency (Chung et al. in Radiology 295(1):202–207, 2020). It is an international real-life problem. Due to deaths, globally everyone is under fear. Now, it is the responsibility of researchers to give hope to the people. In this article, we aim to better protect people and general pandemic preparedness by predicting the lifetime of the disease-causing virus using three mathematical models. This article deals with a complex real-life problem people face all over the world, an international real-life problem. The main focus is on the USA due to large infection and death due to coronavirus and thereby the life of every individual is uncertain. The death counts of the USA from February 29 to April 22, 2020, are used in this article as a data set. The death counts of the USA are fitted by the solutions of three mathematical models and a solution to an international problem is achieved. Based on the death rate, the lifetime of the coronavirus COVID-19 is predicted as 1464.76 days from February 29, 2020. That is, after March 2024 there will be no death in the USA due to COVID-19 if everyone follows the guidelines of WHO and the advice of healthcare workers. People and government can get prepared for this situation and many lives can be saved. It is the contribution of soft computing. Finally, this article suggests several steps to control the spread and severity of the disease. The research work, the lifetime prediction presented in this article is entirely new and differs from all other articles in the literature.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
030	Best practices for fNIRS publications	The application of functional near-infrared spectroscopy (fNIRS) in the neurosciences has been expanding over the last 40 years. Today, it is addressing a wide range of applications within different populations and utilizes a great variety of experimental paradigms. With the rapid growth and the diversification of research methods, some inconsistencies are appearing in the way in which methods are presented, which can make the interpretation and replication of studies unnecessarily challenging. The Society for Functional Near-Infrared Spectroscopy has thus been motivated to organize a representative (but not exhaustive) group of leaders in the field to build a consensus on the best practices for describing the methods utilized in fNIRS studies. Our paper has been designed to provide guidelines to help enhance the reliability, repeatability, and traceability of reported fNIRS studies and encourage best practices throughout the community. A checklist is provided to guide authors in the preparation of their manuscripts and to assist reviewers when evaluating fNIRS papers. The Authors. Published by SPIE under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 Unported License. Distribution or reproduction of this work in whole or in part requires full attribution of the original publication, including its.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
031	Exploring the relationship between information and communication technology	Purpose: Helping others use information and communication technologies (ICTs), such as mobile phones, can be beneficial for individuals and communities. In urban refugee communities, displaced and living far from home, collective behaviors with mobile phones can generate a sense of belonging. The purpose of this paper is to explore the potential for these offline behaviors to generate a sense of community among urban refugees. Design/methodology/approach: Using quantitative		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.

	<p>collective behaviors are sense of community: an urban refugees analysis</p>	<p>evidence, the authors examined the relationship between collective behaviors, such as sharing or helping with a mobile phone, and sense of community. The authors analyzed survey data collected from urban refugees in Rwanda via multiple regression to test hypotheses related to the impact of collective behaviors on sense of community, as well as the mediating role of ICT self-efficacy and gender. Findings: The findings suggest that collective behaviors with mobile phones have a positive relationship with sense of community, driven primarily by providing assistance as compared to sharing. ICT self-efficacy was positively related to sense of community. However, collective behaviors' impacts differed by gender, suggesting that social dynamics influence this relationship. Originality/value: While the extant literature highlights the various roles of mobile phones in refugees' lives, less is known about the social aspects of use and its potential to help overcome isolation by fostering a sense of community. The authors extend this literature to a novel context (urban refugees in the Global South), testing a model that incorporates other factors that may play a role (e.g. self-efficacy and gender). These findings are valuable to urban refugees, due to difficulties in re-building a sense of community and increased ICT access.</p>			<p>sistema.</p>
032	<p>An ensemble of global and local-attention based convolutional neural networks for COVID-19 diagnosis on chest X-ray images</p>	<p>The recent Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic has put a tremendous burden on global health systems. Medical practitioners are under great pressure for reliable screening of suspected cases employing adjunct diagnostic tools to standard point-of-care testing methodology. Chest X-rays (CXRs) are appearing as a prospective diagnostic tool with easy-to-acquire, low-cost and less cross-contamination risk features. Artificial intelligence (AI)-attributed CXR evaluation has shown great potential for distinguishing COVID-19-induced pneumonia from other associated clinical instances. However, one of the associated challenges with diagnostic imaging-based modeling is incorrect feature attribution, which leads the model to learn misleading disease patterns, causing wrong predictions. Here, we demonstrate an effective deep learning-based methodology to mitigate the problem, thereby allowing the classification algorithm to learn from relevant features. The proposed deep-learning framework consists of an ensemble of convolutional neural network (CNN) models focusing on both global and local pathological features from CXR lung images, while the latter is extracted using a multi-instance learning scheme and a local attention mechanism. An inspection of a series of backbone CNN models using global and local features, and an ensemble of both features, trained from high-quality CXR images of 1311 patients, further augmented for achieving the symmetry in class distribution, to localize lung pathological features followed by the classification of COVID-19 and other related pneumonia, shows that a DenseNet161 architecture outperforms all other models, as evaluated on an independent test set of 159 patients with confirmed cases. Specifically, an ensemble of DenseNet161 models with global and local attention-based features achieve an average balanced accuracy of 91.2%, average precision of 92.4%, and F1-score of 91.9% in a multi-label classification framework comprising COVID-19, pneumonia, and control classes. The DenseNet161 ensembles were also found to be statistically significant from all other models in a comprehensive statistical analysis. The current study demonstrated that the proposed deep learning-based algorithm can accurately identify the COVID-19-related pneumonia in CXR images, along with differentiating non-COVID-19-associated pneumonia with high specificity, by effectively alleviating the incorrect feature attribution problem, and exploiting an enhanced feature descriptor.</p>		CE1	<p>Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.</p>
033	<p>Edge Intelligence and Internet of Things in Healthcare: A Survey</p>	<p>With the advent of new technologies and the fast pace of human life, patients today require a sophisticated and advanced smart healthcare framework that is tailored to suit their individual health requirements. Along with 5G and state-of-the-art smart Internet of Things (IoT) sensors, edge computing provides intelligent, real-time healthcare solutions that satisfy energy consumption and latency criteria. Earlier surveys on smart healthcare systems were centered on cloud and fog computing architectures, security, and authentication, and the types of sensors and devices used in edge computing frameworks. They did not focus on the healthcare IoT applications deployed within edge computing architectures. The first purpose of this study is to analyze the existing and evolving edge computing architectures and techniques for smart healthcare and recognize the demands and challenges of</p>		CE5	<p>Survey</p>

		different application scenarios. We examine edge intelligence that targets health data classification with the tracking and identification of vital signs using state-of-the-art deep learning techniques. This study also presents a comprehensive analysis of the use of cutting-edge artificial intelligence-based classification and prediction techniques employed for edge intelligence. Even with its many advantages, edge intelligence poses challenges related to computational complexity and security. To offer a higher quality of life to patients, potential research recommendations for improving edge computing services for healthcare are identified in this study. This study also offers a brief overview of the general usage of IoT solutions in edge platforms for medical treatment and healthcare.			
034	Can structured EHR data support clinical coding? A data mining approach	Structured data formats are gaining momentum in electronic health records and can be leveraged for decision support and research. Nevertheless, such structured data formats have not been explored for clinical coding, which is an essential process requiring significant manual workload in health organisations. This article explores the extent to which fully structured clinical data can support assignment of clinical codes to inpatient episodes, through a methodology that tackles high dimensionality issues, addresses the multi-label nature of coding and optimises model parameters. The methodology encompasses transformation of raw data to define a feature set, build a data matrix representation, and testing combinations of feature selection methods with machine learning models to predict code assignment. The methodology was tested with a real hospital dataset and showed varying predictive power across codes, while demonstrating the potential of leveraging structuring data to reduce workload and increase efficiency in clinical coding.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
035	A Threat Modelling Approach to Analyze and Mitigate Botnet Attacks in Smart Home Use Case	Despite the surging development and utilization of IoT devices, the security of IoT devices is still in infancy. The security pitfalls of IoT devices have made it easy for hackers to take over IoT devices and use them for malicious activities like botnet attacks. With the rampant emergence of IoT devices, botnet attacks are surging. The botnet attacks are not only catastrophic for IoT device users but also for the rest of the world. Therefore, there is a crucial need to identify and mitigate the possible threats in IoT devices during the design phase. Threat modelling is a technique that is used to identify the threats in the earlier stages of the system design activity. In this paper, we propose a threat modelling approach to analyze and mitigate the botnet attacks in an IoT smart home use case. The proposed methodology identifies the development-level and application-level threats in smart home use case using STRIDE and VAST threat modelling methods. Moreover, we reticulate the identified threats with botnet attacks. Finally, we propose the mitigation techniques for all identified threats including the botnet threats.		CE1	Não é da área da saúde.
036	Cystic fibrosis point of personalized detection (CFPOPD): An interactive web application	Background: Despite steady gains in life expectancy, individuals with cystic fibrosis (CF) lung disease still experience rapid pulmonary decline throughout their clinical course, which can ultimately end in respiratory failure. Point-of-care tools for accurate and timely information regarding the risk of rapid decline is essential for clinical decision support. Objective: This study aims to translate a novel algorithm for earlier, more accurate prediction of rapid lung function decline in patients with CF into an interactive web-based application that can be integrated within electronic health record systems, via collaborative development with clinicians. Methods: Longitudinal clinical history, lung function measurements, and time-invariant characteristics were obtained for 30,879 patients with CF who were followed in the US Cystic Fibrosis Foundation Patient Registry (2003-2015). We iteratively developed the application using the R Shiny framework and by conducting a qualitative study with care provider focus groups (N=17). Results: A clinical conceptual model and 4 themes were identified through coded feedback from application users: (1) ambiguity in rapid decline, (2) clinical utility, (3) clinical significance, and (4) specific suggested revisions. These themes were used to revise our application to the currently released version, available online for exploration. This study has advanced the application's potential prognostic utility for monitoring individuals with CF lung disease. Further application development will incorporate additional clinical characteristics requested by the users and also a more modular layout that can be useful for care provider and family interactions. Conclusions: Our framework for creating an interactive and visual analytics platform enables generalized development of applications to synthesize, model, and		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.

		translate electronic health data, thereby enhancing clinical decision support and improving care and health outcomes for chronic diseases and disorders. A prospective implementation study is necessary to evaluate this tool's effectiveness regarding increased communication, enhanced shared decision-making, and improved clinical outcomes for patients with CF.			
037	Institution-specific machine learning models for prehospital assessment to predict hospital admission: Prediction model development study	Background: Although multiple prediction models have been developed to predict hospital admission to emergency departments (EDs) to address overcrowding and patient safety, only a few studies have examined prediction models for prehospital use. Development of institution-specific prediction models is feasible in this age of data science, provided that predictor-related information is readily collectable. Objective: We aimed to develop a hospital admission prediction model based on patient information that is commonly available during ambulance transport before hospitalization. Methods: Patients transported by ambulance to our ED from April 2018 through March 2019 were enrolled. Candidate predictors were age, sex, chief complaint, vital signs, and patient medical history, all of which were recorded by emergency medical teams during ambulance transport. Patients were divided into two cohorts for derivation (3601/5145, 70.0%) and validation (1544/5145, 30.0%). For statistical models, logistic regression, logistic lasso, random forest, and gradient boosting machine were used. Prediction models were developed in the derivation cohort. Model performance was assessed by area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUROC) and association measures in the validation cohort. Results: Of 5145 patients transported by ambulance, including deaths in the ED and hospital transfers, 2699 (52.5%) required hospital admission. Prediction performance was higher with the addition of predictive factors, attaining the best performance with an AUROC of 0.818 (95% CI 0.792-0.839) with a machine learning model and predictive factors of age, sex, chief complaint, and vital signs. Sensitivity and specificity of this model were 0.744 (95% CI 0.716-0.773) and 0.745 (95% CI 0.709-0.776), respectively. Conclusions: For patients transferred to EDs, we developed a well-performing hospital admission prediction model based on routinely collected prehospital information including chief complaints.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
038	Toward cross-platform electronic health record-driven phenotyping using Clinical Quality Language	Introduction: Electronic health record (EHR)-driven phenotyping is a critical first step in generating biomedical knowledge from EHR data. Despite recent progress, current phenotyping approaches are manual, time-consuming, error-prone, and platform-specific. This results in duplication of effort and highly variable results across systems and institutions, and is not scalable or portable. In this work, we investigate how the nascent Clinical Quality Language (CQL) can address these issues and enable high-throughput, cross-platform phenotyping. Methods: We selected a clinically validated heart failure (HF) phenotype definition and translated it into CQL, then developed a CQL execution engine to integrate with the Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics (OHDSI) platform. We executed the phenotype definition at two large academic medical centers, Northwestern Medicine and Weill Cornell Medicine, and conducted results verification (n = 100) to determine precision and recall. We additionally executed the same phenotype definition against two different data platforms, OHDSI and Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR), using the same underlying dataset and compared the results. Results: CQL is expressive enough to represent the HF phenotype definition, including Boolean and aggregate operators, and temporal relationships between data elements. The language design also enabled the implementation of a custom execution engine with relative ease, and results verification at both sites revealed that precision and recall were both 100%. Cross-platform execution resulted in identical patient cohorts generated by both data platforms. Conclusions: CQL supports the representation of arbitrarily complex phenotype definitions, and our execution engine implementation demonstrated cross-platform execution against two widely used clinical data platforms. The language thus has the potential to help address current limitations with portability in EHR-driven phenotyping and scale in learning health systems.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
039	Handling missing data in modelling	Missing information is a major drawback in analyzing data collected in many routine health care settings. Multiple imputation assuming a missing at random mechanism is a popular method to handle missing data. The missing at random assumption cannot be confirmed from the observed data alone, hence the need for	CII		

	<p>quality of clinician-prescribed routine care. Sensitivity analysis of departure from missing at random assumption</p>	<p>sensitivity analysis to assess robustness of inference. However, sensitivity analysis is rarely conducted and reported in practice. We analyzed routine paediatric data collected during a cluster randomized trial conducted in Kenyan hospitals. We imputed missing patient and clinician-level variables assuming the missing at random mechanism. We also imputed missing clinician-level variables assuming a missing not at random mechanism. We incorporated opinions from 15 clinical experts in the form of prior distributions and shift parameters in the delta adjustment method. An interaction between trial intervention arm and follow-up time, hospital, clinician and patient-level factors were included in a proportional odds random-effects analysis model. We performed these analyses using R functions derived from the jomo package. Parameter estimates from multiple imputation under the missing at random mechanism were similar to multiple imputation estimates assuming the missing not at random mechanism. Our inferences were insensitive to departures from the missing at random assumption using either the prior distributions or shift parameters sensitivity analysis approach.</p>			
040	<p>Collaborative Cloud Computing Framework for Health Data with Open Source Technologies</p>	<p>The proliferation of sensor technologies and advancements in data collection methods have enabled the accumulation of very large amounts of data. Increasingly, these datasets are considered for scientific research. However, the design of the system architecture to achieve high performance in terms of parallelization, query processing time, aggregation of heterogeneous data types (e.g., time series, images, structured data, among others), and difficulty in reproducing scientific research remain a major challenge. This is specifically true for health sciences research, where the systems must be i) easy to use with the flexibility to manipulate data at the most granular level, ii) agnostic of programming language kernel, iii) scalable, and iv) compliant with the HIPAA privacy law. In this paper, we review the existing literature for such big data systems for scientific research in health sciences and identify the gaps of the current system landscape. We propose a novel architecture for software-hardware-data ecosystem using open source technologies such as Apache Hadoop, Kubernetes and JupyterHub in a distributed environment. We also evaluate the system using a large clinical data set of 69M patients.</p>	CII		
041	<p>NEDD: A network embedding based method for predicting drug-disease associations</p>	<p>Background: Drug discovery is known for the large amount of money and time it consumes and the high risk it takes. Drug repositioning has, therefore, become a popular approach to save time and cost by finding novel indications for approved drugs. In order to distinguish these novel indications accurately in a great many of latent associations between drugs and diseases, it is necessary to exploit abundant heterogeneous information about drugs and diseases. Results: In this article, we propose a meta-path-based computational method called NEDD to predict novel associations between drugs and diseases using heterogeneous information. First, we construct a heterogeneous network as an undirected graph by integrating drug-drug similarity, disease-disease similarity, and known drug-disease associations. NEDD uses meta paths of different lengths to explicitly capture the indirect relationships, or high order proximity, within drugs and diseases, by which the low dimensional representation vectors of drugs and diseases are obtained. NEDD then uses a random forest classifier to predict novel associations between drugs and diseases. Conclusions: The experiments on a gold standard dataset which contains 1933 validated drug-disease associations show that NEDD produces superior prediction results compared with the state-of-the-art approaches.</p>		CE1	<p>Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.</p>
042	<p>See with your eyes, hear with your ears and listen to your heart: Moving from dyadic teamwork interaction towards a more effective team</p>	<p>The scientific study of teamwork in the context of long-term spaceflight has uncovered a considerable amount of knowledge over the past 20 years. Although much is known about the underlying factors and processes of teamwork, much is left to be discovered for teams who operate in extreme isolation conditions during spaceflights. Thus, special considerations must be made to enhance teamwork and team well-being for long-term missions during which the team will live and work together. Being affected by both mental and physical stress during interactional context conversations might have a direct or indirect impact on team members' speech acoustics, facial expressions, lexical choices and their physiological responses. The purpose of this article is (a) to illustrate the relationship between the modalities of vocal-acoustic, language and physiological cues during stressful teammate conversations, (b) to delineate promising research paths to help further</p>		CE1	<p>Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.</p>

	<p>cohesion and collaboration in long-term spaceflights under stressful conditions</p>	<p>our insights into understanding the underlying mechanisms of high team cohesion during spaceflights, (c) to build upon our preliminary experimental results that were recently published, using a dyadic team corpus during the demanding operational task of “diffusing a bomb” and (d) to outline a list of parameters that should be considered and examined that would be useful in spaceflights for team-effectiveness research in similarly stressful conditions. Under this view, it is expected to take us one step towards building an extremely non-intrusive and relatively inexpensive set of measures deployed in ground analogs to assess complex and dynamic behavior of individuals.</p>			
043	<p>COVID-19 scenario modelling for the mitigation of capacity-dependent deaths in intensive care</p>	<p>Managing healthcare demand and capacity is especially difficult in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, where limited intensive care resources can be overwhelmed by a large number of cases requiring admission in a short space of time. If patients are unable to access this specialist resource, then death is a likely outcome. In appreciating these ‘capacity-dependent’ deaths, this paper reports on the clinically-led development of a stochastic discrete event simulation model designed to capture the key dynamics of the intensive care admissions process for COVID-19 patients. With application to a large public hospital in England during an early stage of the pandemic, the purpose of this study was to estimate the extent to which such capacity-dependent deaths can be mitigated through demand-side initiatives involving non-pharmaceutical interventions and supply-side measures to increase surge capacity. Based on information available at the time, results suggest that total capacity-dependent deaths can be reduced by 75% through a combination of increasing capacity from 45 to 100 beds, reducing length of stay by 25%, and flattening the peak demand to 26 admissions per day. Accounting for the additional ‘capacity-independent’ deaths, which occur even when appropriate care is available within the intensive care setting, yields an aggregate reduction in total deaths of 30%. The modelling tool, which is freely available and open source, has since been used to support COVID-19 response planning at a number of healthcare systems within the UK National Health Service.</p>	<p>CI1</p>		
044	<p>A Survey on Deep Transfer Learning to Edge Computing for Mitigating the COVID-19 Pandemic: DTL-EC</p>	<p>Global Health sometimes faces pandemics as are currently facing COVID-19 disease. The spreading and infection factors of this disease are very high. A huge number of people from most of the countries are infected within six months from its first report of appearance and it keeps spreading. The required systems are not ready up to some stages for any pandemic; therefore, mitigation with existing capacity becomes necessary. On the other hand, modern-era largely depends on Artificial Intelligence(AI) including Data Science; and Deep Learning(DL) is one of the current flag-bearer of these techniques. It could use to mitigate COVID-19 like pandemics in terms of stop spread, diagnosis of the disease, drug & vaccine discovery, treatment, patient care, and many more. But this DL requires large datasets as well as powerful computing resources. A shortage of reliable datasets of a running pandemic is a common phenomenon. So, Deep Transfer Learning(DTL) would be effective as it learns from one task and could work on another task. In addition, Edge Devices(ED) such as IoT, Webcam, Drone, Intelligent Medical Equipment, Robot, etc. are very useful in a pandemic situation. These types of equipment make the infrastructures sophisticated and automated which helps to cope with an outbreak. But these are equipped with low computing resources, so, applying DL is also a bit challenging; therefore, DTL also would be effective there. This article scholarly studies the potentiality and challenges of these issues. It has described relevant technical backgrounds and reviews of the related recent state-of-the-art. This article also draws a pipeline of DTL over Edge Computing as a future scope to assist the mitigation of any pandemic.</p>		<p>CE5</p>	<p>Survey</p>
045	<p>Machine learning techniques with eeg and EEG data: An exploratory study</p>	<p>Electrocardiography (ECG) and electroencephalography (EEG) are powerful tools in medicine for the analysis of various diseases. The emergence of affordable ECG and EEG sensors and ubiquitous mobile devices provides an opportunity to make such analysis accessible to everyone. In this paper, we propose the implementation of a neural network-based method for the automatic identification of the relationship between the previously known conditions of older adults and the different features calculated from the various signals. The data were collected using a smartphone and low-cost ECG and EEG sensors during the performance of the timed-up and go test. Different patterns related to the features extracted, such as</p>		<p>CE1</p>	<p>Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.</p>

		heart rate, heart rate variability, average QRS amplitude, average R-R interval, and average R-S interval from ECG data, and the frequency and variability from the EEG data were identified. A combination of these parameters allowed us to identify the presence of certain diseases accurately. The analysis revealed that the different institutions and ages were mainly identified. Still, the various diseases and groups of diseases were difficult to recognize, because the frequency of the different diseases was rare in the considered population. Therefore, the test should be performed with more people to achieve better results.			
046	Hi, can I help? Exploring how to design a mental health chatbot for youths	Chatbots represent new opportunities for low-threshold preventive mental health support to youths. To provide needed knowledge regarding how to design chatbots for this purpose, we present an exploratory design study where we designed and evaluated a prototype chatbot to complement the work of school nurses in the school health service. The prototype was designed with particular regard for preventive mental health support. The design process involved school nurses, digital health workers, and youths. Through user insight activities, we identified four types of support to be provided through the chatbot: informational, relational, processual, and referral. We explored these four types of support through concept development and prototyping. These results are discussed as a potential basis for a framework for understanding youths' needs regarding chatbots for preventive mental health support. When discussing the study findings, we point out how the study contributes to theory and practice and suggest avenues for future research.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
047	Subspecies niche specialization in the oral microbiome is associated with nasopharyngeal carcinoma risk	Oral health and changes in the oral microbiome have been associated with both local and systemic cancer. Poor oral hygiene is a known risk factor for nasopharyngeal carcinoma (NPC), a virally associated head and neck cancer endemic to southern China. We explored the relationship between NPC and the oral microbiome using 16S rRNA sequencing in a study of 499 NPC patients and 495 population-based age and sex frequency-matched controls from an area of endemicity of Southern China. We found a significant reduction in community richness in cases compared to that in controls. Differences in the overall microbial community structure between cases and controls could not be explained by other potential confounders; disease status explained 5 times more variation in the unweighted UniFrac distance than the next most explanatory variable. In feature-based analyses, we identified a pair of coexclusing <i>Granulicatella adiacens</i> amplicon sequence variants (ASVs) which were strongly associated with NPC status and differed by a single nucleotide. The <i>G. adiacens</i> variant an individual carried was also associated with the overall microbial community based on beta diversity. Co-occurrence analysis suggested the two <i>G. adiacens</i> ASVs sit at the center of two coexclusing clusters of closely related organisms. Our results suggest there are differences in the oral microbiomes between NPC patients and healthy controls, and these may be associated with both a loss of microbial diversity and niche specialization among closely related commensals. IMPORTANCE The relationship between oral health and the risk of nasopharyngeal carcinoma (NPC) was previously established. However, the role of oral microbiome has not been evaluated in the disease in a large epidemiological study. This paper clearly establishes a difference in the oral microbiomes between NPC patients and healthy controls which cannot be explained by other confounding factors. It furthermore identifies a pair of closely related coexclusing organisms associated with the disease, highlighting the importance of modern methods for single-nucleotide resolution in 16S rRNA sequence characterization. To the best of our knowledge, this is one of the first examples of cancer-associated niche specialization of the oral microbiome.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
048	Digital health ecosystems: An epochal review of practice-oriented research	This article describes an epochal review of research literature on practice-oriented digital health ecosystems that have emerged during the period between 1998 and 2018. Practice-orientation refers to efforts that have resulted in positive impact and transformations in the delivery of healthcare. The review is epochal in the sense that there have been 3 major stages of innovation and diffusion in digital health that are identified. The year 1998 was deemed a significant starting point for the literature search because it marked the introduction of the term e-health. The main objective of this review is to track the evolution of digital health and the conspicuous developments in the field - crucial steps to get a grasp of the key		CE5	Revisão da literatura.

		issues involving the delivery of healthcare. The article includes a general discussion of these various key issues and sensitizing concepts. The sense-making thus shed some light on the areas of enquiry, which are central to identifying the direction in which the practice of healthcare is headed. These areas of enquiry often referred to as 'substantive areas' in qualitative research terminology, were identified as 'electronic medical records', 'health cloud', 'data analytics', 'Internet-enabled devices', and other 'emerging information technologies'. The article concludes with a synthesis of key inferences drawn from the epochal review. The digital disruption of healthcare has created necessary conditions for its offering as a global, interoperable service.			
049	Improving geographical accessibility modeling for operational use by local health actors	Background: Geographical accessibility to health facilities remains one of the main barriers to access care in rural areas of the developing world. Although methods and tools exist to model geographic accessibility, the lack of basic geographic information prevents their widespread use at the local level for targeted program implementation. The aim of this study was to develop very precise, context-specific estimates of geographic accessibility to care in a rural district of Madagascar to help with the design and implementation of interventions that improve access for remote populations. Methods: We used a participatory approach to map all the paths, residential areas, buildings and rice fields on OpenStreetMap (OSM). We estimated shortest routes from every household in the District to the nearest primary health care center (PHC) and community health site (CHS) with the Open Source Routing Machine (OSMR) tool. Then, we used remote sensing methods to obtain a high resolution land cover map, a digital elevation model and rainfall data to model travel speed. Travel speed models were calibrated with field data obtained by GPS tracking in a sample of 168 walking routes. Model results were used to predict travel time to seek care at PHCs and CHSs for all the shortest routes estimated earlier. Finally, we integrated geographical accessibility results into an e-health platform developed with R Shiny. Results: We mapped over 100,000 buildings, 23,000 km of footpaths, and 4925 residential areas throughout Ifanadiana district; these data are freely available on OSM. We found that over three quarters of the population lived more than one hour away from a PHC, and 10-15% lived more than 1 h away from a CHS. Moreover, we identified areas in the North and East of the district where the nearest PHC was further than 5 h away, and vulnerable populations across the district with poor geographical access (> 1 h) to both PHCs and CHSs. Conclusion: Our study demonstrates how to improve geographical accessibility modeling so that results can be context-specific and operationally actionable by local health actors. The importance of such approaches is paramount for achieving universal health coverage (UHC) in rural areas throughout the world.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
050	Human-centered design for global health equity	As digital technologies play a growing role in healthcare, human-centered design is gaining traction in global health. Amid concern that this trend offers little more than buzzwords, our paper clarifies how human-centered design matters for global health equity. First, we contextualize how the design discipline differs from conventional approaches to research and innovation in global health, by emphasizing craft skills and iterative methods that reframe the relationship between design and implementation. Second, while there is no definitive agreement about what the 'human' part means, it often implies stakeholder participation, augmenting human skills, and attention to human values. Finally, we consider the practical relevance of human-centered design by reflecting on our experiences accompanying health workers through over seventy digital health initiatives. In light of this material, we describe human-centered design as a flexible yet disciplined approach to innovation that prioritizes people's needs and concrete experiences in the design of complex systems.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
051	Data integration in the Brazilian public health system for tuberculosis: Use	Background: Interoperability of health information systems is a challenge due to the heterogeneity of existing systems at both the technological and semantic levels of their data. The lack of existing data about interoperability disrupts intra-unit and inter-unit medical operations as well as creates challenges in conducting studies on existing data. The goal is to exchange data while providing the same meaning for data from different sources. Objective: To find ways to solve this challenge, this research paper proposes an interoperability solution for the tuberculosis treatment		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto

	<p>of the semantic web to establish interoperability</p>	<p>and follow-up scenario in Brazil using Semantic Web technology supported by an ontology. Methods: The entities of the ontology were allocated under the definitions of Basic Formal Ontology. Brazilian tuberculosis applications were tagged with entities from the resulting ontology. Results: An interoperability layer was developed to retrieve data with the same meaning and in a structured way enabling semantic and functional interoperability. Conclusions: Health professionals could use the data gathered from several data sources to enhance the effectiveness of their actions and decisions, as shown in a practical use case to integrate tuberculosis data in the State of São Paulo.</p>			
052	<p>Enabling agile clinical and translational data warehousing: Platform development and evaluation</p>	<p>Background: Modern data-driven medical research provides new insights into the development and course of diseases and enables novel methods of clinical decision support. Clinical and translational data warehouses, such as Informatics for Integrating Biology and the Bedside (i2b2) and tranSMART, are important infrastructure components that provide users with unified access to the large heterogeneous data sets needed to realize this and support use cases such as cohort selection, hypothesis generation, and ad hoc data analysis. Objective: Often, different warehousing platforms are needed to support different use cases and different types of data. Moreover, to achieve an optimal data representation within the target systems, specific domain knowledge is needed when designing data-loading processes. Consequently, informaticians need to work closely with clinicians and researchers in short iterations. This is a challenging task as installing and maintaining warehousing platforms can be complex and time consuming. Furthermore, data loading typically requires significant effort in terms of data preprocessing, cleansing, and restructuring. The platform described in this study aims to address these challenges. Methods: We formulated system requirements to achieve agility in terms of platform management and data loading. The derived system architecture includes a cloud infrastructure with unified management interfaces for multiple warehouse platforms and a data-loading pipeline with a declarative configuration paradigm and meta-loading approach. The latter compiles data and configuration files into forms required by existing loading tools, thereby automating a wide range of data restructuring and cleansing tasks. We demonstrated the fulfillment of the requirements and the originality of our approach by an experimental evaluation and a comparison with previous work. Results: The platform supports both i2b2 and tranSMART with built-in security. Our experiments showed that the loading pipeline accepts input data that cannot be loaded with existing tools without preprocessing. Moreover, it lowered efforts significantly, reducing the size of configuration files required by factors of up to 22 for tranSMART and 1135 for i2b2. The time required to perform the compilation process was roughly equivalent to the time required for actual data loading. Comparison with other tools showed that our solution was the only tool fulfilling all requirements. Conclusions: Our platform significantly reduces the efforts required for managing clinical and translational warehouses and for loading data in various formats and structures, such as complex entity-attribute-value structures often found in laboratory data. Moreover, it facilitates the iterative refinement of data representations in the target platforms, as the required configuration files are very compact. The quantitative measurements presented are consistent with our experiences of significantly reduced efforts for building warehousing platforms in close cooperation with medical researchers. Both the cloud-based hosting infrastructure and the data-loading pipeline are available to the community as open source software with comprehensive documentation.</p>	CII		
053	<p>Emerging wireless sensor networks and internet of things technologies— foundations of smart healthcare</p>	<p>Future smart healthcare systems – often referred to as Internet of Medical Things (IoMT) – will combine a plethora of wireless devices and applications that use wireless communication technologies to enable the exchange of healthcare data. Smart healthcare requires sufficient bandwidth, reliable and secure communication links, energy-efficient operations, and Quality of Service (QoS) support. The integration of Internet of Things (IoT) solutions into healthcare systems can significantly increase intelligence, flexibility, and interoperability. This work provides an extensive survey on emerging IoT communication standards and technologies suitable for smart healthcare applications. A particular emphasis has been given to low-power wireless technologies as a key enabler for energy-efficient</p>		CE5	Survey

		IoT-based healthcare systems. Major challenges in privacy and security are also discussed. A particular attention is devoted to crowdsourcing/crowdsensing, envisaged as tools for the rapid collection of massive quantities of medical data. Finally, open research challenges and future perspectives of IoMT are presented.			
054	IT vendors' legitimation strategies and market share: The case of EMR systems	This study investigates the legitimation strategies adopted by information technology (IT) vendors and their respective influence on market share. We conducted an analysis of the public discourse on websites of top Electronic Medical Record (EMR) vendors in Ontario, Canada. A total of 815 segments extracted from these websites were analyzed. Our findings indicate that strategies under the cognitive and pragmatic forms of legitimacy were strongly represented in the EMR vendors' discourses compared with regulative and normative strategies. Furthermore, the link between legitimation strategies and market share has not yet been clearly established. Implications for practice and research are discussed.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
055	Developing the infrastructure to support the optimisation of antibiotic prescribing using the learning healthcare system to improve healthcare services in the provision of primary care in England	Introduction The learning healthcare system (LHS) underpinned by data analysis and feedback to clinical care providers is thought to improve quality of care. The work aimed to implement an LHS for antibiotic prescribing in primary care in England. Method Deidentified patient-level data from general practices were processed and analysed at regular intervals (fortnightly increments). A dashboard application was developed and implemented displaying analytical graphics to give periodic feedback to clinicians, tailored to each clinical site. Benchmarking parameters were established by the analysis of two large national primary care datasets allowing peer-to-peer comparisons. To date, the dashboard is available to 70 English practices. Conclusions Successful implementation and uptake of the secure technical LHS infrastructure for the analysis and feedback to clinicians of their antibiotic prescribing demonstrate a great appetite for this type of frequent prescribing review in primary care, combining advanced data analytics with tailored feedback.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto
056	Experimental Measurements of Ultrasound Attenuation in Human Chest Wall and Assessment of the Mechanical Index for Lung Ultrasound	Knowledge of the acoustic attenuation characteristics of the chest wall is necessary to estimate the acoustic exposure at the pleural surface during lung ultrasound and is useful in the prediction of bio-effects (e.g., pulmonary capillary hemorrhage) and the development of safe, effective lung imaging. Currently, this property is not well characterized in humans. The aim of this work was to characterize ultrasonic attenuation in human chest wall such that the ultrasound exposures of the lung can be estimated for clinically relevant conditions. In this study, we experimentally measured ultrasound transmitted through the intercostal tissue of 15 human cadaver chest wall samples relative to ultrasound transmitted through saline to determine attenuation coefficients for each sample. A GE Vivid 7 diagnostic ultrasound machine (GE Vingmed, Horten, Norway) and 3 S and 5 S phased array probes were used at center frequencies from 1.6 to 5 MHz. The chest wall samples varied in thickness from 2.3–5.5 cm with a median thickness of 3.8 cm. The frequency-normalized attenuation coefficient was approximately 1.44 dB/cm/MHz based on a linear best fit through all attenuation measurements. Attenuation characteristics varied appreciably between samples, and the sample-averaged linear attenuation coefficient was 1.43 ± 0.32 (mean \pm standard deviation) dB/cm/MHz. This attenuation is higher than that previously measured in mammalian chest wall samples (1.1–1.3 dB/cm/MHz for mice and rats) and is much greater than that used by the mechanical index (0.3 dB/cm/MHz). Mechanical index values calculated using saline values de-rated by 0.3 dB/cm/MHz were up to 1.2 MPa/MHz ^{1/2} greater than those calculated using the measured through-tissue ultrasound waves. We conclude that the mechanical index overestimates exposures for lung ultrasound and thus may not be an appropriate dosimetry metric for pulmonary ultrasound.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto
057	A Multi-Organ Nucleus Segmentation	Generalized nucleus segmentation techniques can contribute greatly to reducing the time to develop and validate visual biomarkers for new digital pathology datasets. We summarize the results of MoNuSeg 2018 Challenge whose objective was to develop generalizable nuclei segmentation techniques in digital pathology. The challenge was an official satellite event of the MICCAI 2018 conference in which		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de

	Challenge	32 teams with more than 80 participants from geographically diverse institutes participated. Contestants were given a training set with 30 images from seven organs with annotations of 21,623 individual nuclei. A test dataset with 14 images taken from seven organs, including two organs that did not appear in the training set was released without annotations. Entries were evaluated based on average aggregated Jaccard index (AJI) on the test set to prioritize accurate instance segmentation as opposed to mere semantic segmentation. More than half the teams that completed the challenge outperformed a previous baseline. Among the trends observed that contributed to increased accuracy were the use of color normalization as well as heavy data augmentation. Additionally, fully convolutional networks inspired by variants of U-Net, FCN, and Mask-RCNN were popularly used, typically based on ResNet or VGG base architectures. Watershed segmentation on predicted semantic segmentation maps was a popular post-processing strategy. Several of the top techniques compared favorably to an individual human annotator and can be used with confidence for nuclear morphometrics.			um sistema.
058	Towards generic modelling of hospital wards: Reuse and redevelopment of simple models	Generic simulation models are designed to enable model reuse. We argue that there are two weaknesses within the generic simulation modelling literature. Firstly, that generic models sacrifice the relative simplicity of a bespoke simulation model for flexibility. Secondly, that generic models are published in conceptual form only. If researchers cannot access computer implementation of models, then there is little incentive or benefit to recode one over coding a simpler bespoke simulation model. We introduce an incremental approach to generic modelling in discrete-event simulation. We develop an archetype setting-specific generic model of a hospital ward. The archetype model is first developed and applied in a rehabilitation ward setting. Then a second team applies the model in a specialised intensive care setting. We report the successes, obstacles and redevelopment needed for reuse of the generic model along with how the results of these studies were used to inform healthcare delivery.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto
059	Networked health care: Rethinking value creation in learning health care systems	Creating better value in health care service today is very challenging. The social pressure to do so is real for every health care system and its leadership. Real benefit has been achieved in manufacturing sector work by the use of “value-chain” thinking, which assumes that the work is a series of linked processes necessary to make a product. For those activities in health care systems that are similar, this model may be very helpful. Attempts to “install” the value chain widely in health care systems have, however, been frustrating. As a result, well-meaning leaders seeking better value have resorted to programs of cost reduction, rather than service redesign. Professionals have not been very happy or willing participants. The work of health care service invites an expanded model of value creation, one that better matches the work. This paper proposes a networked architecture that can mobilize and integrate the resources of health care professionals, interested patients, family, and other community members in the delivery and improvement of health care systems. It also suggests how this value-creation architecture might contribute to research and the development of new knowledge. Two cases illustrate the proposed architecture and its implications for system design and practice, technology development, and roles and responsibilities of all actors involved in health care systems. We believe that this model better fits the need of making and improving health care services. This expanded understanding of how value is created invites attention by senior leaders, by those attempting to facilitate the improvement of current systems, by patients and clinicians involved in the daily work of health care service coproduction, by those charged with the preparation and formation of future professionals, by those who measure and conduct research in health care services, and by those leading policy, payment, and reimbursement systems.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto
060	Benchmarking MRI reconstruction neural networks on large public datasets	Deep learning is starting to offer promising results for reconstruction in Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI). A lot of networks are being developed, but the comparisons remain hard because the frameworks used are not the same among studies, the networks are not properly re-trained, and the datasets used are not the same among comparisons. The recent release of a public dataset, fastMRI, consisting of raw k-space data, encouraged us to write a consistent benchmark of several deep neural networks for MR image reconstruction. This paper shows the results obtained for this benchmark, allowing to compare the networks, and links		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.

		the open source implementation of all these networks in Keras. The main finding of this benchmark is that it is beneficial to perform more iterations between the image and the measurement spaces compared to having a deeper per-space network.			
061	Big data analytics and processing platform in Czech Republic healthcare	Big data analytics (BDA) in healthcare has made a positive difference in the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in advancements of analytical capabilities, while lowering the costs of medical care. The aim of this study is to improve the existing healthcare eSystem by implementing a Big Data Analytics (BDA) platform and to meet the requirements of the Czech Republic National Health Service (Tender-Id. VZ0036628, No. Z2017-035520). In addition to providing analytical capabilities on Linux platforms supporting current and near-future AI with machine-learning and data-mining algorithms, there is the need for ethical considerations mandating new ways to preserve privacy, all of which are preconditioned by the growing body of regulations and expectations. The presented BDA platform, has met all requirements (N > 100), including the healthcare industry-standard Transaction Processing Performance Council (TPC-H) decision support benchmark in compliance with the European Union (EU) and the Czech Republic legislations. Currently, the presented Proof of Concept (PoC) that has been upgraded to a production environment has unified isolated parts of Czech Republic healthcare over the past seven months. The reported PoC BDA platform, artefacts, and concepts are transferrable to healthcare systems in other countries interested in developing or upgrading their own national healthcare infrastructure in a cost-effective, secure, scalable and high-performance manner.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto
062	Evaluation of e-learning for medical education in low- and middle-income countries: A systematic review	In low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), e-learning for medical education may alleviate the burden of severe health worker shortages and deliver affordable access to high quality medical education. However, diverse challenges in infrastructure and adoption are encountered when implementing e-learning within medical education in particular. Understanding what constitutes successful e-learning is an important first step for determining its effectiveness. The objective of this study was to systematically review e-learning interventions for medical education in LMICs, focusing on their evaluation and assessment methods. Nine databases were searched for publications from January 2007 to June 2017. We included 52 studies with a total of 12,294 participants. Most e-learning interventions were pilot studies (73%), which mainly employed summative assessments of study participants (83%) and evaluated the e-learning intervention with questionnaires (45%). Study designs, evaluation and assessment methods showed considerable variation, as did the study quality, evaluation periods, outcome and effectiveness measures. Included studies mainly utilized subjective measures and custom-built evaluation frameworks, which resulted in both low comparability and poor validity. The majority of studies self-concluded that they had had an effective e-learning intervention, thus indicating potential benefits of e-learning for LMICs. However, MERSQI and NOS ratings revealed the low quality of the studies' evidence for comparability, evaluation instrument validity, study outcomes and participant blinding. Many e-learning interventions were small-scale and conducted as short-termed pilots. More rigorous evaluation methods for e-learning implementations in LMICs are needed to understand the strengths and shortcomings of e-learning for medical education in low-resource contexts. Valid and reliable evaluations are the foundation to guide and improve e-learning interventions, increase their sustainability, alleviate shortages in health care workers and improve the quality of medical care in LMICs.		CE5	Revisão sistemática da literatura.
063	A Design Study to Improve user Experience of a Procedure Booking Software in Healthcare	In the era of technology-driven healthcare delivery and the proliferation of e-health systems, procedure booking software is becoming common. Procedure booking software (PBS) affects healthcare delivery by improving health care efficiency and outcomes, while cutting costs. Therefore, poor software design for PBS, especially if it is designed for important and critical appointments such as cardiac catheterization operations, creates stress for physicians and may result in their rejection of this technology. Moreover, if the system design forces them to spend more time documenting health information, physicians would then tend to prefer face-to-face interaction with patients. Software with poor usability increases the workload of physicians thus reducing system efficiency. So designing a useful and effective web user interface for such software is an essential requirement for health		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto

		websites. The aim of this paper is to design and develop a PBS as a case study using the health systems design (HSD) tool. HSD is a validated design tool for creating PBS based on physician behavior and persona. The applicability of a PBS design is explored by physicians evaluated. The PBS design was evaluated in terms of objective and subjective characteristics and user experience attributes. Test participants were divided into two groups: specialists and fellows. The results show that there was no significant difference between participants in either group. All were able to complete the tasks successfully with a minimum amount of time, clicks, and errors indicating that the effectiveness, efficiency and cognitive load were similar for all participants. User satisfaction yielded a score of 86 on the System Usability Scale (SUS), putting it in the A Grade. Also, user experience attributes demonstrated that participants were satisfied using the proposed design system.			
064	Facial Expression Rendering in Medical Training Simulators: Current Status and Future Directions	Recent technological advances in robotic sensing and actuation methods have prompted development of a range of new medical training simulators with multiple feedback modalities. Learning to interpret facial expressions of a patient during medical examinations or procedures has been one of the key focus areas in medical training. This article reviews facial expression rendering systems in medical training simulators that have been reported to date. Facial expression rendering approaches in other domains are also summarized to incorporate the knowledge from those works into developing systems for medical training simulators. Classifications and comparisons of medical training simulators with facial expression rendering are presented, and important design features, merits and limitations are outlined. Medical educators, students and developers are identified as the three key stakeholders involved with these systems and their considerations and needs are presented. Physical-virtual (hybrid) approaches provide multimodal feedback, present accurate facial expression rendering, and can simulate patients of different age, gender and ethnicity group; makes it more versatile than virtual and physical systems. The overall findings of this review and proposed future directions are beneficial to researchers interested in initiating or developing such facial expression rendering systems in medical training simulators.		CE5	Revisão da literatura.
065	A topic-based hierarchical publish/subscribe messaging middleware for COVID-19 detection in X-ray image and its metadata	Putting real-time medical data processing applications into practice comes with some challenges such as scalability and performance. Processing medical images from different collaborators is an example of such applications, in which chest X-ray data are processed to extract knowledge. It is not easy to process data and get the required information in real time using central processing techniques when data get very large in size. In this paper, real-time data are filtered and forwarded to the right processing node by using the proposed topic-based hierarchical publish/subscribe messaging middleware in the distributed scalable network of collaborating computation nodes instead of classical approaches of centralized computation. This enables processing streaming medical data in near real time and makes a warning system possible. End users have the capability of filtering/searching. The returned search results can be images (COVID-19 or non-COVID-19) and their meta-data are gender and age. Here, COVID-19 is detected using a novel capsule network-based model from chest X-ray images. This middleware allows for a smaller search space as well as shorter times for obtaining search results.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto
066	Using Dissemination and Implementation Strategies to Evaluate Requirement Elicitation Guidelines: A Case Study in a Bed Management	Clinical software is a fundamental tool for supporting healthcare systems because it improves the quality of patient care and automatizes the most frequently performed clinical tasks. Nevertheless, since health systems include various components, such as supplies, transportation, laboratories, and interoperability, eliciting the most critical requirements for understanding the problem that the clinical software must solve is quite a complex task. Indeed, the requirement elicitation process may directly determine the success or failure of the clinical software. In this article, we present the DI framework, a methodology that uses dissemination and implementation strategies to recommend guidelines for the elicitation of clinical software requirements. The objective of this framework is to support software developers in the identification of key requirements with the goal of more holistically understanding the problem to be solved by the clinical software. We evaluated the DI framework with a real case study related to a bed management		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.

	System	system. We employed a usability instrument with 50 clinicians to evaluate tasks in software modules that represent clinical priorities defined by stakeholders. The results indicate that the perception of usability by end users is acceptable, suggesting that the evaluated tasks satisfy the established clinical priorities. The DI framework provides a starting point for research and discussion about the contribution of dissemination and implementation strategies to the body of knowledge about requirement engineering.			
067	Data Classification for Secure Mobile Health Data Collecting Systems	Data collected in Mobile Health Data Collections Systems (MHDCS) are diverse, both in terms of type and value. This calls for different data protection measures to meet security goals of confidentiality, integrity, and availability. The majority of commonly used open-source MHDCS track and monitor individuals over a while. It is therefore important to have sensitive data defined and proper security measures identified. We propose a data classification model as a basis for secure design and implementation. Our method combines interviews with case studies. The case studies focused on three of the widely used MHDCS platforms in low-resource settings; that is Muzima, Open Data Kit (ODK), and District Health Information Software (DHIS) 2 Tracker Capture. Interviews with domain experts helped define the sensitivity of data in MHDCS. The proposed data classification model provides for three sensitivity levels: public, confidential, and critical. The model uses context information and multiple parameters as inputs to a classification scheme that maps data to sensitivity levels. The generated data classifications are intended to guide developers and users to build security into MHDCS starting from the early stages of the software development life cycle.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
068	Classification of Proactive Personality: Text Mining Based on Weibo Text and Short-Answer Questions Text	This study focused on the topic of predicting 'proactive personality'. With 901 participants selected by cluster sampling method, targeted short-answer questions text and participants' social media post text (Weibo) were obtained while participants' labels of proactive personality were evaluated by experts. In order to make classification, five machine learning algorithms included Support Vector Machine (SVM), XGBoost, K-Nearest-Neighbors (KNN), Naive Bayes (NB) and Logistic Regression (LR) were deployed. Seven different indicators, which include Accuracy (ACC), F1-score (F1), Sensitivity (SEN), Specificity (SPE), Positive Predictive Value (PPV), Negative Predictive Value (NPV) and Area under Curve (AUC), combined with hierarchical cross-validation were also used to make the comprehensive evaluation of models. With participants' Weibo text and short-answer questions text, we proposed a new approach to classify individuals' proactive personality based on text mining technology. The results showed that short-answer questions + Weibo text datasets had the best performance, followed by short-answer questions text datasets, while the outcome of Weibo text datasets were the worst. However, it is noteworthy that Weibo text has the highest average score on the SPE, which indicated that Weibo text played an important role in identifying individuals with low proactive personality. With Weibo text, SEN was also improved compared with only applying short-answer questions text. In addition, among all three datasets, the indicator SPE is always higher than SEN, indicating this text classification approach was more competent for identifying college students with low proactive personality. As for algorithms, Support Vector Machine and Logistic Regression showed steadier performance compared with other algorithms.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto
069	A Survey on Blockchain-Based Self-Sovereign Patient Identity in Healthcare	Convergence of physical and digital identity and integration of various individual records, such as patient data, into a united repository remains a serious challenge. On one hand, collecting relevant data can help clinicians, specialists and healthcare service providers to facilitate care for patients. On the other hand, Self-Sovereign identity and the right to control personal data comes into question, because patients do not handle their data explicitly. Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) is a novel method which would allow to securely record time-stamped data and enable patient-driven health and identity records. In this paper, we review the state-of-the-art in Blockchain (BC)-based self-sovereignty and patient data records in healthcare. Our motivation is to investigate the potential of BC technology for use in the patient data and identity management. As a distributed decentralized technology, BC can be very beneficial, giving patients control over their own data and self-sovereign identity. To the extent of our knowledge, there is no literature		CE5	Survey

		covering the same concerns. More specifically, the focus is on solutions that aim the realization of holistic BC-based Electronic Health Records (EHR) and Patient Health Records (PHR). EHR and PHR are used to record patient data, such as the doctor's notes upon a visit and radiology images. Hence, they include critical information regarding patient's privacy and identity. Therefore, development of pure decentralized Healthcare Information Systems (HIS) is a great challenge in terms of architectural and technical structure of the systems. Designing robust and reliable EHR and PHR, which represent the foundation of many other healthcare services, relies on carefully finding the balance in a trade-off between many factors, such as level of decentralization, privacy, scalability and data throughput. In this paper, we review the state-of-the-art and provide an analysis on the design trade-offs.			
070	Blockchain for Industry 4.0: A comprehensive review	Due to the proliferation of ICT during the last few decades, there is an exponential increase in the usage of various smart applications such as smart farming, smart healthcare, supply-chain logistics, business, tourism and hospitality, energy management etc. However, for all the aforementioned applications, security and privacy are major concerns keeping in view of the usage of the open channel, i.e., Internet for data transfer. Although many security solutions and standards have been proposed over the years to enhance the security levels of aforementioned smart applications, but the existing solutions are either based upon the centralized architecture (having single point of failure) or having high computation and communication costs. Moreover, most of the existing security solutions have focussed only on few aspects and fail to address scalability, robustness, data storage, network latency, auditability, immutability, and traceability. To handle the aforementioned issues, blockchain technology can be one of the solutions. Motivated from these facts, in this paper, we present a systematic review of various blockchain-based solutions and their applicability in various Industry 4.0-based applications. Our contributions in this paper are in four fold. Firstly, we explored the current state-of-the-art solutions in the blockchain technology for the smart applications. Then, we illustrated the reference architecture used for the blockchain applicability in various Industry 4.0 applications. Then, merits and demerits of the traditional security solutions are also discussed in comparison to their countermeasures. Finally, we provided a comparison of existing blockchain-based security solutions using various parameters to provide deep insights to the readers about its applicability in various applications.		CE5	Revisão sistemática da literatura.
071	What support do systematic reviews provide for evidence-informed teaching about software engineering practice?	Background: The adoption of the evidence-based research paradigm by software engineering researchers has created a growing knowledge base provided by the outcomes from systematic reviews. Aim: We set out to identify and catalogue a sample of the knowledge provided by systematic reviews, to determine what support they can provide for an evidence-informed approach to teaching about software engineering practice. Method: We undertook a tertiary study (a mapping study of systematic reviews) covering the period to the end of 2015. We identified and catalogued those reviews that had findings or made recommendations that were considered relevant to teaching about industry practice. Results: We examined a sample of 276 systematic reviews, selecting 49 for which we could clearly identify practice-oriented findings and recommendations that were supported by the data analysis provided in the review. We have classified these against established software engineering education knowledge categories and discuss the extent and forms of knowledge provided for each category. Conclusion: While systematic reviews can provide knowledge that can inform teaching about practice, relatively few systematic reviews present the outcomes in a form suitable for this purpose. Using a suitable format for presenting a summary of outcomes could improve this. Additionally, the increasing number of published systematic reviews suggests that there is a need for greater coordination regarding the cataloguing of their findings and recommendations.		CE5	Revisão da literatura.
072	Precision Medicine Informatics	Precision medicine (PM) is an emerging approach that appears with the impression of changing the existing paradigm of medical practice. Recent advances in technological innovations and genetics and the growing availability of health data have set a new pace of the research and impose a set of new requirements on the different stakeholders. Some studies are available that discuss about the different		CE5	Survey

	Principles, Prospects, and Challenges	aspects of PM. Nevertheless, a holistic representation of those aspects deemed to confer with the technological perspective, in relation to the applications and challenges, have been mostly ignored. In this context, this paper surveys the advances in PM from the informatics viewpoint and reviews the enabling tools and techniques in a categorized manner. In addition, the study discusses how other technological paradigms, which include big data, artificial intelligence, and the internet of things, can be exploited to advance the potentials of PM. Furthermore, the paper provides some guidelines for future research for a seamless implementation and a wide-scale deployment of PM based on the identified open issues and the associated challenges. As a result, the paper proposes an integrated holistic framework for PM motivating informatics researchers to design their relevant research work in an appropriate context.			
073	Physiological Closed-Loop Control (PCLC) Systems: Review of a Modern Frontier in Automation	Over the past decade, there has been an unprecedented international focus on improved quality and availability of medical care, which has reignited interest in clinical automation and drawn researchers toward novel solutions in the field of physiological closed-loop control systems (PCLCs). Today, multidisciplinary groups of expert scientists, engineers, clinicians, mathematicians, and policy-makers are combining their knowledge and experience to develop both the next generation of PCLC-based medical equipment and a collaborative commercial/academic infrastructure to support this rapidly expanding frontier. In the following article, we provide a robust introduction to the various aspects of this growing field motivated by the recent and ongoing work supporting two leading technologies: The artificial pancreas (AP) and automated anesthesia. Following a brief high-level overview of the main concepts in automated therapy and some relevant tools from systems and control theory, we explore-separately-the developments, challenges, state-of-The-Art, and probable directions for AP and automated anesthesia systems. We then close the review with a consideration of the common lessons gleaned from these ventures and the implications they present for future investigations and adjacent research.		CE5	Revisão da literatura
074	The Battle of the Video Codecs in the Healthcare Domain - A Comparative Performance Evaluation Study Leveraging VVC and AV1	Video compression is the core technology in mobile (mHealth) and electronic (eHealth) health video streaming applications. With global video traffic projected to reach 82% of all Internet traffic by 2022, there is a strong need to develop efficient compression algorithms to accommodate expected future growth. For the first time in decades, and especially since ISO/IEC MPEG and ITU-T VCEG expert groups strategically joined forces to develop the highly successful H.264/AVC standard, we have two distinct initiatives competing for the best performing video codec. On the one hand, we have the Alliance for Open Media (AOM) that support a new, royalty free video codec generation, termed AV1, based on VP8 and VP9 efforts. On the other hand, the Joint Video Exploration Team (JVET) has been developing the Versatile Video Codec (VVC) as the successor of the High Efficiency Video Coding (HEVC) standard. At the same time, the breadth of applications utilizing video codecs, involving significant content variability and moving across the video resolution ladder, to satisfy different constraints, have resulted in mixed literature results, with respect to the best performing codec. In this paper, we compare the performance of emerging VVC and AV1 codecs, along with popular HEVC implementations, namely the HEVC Test Model (HM) and x265, as well as earlier, VP9 codec, and investigate their suitability for medical applications. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first performance comparison of emerging VVC and AV1 video codecs for use in the healthcare domain. Experimental evaluation based on three datasets (ultrasound, emergency scenery, and general-purpose videos) demonstrate that VVC outperforms all rival codecs while AV1 achieves better compression efficiency than HEVC in all cases but low-resolution (560×448 @40Hz) ultrasound videos of the common carotid artery. Furthermore, the use of video despeckling prior to ultrasound video compression can provide significant bitrate savings.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
075	Transforming French Electronic Health Records	Background Common data models (CDMs) enable data to be standardized, and facilitate data exchange, sharing, and storage, particularly when the data have been collected via distinct, heterogeneous systems. Moreover, CDMs provide tools for data quality assessment, integration into models, visualization, and analysis. The observational medical outcome partnership (OMOP) provides a CDM for		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.

	<p>into the Observational Medical Outcome Partnership's Common Data Model: A Feasibility Study</p>	<p>organizing and standardizing databases. Common data models not only facilitate data integration but also (and especially for the OMOP model) extends the range of available statistical analyses. Objective This study aimed to evaluate the feasibility of implementing French national electronic health records in the OMOP CDM. Methods The OMOP's specifications were used to audit the source data, specify the transformation into the OMOP CDM, implement an extract-transform-load process to feed data from the French health care system into the OMOP CDM, and evaluate the final database. Results Seventeen vocabularies corresponding to the French context were added to the OMOP CDM's concepts. Three French terminologies were automatically mapped to standardized vocabularies. We loaded nine tables from the OMOP CDM's standardized clinical data section, and three tables from the standardized health system data section. Outpatient and inpatient data from 38,730 individuals were integrated. The median (interquartile range) number of outpatient and inpatient stays per patient was 160 (19-364). Conclusion Our results demonstrated that data from the French national health care system can be integrated into the OMOP CDM. One of the main challenges was the use of international OMOP concepts to annotate data recorded in a French context. The use of local terminologies was an obstacle to conceptual mapping; with the exception of an adaptation of the International Classification of Diseases 10th Revision, the French health care system does not use international terminologies. It would be interesting to extend our present findings to the 65 million people registered in the French health care system.</p>			
076	<p>Home Visits for Children and Adolescents with Uncontrolled Type 1 Diabetes</p>	<p>Background: Home-based video visits were provided over one year as a supplement to in-person care for pediatric type 1 diabetes (T1D) patients with suboptimal glycemic control. We hypothesized that the intervention would be feasible and satisfactory for the target population and would significantly improve hemoglobin A1c (HbA1c) levels and completion of recommended quarterly diabetes clinic visits. Methods: This was a nonrandomized clinical trial. Fifty-seven patients aged 3-17 years with known T1D and HbA1c $\geq 8\%$ (64 mmol/mol) were recruited to receive the intervention. The study population was 49% adolescent (13-17 years old) and 58% publicly insured patients. Video visits were scheduled every 4, 6, or 8 weeks depending on the HbA1c level. HbA1c levels as well as frequencies of clinic visits and of diabetes-related emergency department (ED) and hospital encounters were compared before and after the study. Results: Thirty participants completed 12 months of video visits. The study cohort demonstrated significant improvement in mean HbA1c in both intention-To-Treat (N = 57) analysis (10.8% [95 mmol/mol] to 10.0% [86 mmol/mol], P = 0.01) and per-protocol (N = 30) analysis (10.8% [95 mmol/mol] to 9.6% [81 mmol/mol], P = 0.004). Completion of ≥ 4 annual diabetes clinic visits improved significantly from 21% at baseline to 83% during the study period for the entire cohort, P < 0.0001. The frequency of diabetes-related ED and hospital encounters did not change significantly. Conclusions: Home-based video visits are a feasible supplement to in-person care for children and adolescents with T1D and suboptimal glycemic control and can successfully improve HbA1c levels and adherence to recommended frequency of care in this high-risk clinical population.</p>		CE1	<p>Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.</p>
077	<p>Evaluation of algorithms for Multi-Modality Whole Heart Segmentation: An open-access grand challenge</p>	<p>Knowledge of whole heart anatomy is a prerequisite for many clinical applications. Whole heart segmentation (WHS), which delineates substructures of the heart, can be very valuable for modeling and analysis of the anatomy and functions of the heart. However, automating this segmentation can be challenging due to the large variation of the heart shape, and different image qualities of the clinical data. To achieve this goal, an initial set of training data is generally needed for constructing priors or for training. Furthermore, it is difficult to perform comparisons between different methods, largely due to differences in the datasets and evaluation metrics used. This manuscript presents the methodologies and evaluation results for the WHS algorithms selected from the submissions to the Multi-Modality Whole Heart Segmentation (MM-WHS) challenge, in conjunction with MICCAI 2017. The challenge provided 120 three-dimensional cardiac images covering the whole heart, including 60 CT and 60 MRI volumes, all acquired in clinical environments with manual delineation. Ten algorithms for CT data and eleven algorithms for MRI data, submitted from twelve groups, have been evaluated. The results showed that</p>		CE1	<p>Não deixa explícito o uso de código-abierto.</p>

		the performance of CT WHS was generally better than that of MRI WHS. The segmentation of the substructures for different categories of patients could present different levels of challenge due to the difference in imaging and variations of heart shapes. The deep learning (DL)-based methods demonstrated great potential, though several of them reported poor results in the blinded evaluation. Their performance could vary greatly across different network structures and training strategies. The conventional algorithms, mainly based on multi-atlas segmentation, demonstrated good performance, though the accuracy and computational efficiency could be limited. The challenge, including provision of the annotated training data and the blinded evaluation for submitted algorithms on the test data, continues as an ongoing benchmarking resource via its homepage (www.sdspeople.fudan.edu.cn/zhuangxiahai/0/mmwhs/).			
078	Analysing dependability and performance of a real-world Elastic Search application	Increased complexity in IT, big data, and advanced analytical techniques are some of the trends driving demand for more sophisticated and scalable search technology. Despite Quality of Service (QoS) being a critical success factor in most enterprise software service offerings, it is often not a generic component of the enterprise search software stack. In this paper, we explore enterprise search engine dependability and performance using a real-world company architecture and associated data sourced from an ElasticSearch implementation on Linknovate.com. We propose a Fault Tree model to assess the availability and reliability of the Linknovate.com architecture. The results of the Fault Tree model are fed into a Stochastic Petri Net (SPN) model to analyze how failures and redundancy impact application performance of the use case system. Availability and MTTF were used to evaluate the reliability and throughput was used to evaluate the performance of the target system. The best results for all three metrics were returned in scenarios with high levels of redundancy.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
079	Fast healthcare interoperability resources (fhir) as a meta model to integrate common data models: Development of a tool and quantitative validation study	Background: In a multisite clinical research collaboration, institutions may or may not use the same common data model (CDM) to store clinical data. To overcome this challenge, we proposed to use Health Level 7's Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR) as a meta-CDM-a single standard to represent clinical data. Objective: In this study, we aimed to create an open-source application termed the Clinical Asset Mapping Program for FHIR (CAMP FHIR) to efficiently transform clinical data to FHIR for supporting source-agnostic CDM-to-FHIR mapping. Methods: Mapping with CAMP FHIR involves (1) mapping each source variable to its corresponding FHIR element and (2) mapping each item in the source data's value sets to the corresponding FHIR value set item for variables with strict value sets. To date, CAMP FHIR has been used to transform 108 variables from the Informatics for Integrating Biology & the Bedside (i2b2) and Patient-Centered Outcomes Research Network data models to fields across 7 FHIR resources. It is designed to allow input from any source data model and will support additional FHIR resources in the future. Results: We have used CAMP FHIR to transform data on approximately 23,000 patients with asthma from our institution's i2b2 database. Data quality and integrity were validated against the origin point of the data, our enterprise clinical data warehouse. Conclusions: We believe that CAMP FHIR can serve as an alternative to implementing new CDMs on a project-by-project basis. Moreover, the use of FHIR as a CDM could support rare data sharing opportunities, such as collaborations between academic medical centers and community hospitals. We anticipate adoption and use of CAMP FHIR to foster sharing of clinical data across institutions for downstream applications in translational research.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
080	Open data kit: Mobile data collection framework for developing countries	To evaluate and improve the delivery of health care services and programs; to collect and share information on agro-biodiversity; to fill the gaps in the data of artisanal or industrial fisheries, the use of computer tools of data collection is a major asset. It is now obvious that most of these tools are difficult to use in developing countries. And this is because of the complexity of use, either because they are commercial solutions or simply because these tools require a stable internet connection. This study is the result of thorough research on Open Data Kit (ODK), a suite of tools fully compatible with the context of developing countries and fully open source software. This article traces the research work done for the design, implementation, and improvement of ODK. A description of the different		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.

		ODK extensions that can be found in the literature is given in addition to the reasons that explain the success of ODK in developing countries. To highlight the utility of ODK, an analysis of the areas of use of ODK has been made. This analysis concludes that ODK is mainly used to improve the intervention effectiveness of health system agents in developing countries.			
081	Zynq SoC based acceleration of the lattice Boltzmann method	Cerebral aneurysm is a life-threatening condition. It is a weakness in a blood vessel that may enlarge and bleed into the surrounding area. In order to understand the surrounding environmental conditions during the interventions or surgical procedures, a simulation of blood flow in cerebral arteries is needed. One of the effective simulation approaches is to use the lattice Boltzmann (LB) method. Due to the computational complexity of the algorithm, the simulation is usually performed on high performance computers. In this paper, efficient hardware architectures of the LB method on a Zynq system-on-chip (SoC) are designed and implemented. The proposed architectures have first been simulated in Vivado HLS environment and later implemented on a ZedBoard using the software-defined SoC (SDSoC) development environment. In addition, a set of evaluations of different hardware architectures of the LB implementation is discussed in this paper. The experimental results show that the proposed implementation is able to accelerate the processing speed by a factor of 52 compared to a dual-core ARM processor-based software implementation.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
082	FOSS TECHNOLOGIES IN MODELLING SPATIAL ACCESSIBILITY OF PRIMARY HEALTH CARE IN MALAWI	Primary health care (PHC) is the first point of contact people have with a health system. As such access to PHC services is an important factor to ensure good health of a community. While the need to provide equal and easy access to PHC is well understood, the approaches informing the decision-making process to improve the access tend to face a number of challenges in the developing world. Use of conventional Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) comes with requisite financial costs which Free and Open Source Software (FOSS) ICT technologies have the potential to help lower among other benefits. In this study, the confluence of spatial accessibility tools provided by FOSS technologies, specifically PostgreSQL/PostGIS and QGIS, was explored to inform decision making in PHC accessibility in Zomba, Malawi. The results show that the household population (P) that is within the threshold time was 82,863, representing 59% of all households having access to health care. The mean accessibility score for the district was 0.010 and ranged from 0.00 to 0.231. While the findings provide, arguably, spatially objective PHC accessibility data to inform policy direction and also reveals accessibility to PHC in Malawi to be lower than reported, the study also reveals the usefulness of FOSS technologies, in the developing world. Use of FOSS facilitated incremental setup of the model thereby allowing to run the model with limited processing power. That notwithstanding, the study adds to the formal scientific research on the use of relational spatial analysis in the developing world.	CII		
083	Multivariate statistical analysis of surface enhanced Raman spectra of human serum for Alzheimer's disease diagnosis	Alzheimer's disease (AD) is the most common form of dementia worldwide and is characterized by progressive cognitive decline. Along with being incurable and lethal, AD is difficult to diagnose with high levels of accuracy. Blood serum from Alzheimer's disease (AD) patients was analyzed by surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy (SERS) coupled with multivariate statistical analysis. The obtained spectra were compared with spectra from healthy controls (HC) to develop a simple test for AD detection. Serum spectra from AD patients were further compared to spectra from patients with other neurodegenerative dementias (OD). Colloidal silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) were used as the SERS-active substrates. Classification experiments involving serum SERS spectra using artificial neural networks (ANNs) achieved a diagnostic sensitivity around 96% for differentiating AD samples from HC samples in a binary model and 98% for differentiating AD, HC, and OD samples in a tertiary model. The results from this proof-of-concept study demonstrate the great potential of SERS blood serum analysis to be developed further into a novel clinical assay for the effective and accurate diagnosis of AD.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
084	PhishLedger: A	In recent years, phishing has become one of the biggest security threats on the Internet. To combat phishing, it requires multiple steps and multi-agency participation and thus desperately need uniform data sharing format and		CE1	Não é da área da saúde.

	decentralized phishing data sharing mechanism	unobstructed sharing channels, which unfortunately is just what is lacking currently. This paper proposes a novel phishing data sharing mechanism based on the consortium blockchain. It designs four types of nodes, including reporting node, accounting node, servicing node and supervising node and illustrates the roles of each type. Then it demonstrates the process of reporting, accounting and servicing and designs the process of post-supervision, which ensures the operation of the mechanism stable and fastest; and then discusses its implementation on Hyperledger Fabric. The proposed mechanism includes multi-source reporting, anti-tamper accounting, multichannel disposal of phishing data and post-supervision. It provides a platform for multi-party participation, transparent and efficient coordination and unified standard and overcomes the current prominent problems of phishing data sharing; and the participants on the consortium blockchain all have a strong desire to combat phishing, which ensures the proposed mechanism is also very practical and highly feasible.			
085	Narrative review for exploring barriers to readiness of electronic health record implementation in primary health care	Objectives: The aim of this study is to explore the enabling factors associated with readiness in Electronic Health Record (EHR) implementation and to identify the barriers related to readiness regarding the situation of primary health cares in developed and developing countries. Methods: A narrative review of open-source literature was conducted using the ProQuest, ScienceDirect, MEDLINE, and PMC databases to identify the enabling factors and barriers to EHR readiness. The keywords applied were 'electronic health record', 'readiness', 'primary health care', and 'primary care'. Results: Some barriers were found that may affect readiness, specifically individual barriers and organizational barriers. In developing countries, organizational barriers such as a lack of skilled manpower, insufficient senior management, and a lack of interaction among team members were the common barriers, while in developed countries individual barriers such as unfamiliarity with new systems and a lack of time to use computers were frequently found as barriers to readiness. Conclusions: This study summarized the enabling factors and barriers with regard to EHR readiness in developed and developing countries.		CE5	Revisão da literatura.
086	Mining sequential patterns of diseases contracted and medications prescribed before the development of Stevens-Johnson Syndrome in Taiwan	Medication is designed to cure diseases, but serious risks can arise from severe adverse drug reactions (ADRs). ADRs can lead to emergency room visits and hospitalization, straining healthcare resources and, thus, they have strong implications for public health. Stevens-Johnson Syndrome (SJS) is one ADR and comprises the highest proportion of all drug relief cases in Taiwan. Pharmacovigilance involves the collection, detection, assessment, monitoring, and prevention of ADRs, including SJS. Most medical specialists are not fully aware of the risk of drug-induced SJS. Consequently, various drugs may be prescribed to susceptible patients for a great variety of diseases and, in turn, cause SJS. In this research, medical records of SJS patients were retrieved from the Taiwan National Health Insurance Research Database, and the Generalized Sequential Patterns (GSP) algorithm was used to find the sequential patterns of diseases before SJS onset. Then we mined the sequential patterns of medications prescribed in each disease pattern. Afterwards, we detected significant associations of each pattern of diseases and medications prescribed among age groups with statistical analysis. We found that, first, most patients developed SJS after being prescribed the causative medications fewer than four times. Second, Respiratory System Diseases (RSDs) appeared in disease sequential patterns of all lengths. Patterns involving RSDs were more frequent than others. Third, NSAIDs, H2-antagonists for peptic ulcer, penicillin antibiotics, theophylline bronchodilators, and cephalosporin antibiotics were the most frequent medications prescribed. Fourth, we found that patients in certain age groups had higher risks of developing SJS. This study aimed to mine the sequential patterns of diseases contracted and medications prescribed before patients developed SJS in Taiwan. This useful information can be provided to physicians so that they can stop the administration of suspected drugs to avoid evolution towards more severe cases.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
087	Assessing source code	Healthcare systems have been improved in order to provide support to cross-border situations where one citizen from one country travels to another country and requires the use of their health records. Several initiatives have been carried out to tackle this problem. This is the case for the OpenNCP which is supported by the		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-

	vulnerabilities in a cloud-based system for health systems; OpenNCP	European Commission by providing a common network and an infrastructure to connect different national healthcare systems which most of the times are cloud-based systems. The OpenNCP plays a key role in communicating health records among European Union's member states, and therefore it manages sensitive information. Therefore, this study provides a security analysis of this platform and a prototype is developed for identifying secure patterns in source code.			aberto.
088	Supporting integrated care with a flexible data management framework built upon Linked Data, HL7 FHIR and ontologies	In this paper we present the methodology and decisions behind an implementation of a telehealth data management framework, aiming to support integrated care services for chronic and multimorbid patients. The framework leverages an OWL ontology, built upon HL7 FHIR resources, to provide storage and representation of semantically enriched EHR data following Linked Data principles. This is presented along with the realization of the persistent storage solution and communication web services that allow the management of EHR data, ensuring the validity and integrity of the exchanged patient data as self-describing ontology instances. The framework concentrates on flexibility and reusability, which is addressed by regarding the aforementioned ontology as a single point of change. This solution has been implemented in the scope of the EU project WELCOME for managing data in a telemonitoring system for patients with COPD and comorbidities and was also successfully deployed for the INLIFE EU project with minimal effort. The results of the two applications suggest it can be adopted and properly adapted in a series of integrated care scenarios with minimal effort.	CII		
089	Design and virtual implementation of a biomedical registry framework for the enhancement of clinical trials: colorectal cancer example	Introduction Clinical trials generate a large volume of literature and a vast amount of data. Following the 'open science' model, data sharing has enormous potential to strengthen scientific research. Currently, to the best of our knowledge, there is no existing web based Hellenic biomedical registry that displays available patients for clinical trials, providing direct access to registered physicians to all data, assisting them in finding eligible patients in the initial clinical trial recruitment process. Methods This paper describes the design and virtual implementation of a web based prototype biomedical registry in Greece. The system represents an eGovernment framework proposal for the central storage of patients' biomedical information and the operations associated with this process. The increasing tendency to include molecular data as prerequisite elements in clinical trials is adopted in the registry philosophy. The designed system is based on free, open source software and it is implemented virtually on a local host environment. Results Using colorectal cancer as an example, valid data from patients increases the reliability index, demonstrating the functionality of the web application. Conclusion In conclusion, the combination of biomedical data and information technology in order to display potential participants per health unit, facilitates recruitment for clinical trials.	CII		
090	A self-assessment instrument for assessing test automation maturity	Test automation is important in the software industry but self-assessment instruments for assessing its maturity are not sufficient. The two objectives of this study are to synthesize what an organization should focus to assess its test automation; develop a self-assessment instrument (a survey) for assessing test automation maturity and scientifically evaluate it. We carried out the study in four stages. First, a literature review of 25 sources was conducted. Second, the initial instrument was developed. Third, seven experts from five companies evaluated the initial instrument. Content Validity Index and Cognitive Interview methods were used. Fourth, we revised the developed instrument. Our contributions are as follows: (a) we collected practices mapped into 15 key areas that indicate where an organization should focus to assess its test automation; (b) we developed and evaluated a self-assessment instrument for assessing test automation maturity; (c) we discuss important topics such as response bias that threatens self-assessment instruments. Our results help companies and researchers to understand and improve test automation practices and processes.		CE1	Não é da área de saúde.
091	The effect of eHealth information	EHealth information systems have brought about a lot of positives which include timeous reporting, efficient data analysis, better decision making, coordination and better work processes. Zimbabwe has also adopted the eHealth information systems and this study sought to establish the effects of eHealth information systems on the management of health information in hospitals in Bulawayo, Zimbabwe. The study		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de

	systems on health information management in hospitals in Bulawayo, Zimbabwe	applies a qualitative research methodology in which a case study research design and a purposive sampling technique were used. Document analysis and face to face interviews were held with a total of eleven research participants.			um sistema.
092	Cross-Network Directory Service: Infrastructures to enable collaborations across distributed research networks	Introduction: Existing large-scale distributed health data networks are disconnected even as they address related questions of healthcare research and public policy. This paper describes the design and implementation of a fully functional prototype open-source tool, the Cross-Network Directory Service (CNDS), which addresses much of what keeps distributed networks disconnected from each other. Methods: The set of services needed to implement a Cross-Directory Service was identified through engagement with stakeholders and workgroup members. CNDS was implemented using PCORnet and Sentinel network instances and tested by participating data partners. Results: Web services that enable the four major functional features of the service (registration, discovery, communication, and governance) were developed and placed into an open-source repository. The services include a robust metadata model that is extensible to accommodate a virtually unlimited inventory of metadata fields, without requiring any further software development. The user interfaces are programmatically generated based on the contents of the metadata model. Conclusion: The CNDS pilot project gathered functional requirements from stakeholders and collaborating partners to build a software application to enable cross-network data and resource sharing. The two partners—one from Sentinel and one from PCORnet—tested the software. They successfully entered metadata about their organizations and data sources and then used the Discovery and Communication functionality to find data sources of interest and send a cross-network query. The CNDS software can help integrate disparate health data networks by providing a mechanism for data partners to participate in multiple networks, share resources, and seamlessly send queries across those networks.		CE1	Não é da área da saúde.
093	Identifying Effective Motivational Interviewing Communication Sequences Using Automated Pattern Analysis	Motivational interviewing (MI) is an evidence-based strategy for communicating with patients about behavior change. Although there is strong empirical evidence linking “MI-consistent” counselor behaviors and patient motivational statements (i.e., “change talk”), the specific counselor communication behaviors effective for eliciting patient change talk vary by treatment context and, thus, are a subject of ongoing research. An integral part of this research is the sequential analysis of pre-coded MI transcripts. In this paper, we evaluate the empirical effectiveness of the Hidden Markov Model, a probabilistic generative model for sequence data, for modeling sequences of behavior codes and closed frequent pattern mining, a method to identify frequently occurring sequential patterns of behavior codes in MI communication sequences to inform MI practice. We conducted experiments with 1,360 communication sequences from 37 transcribed audio recordings of weight loss counseling sessions with African-American adolescents with obesity and their caregivers. Transcripts had been previously annotated with patient-counselor behavior codes using a specialized codebook. Empirical results indicate that Hidden Markov Model and closed frequent pattern mining techniques can identify counselor communication strategies that are effective at eliciting patients’ motivational statements to guide clinical practice.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
094	How to develop IoT cloud e-health systems based on fware: A lesson learn	Nowadays, the penetration of sensors and actuators in different application fields is revolutionizing all aspects of our daily life. One of the major sectors that is taking advantage of such cutting-edge cheap smart devices is healthcare. In this context, Remote Patient Monitoring (RPM) at home represents a tempting opportunity for hospitals to reduce clinical costs and to improve the quality of life of both patients and their families. It allows patients to be monitored remotely by means networks of Internet of Things (IoT) medical devices equipped with sensors and actuators that collect healthcare data from patients and send them to a Cloud-based Hospital Information System (HIS) for processing. Up to now, many different proprietary		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.

		<p>software systems have been developed as stand-alone expensive solutions, presenting interoperability, extensibility, and scalability issues. In recent years, the European Commission (EC) has promoted the wide adoption of FIWARE technology, launching 16 Industrial Accelerators focusing on different application fields. One of these, i.e., FICHe, is specialized in healthcare, providing the guidelines on how to develop eHealth systems. This paper focuses on how to compose new cutting-edge IoT and Cloud-based Cyber Physical Health System (CPHS) services and applications interconnected with remote medical sensors and actuators using FIWARE technology in the context envisioned by FICHe. In particular, we discuss the design and development of an RPM system implemented through the collaboration between the Istituto di Ricovero e Cura a Carattere Scientifico (IRCCS) “Bonino Pulejo” (i.e., a clinical and research healthcare centre specialized in the treatment of neuro lesions), University of Messina, IBM Research, Telefónica, and the University of the Western Cape in South Africa. The description of our best practice provides a model and guidelines for the development of lightweight and low cost RPM services for rural and isolated areas, with the expectation of expanding healthcare to the developing world and in general allows us to outline how to deal with the real adoption of the FIWARE technology in an e-health project.</p>			
095	<p>Roadmap for Design of Surgical Equipment for Safe Surgery Worldwide</p>	<p>Safe and affordable surgery is not accessible for five billion people when they need it. Multiple surgical capacity studies have shown that hospitals in low-And-middle income countries do not have complete coverage of basic surgical equipment such as, theatre lights, anesthesia machines and electro surgical units. Currently, almost all equipment is designed and manufactured with a main focus on the context in high income countries. The context in low-And-middle income countries in which surgical equipment is used, differs from high income countries, especially in terms of financial resources and access to maintenance, spare parts and consumables. The aim of this study is to present a roadmap for design of surgical equipment for worldwide use. The roadmap consists of four phases: before the start of a design project a clear need for certain surgical equipment should be identified (Phase 0). During Phase 1 the context should be researched thoroughly by determining the barriers encountered by patients to surgical care, the structure of the health care system and if the aspects required for safe surgery are in place. In Phase 2 the implementation strategy and design requirements should be determined and in phase 3 prototyping starts in close interaction with local end-users. We believe that designers should strive for design that is of the same quality and complies with the same safety regulations as equipment designed for HICs. In this way user and patient safety can be assured in any setting worldwide. And we advocate for surgical equipment that fits the context optimally and that will be applicable in comparable settings globally.</p>		CE1	<p>Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.</p>
096	<p>Snomed ct concept hierarchies for computable clinical phenotypes from electronic health record data: Comparison of intensional versus extensional value sets</p>	<p>Background: Defining clinical phenotypes from electronic health record (EHR)-derived data proves crucial for clinical decision support, population health endeavors, and translational research. EHR diagnoses now commonly draw from a finely grained clinical terminology-either native SNOMED CT or a vendor-supplied terminology mapped to SNOMED CT concepts as the standard for EHR interoperability. Accordingly, electronic clinical quality measures (eCQMs) increasingly define clinical phenotypes with SNOMED CT value sets. The work of creating and maintaining list-based value sets proves daunting, as does insuring that their contents accurately represent the clinically intended condition. Objective: The goal of the research was to compare an intensional (concept hierarchy-based) versus extensional (list-based) value set approach to defining clinical phenotypes using SNOMED CT-encoded data from EHRs by evaluating value set conciseness, time to create, and completeness. Methods: Starting from published Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services (CMS) high-priority eCQMs, we selected 10 clinical conditions referenced by those eCQMs. For each, the published SNOMED CT list-based (extensional) value set was downloaded from the Value Set Authority Center (VSAC). Ten corresponding SNOMED CT hierarchy-based intensional value sets for the same conditions were identified within our EHR. From each hierarchy-based intensional value set, an exactly equivalent full extensional value set was derived enumerating all included descendant SNOMED CT concepts.</p>		CE1	<p>Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema</p>

		<p>Comparisons were then made between (1) VSAC-downloaded list-based (extensional) value sets, (2) corresponding hierarchy-based intensional value sets for the same conditions, and (3) derived list-based (extensional) value sets exactly equivalent to the hierarchy-based intensional value sets. Value set conciseness was assessed by the number of SNOMED CT concepts needed for definition. Time to construct the value sets for local use was measured. Value set completeness was assessed by comparing contents of the downloaded extensional versus intensional value sets. Two measures of content completeness were made: For individual SNOMED CT concepts and for the mapped diagnosis clinical terms available for selection within the EHR by clinicians. Results: The 10 hierarchy-based intensional value sets proved far simpler and faster to construct than exactly equivalent derived extensional value set lists, requiring a median 3 versus 78 concepts to define and 5 versus 37 minutes to build. The hierarchy-based intensional value sets also proved more complete: In comparison, the 10 downloaded 2018 extensional value sets contained a median of just 35% of the intensional value sets' SNOMED CT concepts and 65% of mapped EHR clinical terms. Conclusions: In the EHR era, defining conditions preferentially should employ SNOMED CT concept hierarchy-based (intensional) value sets rather than extensional lists. By doing so, clinical guideline and eCQM authors can more readily engage specialists in vetting condition subtypes to include and exclude, and streamline broad EHR implementation of condition-specific decision support promoting guideline adherence for patient benefit.</p>			
097	<p>Big Data Visualization in Cardiology - A Systematic Review and Future Directions</p>	<p>The digital transformations and use of healthcare information system, electronic medical records, wearable technology, and smart devices are increasing with the passage of time. A variety of sources of big data in healthcare are available, such as biometric data, registration data, electronic health record, medical imaging, patient reported data, biomarker data, clinical data, and administrative data. Visualization of data is a key tool for producing images, diagrams, or animations to convey messages from the viewed insight. The role of cardiology in healthcare is obvious for living and life. The function of heart is the control of blood supply to the entire parts of the body. Recent speedy growth in healthcare and the development of computation in the field of cardiology enable researchers and practitioners to mine and visualize new insights from patient data. The role of visualization is to capture the important information from the data and to visualize it for the easiness of doctors and practitioners. To help the doctors and practitioners, the proposed study presents a detailed report of the existing literature on visualization of data in the field of cardiology. This report will support the doctors and practitioners in decision-making process and to make it easier. This detailed study will eventually summarize the results of the existing literature published related to visualization of data in the cardiology. This research uses the systematic literature protocol and the data was collected from the studies published during the year 2009 to 2018 (10 years). The proposed study selected 53 primary studies from different repositories according to the defined exclusion, inclusion, and quality criteria. The proposed study focused mainly on the research work been done on visualization of big data in the field of cardiology, presented a summary of the techniques used for visualization of data in cardiology, and highlight the benefits of visualizations in cardiology. The current research summarizes and organizes the available literature in the form of published materials related to big data visualization in cardiology. The proposed research will help the researchers to view the available research studies on the subject of medical big data in cardiology and then can ultimately be used as evidence in future research. The results of the proposed research show that there is an increase in articles published yearly wise and several studies exist related to medical big data in cardiology. The derivations from the studies are presented in the paper.</p>		CES	Revisão da literatura.
098	<p>Securing web applications through a framework of</p>	<p>Source code analysis is becoming extremely important for the universal acceptance of web applications because the automated source code analysis tools play a key role in identifying and fixing security-related vulnerabilities. This paper proposes a framework for securing web applications through source code analysis. The framework has three prescriptive phases including executing and monitoring, classifying and controlling and refining and managing. The framework helps to</p>	C12		

	source code analysis	examine the web application source code related to security issues. The executing and monitoring phase employs five different open source tools for statically analyzing the source code. According to the literature, there are nine broad categories of vulnerabilities in web applications. After filtration of these vulnerabilities, classifying and controlling phase categorize the vulnerabilities according to their severity level with the help of fuzzy analytical analysis process and suggestive measures. The refining and managing phase takes these measures and suggests changes to the source code to make it more secure. This framework was validated through a web-based hospital management system. The results of the validation showed that the framework implementation made the source code more robust towards the upcoming vulnerabilities and bugs.			
099	Information technology-assisted treatment planning and performance assessment for severe thalassemia care in low and middle-income countries: Observational study	Background: Successful models of information and communication technology (ICT) applied to cost-effective delivery of quality care in low- and middle-income countries (LMIC) are an increasing necessity. Severe thalassemia is one of the most common life-threatening noncommunicable diseases of children globally. Objective: The aim was to study the impact of ICT on quality of care for severe thalassemia patients in LMIC. Methods: A total of 1110 patients with severe thalassemia from five centers in India were followed over a 1-year period. The impact of consistent use of a Web-based platform designed to assist comprehensive management of severe thalassemia (ThalCare) on key indicators of quality of care such as minimum (pretransfusion) hemoglobin, serum ferritin, liver size, and spleen size were assessed. Results: Overall improvements in initial hemoglobin, ferritin, and liver and spleen size were significant ($P < .001$ for each). For four centers, the improvement in mean pretransfusion hemoglobin level was statistically significant ($P < .001$). Four of five centers achieved reduction in mean ferritin levels, with two displaying a significant drop in ferritin ($P = .004$ and $P < .001$). One of the five centers did not record liver and spleen size on palpation, but of the remaining four centers, two witnessed a large drop in liver and spleen size ($P < .01$), one witnessed moderate drop ($P = .05$ for liver; $P = .03$ for spleen size), while the fourth witnessed a moderate increase in liver size ($P = .08$) and insignificant change in spleen size ($P = .12$). Conclusions: Implementation of computer-assisted treatment planning and performance assessment consistently and positively impacted indexes reflecting effective delivery of care to patients suffering from severe thalassemia in LMIC.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
100	Perspective on the Development of a Large-Scale Clinical Data Repository for Pediatric Hearing Research	The use of "big data" for pediatric hearing research requires new approaches to both data collection and research methods. The widespread deployment of electronic health record systems creates new opportunities and corresponding challenges in the secondary use of large volumes of audiological and medical data. Opportunities include cost-effective hypothesis generation, rapid cohort expansion for rare conditions, and observational studies based on sample sizes in the thousands to tens of thousands. Challenges include finding and forming appropriately skilled teams, access to data, data quality assessment, and engagement with a research community new to big data. The authors share their experience and perspective on the work required to build and validate a pediatric hearing research database that integrates clinical data for over 185,000 patients from the electronic health record systems of three major academic medical centers.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
101	Proposal of an integrated decision support system for Tuberculosis based on Semantic Web	Epidemiological surveillance of Tuberculosis (TB) requires a strong integration of different health services, programs and levels of care. The deepening and broadening of data management techniques must be constantly carried out to increase the integrality of healthcare. Otherwise, knowledge extraction and clinical and administrative decision-making processes are significantly hampered, directly affecting the management and quality of health services. Thus, this work aims to establish a computerized decision support system capable of collecting, integrating and sharing TB health data in Brazilian Unified Public Health System. Also, it will allow the monitoring of infected patients and the visualization of consolidated information of regular TB and its resistant variants for health professionals and managers. The data will be made available from heterogeneous, disconnected and unstructured sources by combining traditional web services, Semantic Web resources and security algorithms. A solid knowledge base applied to epidemiological surveillance, health information governance and clinical support will be enabled to integrate the multiple areas of TB patients care, as well as to		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.

102	Development and face validation of ultrasound-guided renal biopsy virtual trainer	<p>support the creation of more accurate operational and diagnostics models.</p> <p>The overall prevalence of chronic kidney disease in the general population is ~14% with more than 661,000 Americans having a kidney failure. Ultrasound (US)-guided renal biopsy is a critically important tool in the evaluation and management of renal pathologies. This Letter presents KBVTrainer, a virtual simulator that the authors developed to train clinicians to improve procedural skill competence in US-guided renal biopsy. The simulator was built using low-cost hardware components and open source software libraries. They conducted a face validation study with five experts who were either adult/pediatric nephrologists or interventional/diagnostic radiologists. The trainer was rated very highly (>4.4) for the usefulness of the real US images (highest at 4.8), potential usefulness of the trainer in training for needle visualization, tracking, steadiness and hand-eye coordination, and overall promise of the trainer to be useful for training US-guided needle biopsies. The lowest score of 2.4 was received for the look and feel of the US probe and needle compared to clinical practice. The force feedback received a moderate score of 3.0. The clinical experts provided abundant verbal and written subjective feedback and were highly enthusiastic about using the trainer as a valuable tool for future trainees.</p>	CE6	Duplicado Pubmed
103	Internet of Things Based on Electronic and Mobile Health Systems for Blood Glucose Continuous Monitoring and Management	<p>Over 425 million people suffer from diabetes worldwide and this number is expected to increase over the years. Rigorous and extensive research has led to the development of increasingly advanced technologies, such as continuous glucose monitoring and glucose flash monitoring. These new technologies are more promising and efficient with respect to calculating the glycemic index and are more easier to use than the glucometer technology already established in the market. However, market solutions are often highly restrictive due to their costs. In an effort to address this challenge, this article describes the Freestyle Free sensor and the associated advantages of an integrated and low-cost environment that it offers patients. The proposed environment allows continuously monitoring the blood glucose rate and provides doctors and caregivers information remotely. Additionally, the data generated will allow the application of data mining techniques in efforts aimed at understanding the disease better. The integration between the patient and the integrated environment occurs through the near-field communication sensor over an Internet of Things card, which sends the data collected for the LibreMonitor mobile application. To evaluate the integrated environment, we compared the glucose rates measured with an official Freestyle Libre software during the same period. Based on the positive results, we propose that the integrated environment is a low-cost alternative for continuous glucose monitoring of patients with diabetes.</p>	CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
104	Automated gathering and analysis of cannabinoids treatment data	<p>The paper presents an open source platform to integrate and analyse the cannabinoids research data gathered from academic publications, industrial and clinical trials as well as patients. The project focuses on the analysis of the usability aspects important for the applications collecting the treatment data as well as data on diverse cannabinoids strains. The collected data will be used to estimate the efficiency of cannabinoid treatment of various disorders, which will provide an evidence-based assistance for doctors, researchers and industry to identify the right cannabinoid profiles for various conditions.</p>	CII	
105	Development of Disease Prediction Model Based on Ensemble Learning Approach for Diabetes and Hypertension	<p>Early diseases prediction plays an important role for improving healthcare quality and can help individuals avoid dangerous health situations before it is too late. This paper proposes a disease prediction model (DPM) to provide an early prediction for type 2 diabetes and hypertension based on individual's risk factors data. The proposed DPM consists of isolation forest (iForest) based outlier detection method to remove outlier data, synthetic minority oversampling technique tomekek link (SMOTETomek) to balance data distribution, and ensemble approach to predict the diseases. Four datasets were utilized to build the model and extract the most significant risks factors. The results showed that the proposed DPM achieved highest accuracy when compared to other models and previous studies. We also developed a mobile application to provide the practical application of the proposed DPM. The developed mobile application gathers risk factor data and send it to a remote server, so that an individual's current condition can be diagnosed with the proposed DPM. The prediction result is then sent back to the mobile application;</p>	CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.

		thus, immediate and appropriate action can be taken to reduce and prevent individual's risks once unexpected health situations occur (i.e., type 2 diabetes and/or hypertension) at early stages.			
106	A novel technology tool to capture the clinical information of patients across rural vision centers in a three-tier eye care network in India using the eyeSmart EMR App	Introduction: This article describes the implementation of a novel technology tool to capture demographic distribution and clinical presentation of patients in rural vision centers using the eyeSmart electronic medical record (EMR) app in a three-tier eyecare network in India. Methods: A two-year retrospective review of all patients who presented to the rural vision centers of LV Prasad Eye Institute (LVPEI) eyecare network was performed from September 2016 to August 2018 using an in-house developed eyeSmart EMR app. Results: A total of 501 771 patients were captured on the eyeSmart EMR app across the LVPEI network. The ratio of males (n=273 985, 54.60%) and females (n=227 786, 45.40%) presenting to the rural vision centers was 1.2:1. The most prevalent ocular disorder was refractive errors (n=273 720, 44.32%). Conclusions: This study details the demographic distribution and prevalence of ocular disorders in a large cohort of Indian patients and demonstrates the potential for real-time analytics through the use of EMR systems. This provides rigorous evidence for the community and eyecare providers that the use of a web application/tablet app (eyeSmart) aids in providing better eyecare services in rural areas. It helps in creating government policies and improves the treatment strategies for various preventable ocular disorders in India.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
107	Based Multiple Heterogeneous Wearable Sensors: A Smart Real-Time Health Monitoring Structured for Hospitals Distributor	This paper proposes a smart real-time health monitoring structured for hospitals' distributor based on wearable health data sensors. Health data were received from multiple heterogeneous wearable sensors, such as electrocardiogram (ECG), oxygen saturation sensor (SpO2), blood pressure monitor, and non-sensory measurement (text frame), from 500 patients with different symptoms. Triage level and healthcare services were identified based on the new four-level remote triage and package localization (4LRTP). The numbers of healthcare services that represent hospital status were collected from 12 hospitals located in Baghdad city. This study constructed a decision matrix based on the crossover of 'multi-healthcare services' and 'hospital list' within Tier 4. The hospitals were then ranked using multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) techniques, namely, integrated analytic hierarchy process (AHP) and vlsekriterijumskaoptimizacija i kompromisnoresenje (VIKOR). Mean ± standard deviation was computed to ensure that the hospital ranking undergoes systematic ranking for objective validation. This research provided scenarios and checklist benchmarking to evaluate the proposed and existing health recommender frameworks. Results corroborated that: 1) the integration of AHP and VIKOR effectively solved hospital selection problems; 2) in the objective validation, significant differences were recognized between the scores of groups, indicating that the ranking results were identical; 3) in evaluation, the proposed framework exhibited an advantage over the benchmark framework with a percentage of 56.25%; and 4) hospitals with multiple healthcare services received the highest ranks, whereas hospitals with fewer healthcare services received low ranks.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
108	Model driven data management in healthcare	Healthcare research depends on the availability of data that is of high quality, that is easy to query, consistent and current. Traditionally, healthcare data has relied on multiple diverse datasets being integrated by domain experts. These integration processes are executed with a high degree of human involvement, integrating datasets can be time-consuming and can result in the introduction of errors into the data. This paper describes work to build an integration toolset for healthcare datasets based on the ISO11179 Standard for metadata registries. It describes issues encountered whilst implementing the standard and shows how these short-comings were overcome by using techniques from the field of Model Driven Engineering (MDE).		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
109	Fault-Tolerant mHealth Framework in the Context of IoT	The emerging technology breakthrough of the Internet of Things (IoT) is expected to offer promising solutions for indoor/outdoor healthcare, which may contribute significantly to human health and well-being. In this paper, we investigated the technologies of healthcare service applications in telemedicine architecture. We aimed to resolve a series of healthcare problems on the frequent failures in telemedicine architecture through IoT solutions, particularly the failures of		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.

	<p>Based Real-Time Wearable Health Data Sensor</p>	<p>wearable body sensors (Tier 1) and a medical center server (Tier 3). For improved generalisability, we demonstrated an effective research approach, the fault-tolerant framework on mHealth or the so-called FTF-mHealth-IoT in the context of IoT, to resolve essential problems in current investigations on healthcare services. First, we propose a risk local triage algorithm known as the risk-level localization triage (RLLT), which can exclude the control process of patient triage from the medical center by using mHealth and can warn about failures related to wearable sensors. RLLT performs this initial step towards detecting a patient's emergency case and then identifying the healthcare service package of the risk-level. Second, according to the risk-level package, our framework can aid decision makers in hospital selection through multi-criteria decision making (MCDM). Accordingly, mHealth can connect directly with the servers of distributed hospitals to ascertain available healthcare services for the risk-level package in those hospitals. The time of arrival of the patient at the hospital (TAH) is considered for each hospital to reach a final decision and select the appropriate institution in case of medical center failure. This paper used two datasets. The first dataset involved 572 patients with chronic heart disease. Their triage levels were evaluated using our RLLT algorithm. The second dataset included hospital healthcare services with two levels of availability within distributed hospitals to show variety when testing the proposed framework. The former dataset is an actual dataset of services collected from 12 hospitals located in the capital Baghdad, which represents the maximum level of availability. The latter is an assumption dataset of the services within the 12 hospitals located in the capital Kuala Lumpur, which represents the minimum level of availability. Subsequently, the hospitals were prioritized using a unique MCDM method for estimating small power consumption, namely, the analytic hierarchy process (AHP), based on a crossover between the 'healthcare services package/TAH' of each hospital and the 'hospital list'. The results showed that the AHP is effective for solving hospital selection problems within mHealth. The implications of this study support the patients, organizations, and medical staff in a modern lifestyle.</p>			
110	<p>Mobile Health Technologies for Diabetes Mellitus: Current State and Future Challenges</p>	<p>The prevalence of diabetes is rising globally. Diabetes patients need continuous monitoring, and to achieve this objective, they have to be engaged in their healthcare management process. Mobile health (MH) is an information and communications technology trend to empower chronically ill patients in a smart environment. Discussing the current state of MH technologies is required in order to address their limitations. Existing review articles have evaluated the MH literature based on applicability and level of adoption by patients and healthcare providers. Most of these reviews asserted that MH apps and research have not reached a stable level yet. To the best of our knowledge, there is no clear description of solutions to these problems. In addition, no one has investigated and analyzed MH in its contextual environment in a detailed way. We conducted a comprehensive survey of MH research on diabetes management articles published between 2011 and September 27, 2017. In this survey, we discuss current challenges in MH, along with research gaps, opportunities, and trends. Our literature review searched three academic databases (ScienceDirect, IEEE Xplore, and SpringerLink). A total of 60 articles were analyzed, with 30% from ScienceDirect, 38% from IEEE Xplore, and 32% from SpringerLink. MH was analyzed in the context of the electronic health record (EHR) ecosystem. We consider dimensions such as clinical decision support systems, EHRs, cloud computing, semantic interoperability, wireless body area networks, and big data analytics. We propose specific metrics to analyze and evaluate MH from each of these dimensions. A comprehensive analysis of the literature from this viewpoint is valuable for both theoretical and developmental progress. This paper provides a critical analysis of challenges that have not been fully met and highlights directions for future research that could improve MH applicability.</p>		CE5	Survey
111	<p>A method for harmonization of clinical abbreviation and</p>	<p>Background: Previous research has developed methods to construct acronym sense inventories from a single institutional corpus. Although beneficial, a sense inventory constructed from a single institutional corpus is not generalizable, because acronyms from different geographic regions and medical specialties vary greatly. Objective: Develop an automated method to harmonize sense inventories from different regions and specialties towards the development of a comprehensive</p>		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.

	<p>acronym sense inventories</p>	<p>inventory. Methods: The method involves integrating multiple source sense inventories into one centralized inventory and cross-mapping redundant entries to establish synonymy. To evaluate our method, we integrated 8 well-known source inventories into one comprehensive inventory (or metathesaurus). For both the metathesaurus and its sources, we evaluated the coverage of acronyms and their senses on a corpus of 1 million clinical notes. The corpus came from a different institution, region, and specialty than the source inventories. Results: In the evaluation using clinical notes, the metathesaurus demonstrated an acronym (short form) micro-coverage of 94.3%, representing a substantial increase over the two next largest source inventories, the UMLS LRABR (74.8%) and ADAM (68.0%). The metathesaurus demonstrated a sense (long form) micro-coverage of 99.6%, again a substantial increase compared to the UMLS LRABR (82.5%) and ADAM (55.4%). Conclusions: Given the high coverage, harmonizing acronym sense inventories is a promising methodology to improve their comprehensiveness. Our method is automated, leverages the extensive resources already devoted to developing institution-specific inventories in the United States, and may help generalize sense inventories to institutions who lack the resources to develop them. Future work should address quality issues in source inventories and explore additional approaches to establishing synonymy.</p>			
<p>112</p>	<p>Developing a representative community health survey sampling frame using open-source remote satellite imagery in Mozambique</p>	<p>Background: Lack of accurate data on the distribution of sub-national populations in low- and middle-income countries impairs planning, monitoring, and evaluation of interventions. Novel, low-cost methods to develop unbiased survey sampling frames at sub-national, sub-provincial, and even sub-district levels are urgently needed. This article details our experience using remote satellite imagery to develop a provincial-level representative community survey sampling frame to evaluate the effects of a 7-year health system intervention in Sofala Province, Mozambique. Methods: Mozambique's most recent census was conducted in 2007, and no data are readily available to generate enumeration areas for representative health survey sampling frames. To remedy this, we partnered with the Humanitarian OpenStreetMap Team to digitize every building in Sofala and Manica provinces (685,189 Sofala; 925,713 Manica) using up-to-date remote satellite imagery, with final results deposited in the open-source OpenStreetMap database. We then created a probability proportional to size sampling frame by overlaying a grid of 2.106km resolution (0.02 decimal degrees) across each province, and calculating the number of buildings within each grid square. Squares containing buildings were used as our primary sampling unit with replacement. Study teams navigated to the geographic center of each selected square using geographic positioning system coordinates, and then conducted a standard "random walk" procedure to select 20 households for each time a given square was selected. Based on sample size calculations, we targeted a minimum of 1500 households in each province. We selected 88 grids within each province to reach 1760 households, anticipating ongoing conflict and transport issues could preclude the inclusion of some clusters. Results: Civil conflict issues forced the exclusion of 8 of 31 subdistricts in Sofala and 15 of 39 subdistricts in Manica. Using Android tablets, Open Data Kit software, and a remote RedCap data capture system, our final sample included 1549 households in Sofala (4669 adults; 4766 children; 33 missing age) and 1538 households in Manica (4422 adults; 4898 children; 33 missing age). Conclusions: Other implementation or evaluation teams may consider employing similar methods to track population distributions for health systems planning or the development of representative sampling frames using remote satellite imagery.</p>		<p>CE6</p>	<p>Duplicado Pubmed</p>
<p>113</p>	<p>Promoting self-Care of diabetic foot ulcers through a mobile phone app: User-Centered design and evaluation</p>	<p>Background: Without effective self-care, people with diabetic foot ulcers (DFUs) are at risk of prolonged healing times, hospitalization, amputation, and reduced quality of life. Despite these consequences, adherence to DFU self-care remains low. New strategies are needed to engage people in the self-care of their DFUs. Objective: This study aimed to evaluate the usability and potential usefulness of a new mobile phone app to engage people with DFUs in self-care. Methods: We developed a new mobile phone app, MyFootCare, to engage people with DFUs through goals, progress monitoring, and reminders in self-care. Key features included novel visual analytics that automatically extract and monitor DFU size information from mobile phone photos of the foot. A functional prototype of</p>		<p>CE1</p>	<p>Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.</p>

		MyFootCare was created and evaluated through a user-centered design process with 11 participants with DFUs. Data were collected through semistructured interviews discussing existing self-care practices and observations of MyFootCare with participants. Data were analyzed qualitatively through thematic analysis. Results: Key themes were as follows: (1) participants already used mobile phone photos to monitor their DFU progress; (2) participants had limited experience with using mobile phone apps; (3) participants desired the objective DFU size data provided by the tracking feature of MyFootCare to monitor their DFU progress; (4) participants were ambivalent about the MyFootCare goal image and diary features, commenting that these features were useful but also that it was unlikely that they would use them; and (5) participants desired to share their MyFootCare data with their clinicians to demonstrate engagement in self-care and to reflect on their progress. Conclusions: MyFootCare shows promising features to engage people in DFU self-care. Most notably, ulcer size data are useful to monitor progress and engage people. However, more work is needed to improve the usability and accuracy of MyFootCare, that is, by refining the process of taking and analyzing photos of DFUs and removing unnecessary features. These findings open the door for further work to develop a system that is easy to use and functions in everyday life conditions and to test it with people with DFUs and their carers.		
114	Declarative GUIs: Simple, consistent, and verified	Graphical user interfaces (GUIs) are ubiquitous in real-world software and a notorious source of bugs that are difficult to catch through software testing. Model checking has been used to prove the absence of certain kinds of bugs, but model checking works on an abstract model of the GUI application, which might be inconsistent with its implementation. We present a library for developing directly verified, state-dependent GUI applications in the dependently typed programming language Agda. In the library, the type of a GUI's controller depends on a specification of the GUI itself, statically enforcing consistency between them. Arbitrary properties can be defined and proved in terms of user interactions and state transitions. Our library connects to a custom-built Haskell back-end for declarative vector-based GUI elements. Compared to an earlier version of our library built on an existing imperative GUI framework, the more declarative back-end supports simpler definitions and proofs. As a practical application of our library to a safety-critical domain, we present a case study developed in cooperation with the Medical University of Vienna. The case study implements a healthcare process for prescribing anticoagulants, which is highly error-prone when followed manually. Our implementation generates GUIs from an abstract description of a data-aware business process, making our approach easy to reuse and adapt to other safety-critical processes. We prove medically relevant safety properties about the executable GUI application, such as that given certain inputs, certain states must or must not be reached.		CE1 Não deixa explícito o uso de código-abierto.
115	A review and classification of assisted living systems	Europe's social agenda for the "active elderly" is based upon a series of programs that provide a flexible infrastructure for their lives so that they are motivated, engaged in lifelong learning, and contributing to society. Economically speaking, Europe must engage in active aging research in order to avoid unsustainable health costs, and ambient assisted living (AAL) systems provide a platform for the elderly to remain living independently. This paper reviews research conducted within the area of AAL, and offers a taxonomy within which such systems may be classified. This classification distinguishes itself from others in that it categorises AAL systems in a top-down fashion, with the most important categories placed immediately to the left. In this paper, each section is explored further, and AAL systems are the focus. Entire AAL systems still cannot be fully evaluated, but their constituent technical parts can be assessed. The activities of daily living (ADLs) component was given further priority due to its potential for system evaluation, based on its ability to recognise ADLs with reasonable accuracy.		CE5 Revisão da literatura
116	MIRACUM: Medical Informatics in Research and	ARCHITECTURAL FRAMEWORK AND METHODOLOGY: The MIRACUM DIC architecture builds on a comprehensive ecosystem of reusable open source tools (MIRACOLIX), which are linkable and interoperable amongst each other, but also with the existing software environment of the MIRACUM hospitals. Efficient data protection measures, considering patient consent, data harmonization and a MIRACUM metadata repository as well as a common data model are major pillars		CE6 Duplicado Pubmed

	Care in University Medicine	of this framework. The methodological approach for shared data usage relies on a federated querying and analysis concept.			
117	Real-Time Adaptation to Time-Varying Constraints for Medical Video Communications	The wider adoption of mobile Health video communication systems in standard clinical practice requires real-time control to provide for adequate levels of clinical video quality to support reliable diagnosis. The latter can only be achieved with real-time adaptation to time-varying wireless networks' state to guarantee clinically acceptable performance throughout the streaming session, while conforming to device capabilities for supporting real-time encoding. We propose an adaptive video encoding framework based on multi-objective optimization that jointly maximizes the encoded video's quality and encoding rate (in frames per second) while minimizing bitrate demands. For this purpose, we construct a dense encoding space and use linear regression to estimate forward prediction models for quality, bitrate, and computational complexity. The prediction models are then used in an adaptive control framework that can fine-tune video encoding based on real-time constraints. We validate the system using a leave-one-out algorithm applied to ten ultrasound videos of the common carotid artery. The prediction models can estimate structural similarity quality with a median accuracy error of less than 1%, bitrate demands with deviation error of 10% or less, and encoding frame rate within a 6% margin. Real-time adaptation at a group of pictures level is demonstrated using the high efficiency video coding standard. The effectiveness of the proposed framework compared to static, nonadaptive approaches is demonstrated for different modes of operation, achieving significant quality gains, bitrate demands reductions, and performance improvements, in real-life scenarios imposing time-varying constraints. Our approach is generic and should be applicable to other medical video modalities with different applications.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
118	Systematic analyses of drug and disease indications in RepurposeDB reveal pharmacological, biological and epidemiological factors influencing drug repositioning	Increase in global population and growing disease burden due to the emergence of infectious diseases (Zika virus), multidrug-resistant pathogens, drug-resistant cancers (cisplatin-resistant ovarian cancer) and chronic diseases (arterial hypertension) necessitate effective therapies to improve health outcomes. However, the rapid increase in drug development cost demands innovative and sustainable drug discovery approaches. Drug repositioning, the discovery of new or improved therapies by reevaluation of approved or investigational compounds, solves a significant gap in the public health setting and improves the productivity of drug development. As the number of drug repurposing investigations increases, a new opportunity has emerged to understand factors driving drug repositioning through systematic analyses of drugs, drug targets and associated disease indications. However, such analyses have so far been hampered by the lack of a centralized knowledgebase, benchmarking data sets and reporting standards. To address these knowledge and clinical needs, here, we present RepurposeDB, a collection of repurposed drugs, drug targets and diseases, which was assembled, indexed and annotated from public data. RepurposeDB combines information on 253 drugs [small molecules (74.30%) and protein drugs (25.29%)] and 1125 diseases. Using RepurposeDB data, we identified pharmacological (chemical descriptors, physicochemical features and absorption, distribution, metabolism, excretion and toxicity properties), biological (protein domains, functional process, molecular mechanisms and pathway cross talks) and epidemiological (shared genetic architectures, disease comorbidities and clinical phenotype similarities) factors mediating drug repositioning. Collectively, RepurposeDB is developed as the reference database for drug repositioning investigations. The pharmacological, biological and epidemiological principles of drug repositioning identified from the meta-analyses could augment therapeutic development.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
119	Cyber-physical system for stroke detection	Stroke is one of the fatal diseases that affect the brain and causes death within 3 to 10 h. However, most of the deaths caused by a stroke can be avoided with the identification of the nature of stroke and react to it in a timely manner by intelligent health systems. The state-of-the-art cyber-physical systems (CPS) enable interaction between physical and computational world to identify any anomaly in the physical world and respond to it. The response of CPS may vary depending		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.

		upon the context of the physical world. Extensive research has been done in this area from the perspective of wireless sensor networks, body area networks, and wearable smart devices. This paper proposes a CPS for detecting the occurrence of stroke in patients, who have a high risk of stroke or have survived a stroke before. The developed CPS sends recorded data to the doctor and alerts him when the stroke occurs. The proposed system is operating on data acquired from electroencephalography sensors from patients' brain. This article aimed at decreasing human mortality rate due to stroke and will bridge the gaps in CPS due to interdisciplinary isolation. The disciplines involved in the development of a CPS include communication networks, pattern recognition, software engineering, mathematics, and biomedical.			
120	ProFUSO: Business process and ontology-based framework to develop ubiquitous computing support systems for chronic patients' management	New advances in telemedicine, ubiquitous computing, and artificial intelligence have supported the emergence of more advanced applications and support systems for chronic patients. This trend addresses the important problem of chronic illnesses, highlighted by multiple international organizations as a core issue in future healthcare. Despite the myriad of exciting new developments, each application and system is designed and implemented for specific purposes and lacks the flexibility to support different healthcare concerns. Some of the known problems of such developments are the integration issues between applications and existing healthcare systems, the reusability of technical knowledge in the creation of new and more sophisticated systems and the usage of data gathered from multiple sources in the generation of new knowledge. This paper proposes a framework for the development of chronic disease support systems and applications as an answer to these shortcomings. Through this framework our pursuit is to create a common ground methodology upon which new developments can be created and easily integrated to provide better support to chronic patients, medical staff and other relevant participants. General requirements are inferred for any support system from the primary attention process of chronic patients by the Business Process Management Notation. Numerous technical approaches are proposed to design a general architecture that considers the medical organizational requirements in the treatment of a patient. A framework is presented for any application in support of chronic patients and evaluated by a case study to test the applicability and pertinence of the solution.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
121	Online efficient bio-medical video transcoding on MPSoCs through content-aware workload allocation	Bio-medical image processing in the field of telemedicine, and in particular the definition of systems that allow medical diagnostics in a collaborative and distributed way is experiencing an undeniable growth. Due to the high quality of bio-medical videos and the subsequent large volumes of data generated, to enable medical diagnosis on-the-go it is imperative to efficiently transcode and stream the stored videos on real time, without quality loss. However, online video transcoding is a high-demanding computationally-intensive task and its efficient management in Multiprocessor Systems-on-Chip (MPSoCs) poses an important challenge. In this work, we propose an efficient motion- and texture-aware frame-level parallelization approach to enable online medical imaging transcoding on MPSoCs for next generation video encoders. By exploiting the unique characteristics of bio-medical videos and the medical procedure that enable diagnosis, we split frames into tiles based on their motion and texture, deciding the most adequate level of parallelization. Then, we employ the available encoding parameters to satisfy the required video quality and compression. Moreover, we propose a new fast motion search algorithm for bio-medical videos that allows to drastically reduce the computational complexity of the encoder, thus achieving the frame rates required for online transcoding. Finally, we heuristically allocate the threads to the most appropriate available resources and set the operating frequency of each one. We evaluate our work on an enterprise multicore server achieving online medical imaging with 1.6x higher throughput and 44% less power consumption when compared to the state-of-the-art techniques.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
122	Addressing the unique healthcare needs of women:	Introduction: Women have unique healthcare needs that are not well addressed by our current healthcare system and with healthcare transformation underway the opportunity exists to avoid weaving these age-old problems into the fabric of the new healthcare design. myAva is an example of a learning health system integrated into a cloud-based precision health platform. The goal of myAva is to integrate the		CE6	Duplicade Pubmed

	<p>Opportunity for change exists at the intersection of precision health and learning health systems</p>	<p>tools of precision health and principals of a learning health system to improve care for women, starting with polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS). Methods: Putting patients at the center in designing a new style of healthcare has been an important concept underlying the development of myAva since inception. Understanding the needs of patients and providers is key to the development of myAva. Surveys were collected from members of the PCOS patient community and patient and medical advisory boards were recruited. For the pilot group comprehensive omic data, biometric and self-reported data were collected and integrated into a personalized health dashboard enabling providers to formulate personalized treatment plans. The ongoing collection of data will create continuous improvement of healthcare. Results: Precision health for chronic issues faced is in its infancy and although myriad challenges exist the potential to improve health outcomes is great. myAva's providers, patients, and advisors are encouraged by the early outcomes of the program with improved health outcomes and an increased sense of empowerment reported. It is clear that designing and implementing this type of care requires collaboration, the involvement of all stakeholders, with patients at the center.</p>			
123	<p>Focus section on health IT usability: Perceived burden of EHRs on physicians at different stages of their career</p>	<p>Objective The purpose of this study was to further explore the effect of EHRs on emergency department (ED) attending and resident physicians' perceived workload, satisfaction, and productivity through the completion of six EHR patient scenarios combined with workload, productivity, and satisfaction surveys. Methods To examine EHR usability, we used a live observational design combined with post observation surveys conducted over 3 days, observing emergency physicians' interactions with the EHR during a 1-hour period. Physicians were asked to complete six patient scenarios in the EHR, and then participants filled two surveys to assess the perceived workload and satisfaction with the EHR interface. Results Fourteen physicians participated, equally distributed by gender (50% females) and experience (43% residents, 57% attendings). Frustration levels associated to the EHR were significantly higher for attending physicians compared with residents. Among the factors causing high EHR frustrations are: (1) remembering menu and button names and commands use; (2) performing tasks that are not straightforward; (3) system speed; and (4) system reliability. In comparisons between attending and resident physicians, time to complete half of the cases as well as the overall reaction to the EHR were statistically different. Conclusion ED physicians already have the highest levels of burnout and fourth lowest level of satisfaction among physicians and, hence, particular attention is needed to study the impact of EHR on ED physicians. This study investigated key EHR usability barriers in the ED particularly, the assess frustration levels among physicians based on experience, and identifying factors impacting those levels of frustrations. In our findings, we highlight the most favorable and most frustrating EHR functionalities between both groups of physicians.</p>		CE1	<p>Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.</p>
124	<p>Implementing an open source electronic health record system in Kenyan health care facilities: Case study</p>	<p>Background: The Kenyan government, working with international partners and local organizations, has developed an eHealth strategy, specified standards, and guidelines for electronic health record adoption in public hospitals and implemented two major health information technology projects: District Health Information Software Version 2, for collating national health care indicators and a rollout of the KenyaEMR and International Quality Care Health Management Information Systems, for managing 600 HIV clinics across the country. Following these projects, a modified version of the Open Medical Record System electronic health record was specified and developed to fulfill the clinical and administrative requirements of health care facilities operated by devolved counties in Kenya and to automate the process of collating health care indicators and entering them into the District Health Information Software Version 2 system. Objective: We aimed to present a descriptive case study of the implementation of an open source electronic health record system in public health care facilities in Kenya. Methods: We conducted a landscape review of existing literature concerning eHealth policies and electronic health record development in Kenya. Following initial discussions with the Ministry of Health, the World Health Organization, and implementing partners, we conducted a series of visits to implementing sites to conduct semistructured individual interviews and group discussions with stakeholders to produce a historical case study of the implementation. Results: This case study</p>	CII		

		describes how consultants based in Kenya, working with developers in India and project stakeholders, implemented the new system into several public hospitals in a county in rural Kenya. The implementation process included upgrading the hospital information technology infrastructure, training users, and attempting to garner administrative and clinical buy-in for adoption of the system. The initial deployment was ultimately scaled back due to a complex mix of sociotechnical and administrative issues. Learning from these early challenges, the system is now being redesigned and prepared for deployment in 6 new counties across Kenya. Conclusions: Implementing electronic health record systems is a challenging process in high-income settings. In low-income settings, such as Kenya, open source software may offer some respite from the high costs of software licensing, but the familiar challenges of clinical and administration buy-in, the need to adequately train users, and the need for the provision of ongoing technical support are common across the North-South divide. Strategies such as creating local support teams, using local development resources, ensuring end user buy-in, and rolling out in smaller facilities before larger hospitals are being incorporated into the project. These are positive developments to help maintain momentum as the project continues. Further integration with existing open source communities could help ongoing development and implementations of the project. We hope this case study will provide some lessons and guidance for other challenging implementations of electronic health record systems as they continue across Africa.			
125	Kanban in software engineering: A systematic mapping study	Following a well-established track record of success in other domains such as manufacturing, Kanban is increasingly used to achieve continuous development and delivery of value in the software industry. However, while research on Kanban in software is growing, these articles are largely descriptive, and there is limited rigorous research on its application and with little cohesive building of cumulative knowledge. As a result, it is extremely difficult to determine the true value of Kanban in software engineering. This study investigates the scientific evidence to date regarding Kanban by conducting a systematic mapping of Kanban literature in software engineering between 2006 and 2016. The search strategy resulted in 382 studies, of which 23 were identified as primary papers relevant to this research. This study is unique as it compares the findings of these primary papers with insights from a review of 23 Kanban experience reports during the same period. This study makes four important contributions, (i) a state-of-the-art of Kanban research is provided, (ii) the reported benefits and challenges are identified in both the primary papers and experience reports, (iii) recommended practices from both the primary papers and experience reports are listed and (iv) opportunities for future Kanban research are identified.		CE5	Mapeamento sistemático da literatura.
126	Towards Emotionally Aware AI Smart Classroom: Current Issues and Directions for Engineering and Education	Future smart classrooms that we envision will significantly enhance learning experience and seamless communication among students and teachers using real-Time sensing and machine intelligence. Existing developments in engineering have brought the state-of-The-Art to an inflection point, where they can be utilized as components of a smart classroom. In this paper, we propose a smart classroom system that consists of these components. Our proposed system is capable of making real-Time suggestions to an in-class presenter to improve the quality and memorability of their presentation by allowing the presenter to make real-Time adjustments/corrections to their non-verbal behavior, such as hand gestures, facial expressions, and body language. We base our suggested system components on existing research in affect sensing, deep learning-based emotion recognition, and real-Time mobile-cloud computing. We provide a comprehensive study of these technologies and determine the computational requirements of a system that incorporates these technologies. Based on these requirements, we provide a feasibility study of the system. Although the state-of-The-Art research in most of the components we propose in our system are advanced enough to realize the system, the main challenge lies in: 1) the integration of these technologies into a holistic system design; 2) their algorithmic adaptation to allow real-Time execution; and 3) quantification of valid educational variables for use in algorithms. In this paper, we discuss current issues and provide future directions in engineering and education disciplines to deploy the proposed system.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.

127	Overcoming barriers to healthcare access and delivery	Access to standard and economical health care delivery, availability of significant health information are viewed as some of the most functional public health interventions in present-day history. Despite that, current information obtained from the WHO regarding Nigeria's health condition shows that the average existence expectancy is at 54 years and maternal mortality at 608 per 100,000 live births as a result of poor health care services. Several aspects of health informatics have been applied to solve these challenges such as the transformation of records from manual to electronic. Among these are the telemedicine and socialized healthcare, which have been barely adopted in developing nations. This work thus proposes an architectural framework for a cloud-supported socialized healthcare system. In order to achieve this; a web-based application software was designed and implemented through the use of cloud computing technology platforms and server side scripting tools. This study proves that socialized healthcare will really go a long way in defeating barriers of viable human access and delivery.	CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
128	A systematic review of the use of blockchain in healthcare	Blockchain technology enables a decentralized and distributed environment with no need for a central authority. Transactions are simultaneously secure and trustworthy due to the use of cryptographic principles. In recent years, blockchain technology has become very trendy and penetrated different domains, mostly due to the popularity of cryptocurrencies. One field where blockchain technology has tremendous potential is healthcare, due to the need for a more patient-centric approach to healthcare systems and to connect disparate systems and increase the accuracy of electronic healthcare records (EHRs). In this systematic review, an analysis of state-of-the-art blockchain research in the field of healthcare is conducted. The aim is to reveal the potential applications of the technology and to highlight the challenges and possible directions of blockchain research in healthcare. First, background information is discussed, followed by a description of the exact methodology used in this paper. Next, an analysis of the results is given, which includes a bibliometric overview, an analysis of gathered data and its properties, and the results of a literature quality assessment. Lastly, there is a discussion of the results from the analysis. The findings indicate that blockchain technology research in healthcare is increasing and it is mostly used for data sharing, managing health records and access control. Other scenarios are very rare. Most research is aimed at presenting novel structural designs in the form of frameworks, architectures or models. Findings also show that technical details about the used blockchain elements are not given in most of the analyzed publications and that most research does not present any prototype implementation or implementation details. Often even with a prototype implementation, no details about blockchain elements are given.	CE5	Revisão sistemática da literatura.
129	Health big data analytics: A technology survey	Because of the vast availability of data, there has been an additional focus on the health industry and an increasing number of studies that aim to leverage the data to improve healthcare have been conducted. The health data are growing increasingly large, more complex, and its sources have increased tremendously to include computerized physician order entry, electronic medical records, clinical notes, medical images, cyber-physical systems, medical Internet of Things, genomic data, and clinical decision support systems. New types of data from sources like social network services and genomic data are used to build personalized healthcare systems, hence health data are obtained in various forms, from varied sources, contexts, technologies, and their nature can impede a proper analysis. Any analytical research must overcome these obstacles to mine data and produce meaningful insights to save lives. In this paper, we investigate the key challenges, data sources, techniques, technologies, as well as future directions in the field of big data analytics in healthcare. We provide a do-it-yourself review that delivers a holistic, simplified, and easily understandable view of various technologies that are used to develop an integrated health analytic application.	CE5	Survey
130	A progress report on the state of pharmacy informatics	Objective. To characterize informatics education opportunities in US colleges and schools of pharmacy curricula. Methods. Informatics curricular information online was catalogued via publicly available websites. Website content was searched via domain-specific keywords. Online course descriptions were reviewed. Website searches were also conducted for informatics-related opportunities. Results. Of 132 pharmacy curricula found online, 47 (36%) included an informatics course. Of	CE5	Revisão da literatura.

	education in us pharmacy schools and colleges	those, 64% (n530) were required while 47% (n522) were elective courses. Additionally, 20% (n526) provided informatics advanced and/or introductory pharmacy practice experiences, 20% (n527) offered an informatics residency, and 17% (n522) listed certificate and/or graduate degree programs in informatics. Conclusion. Over the past 10 years, little observable progress has been made in pharmacy school curricula in response to the increasing importance of informatics to the profession. Pharmacy programs can address this educational gap by internal (eg, course development) and external (eg, open source curriculum) solutions.			
131	Semi-autonomous electrosurgery for tumor resection using a multi-degree of freedom electrosurgical tool and visual servoing	This paper specifies a surgical robot performing semi-autonomous electrosurgery for tumor resection and evaluates its accuracy using a visual servoing paradigm. We describe the design and integration of a novel, multi-degree of freedom electrosurgical tool for the smart tissue autonomous robot (STAR). Standardized line tests are executed to determine ideal cut parameters in three different types of porcine tissue. STAR is then programmed with the ideal cut setting for porcine tissue and compared against expert surgeons using open and laparoscopic techniques in a line cutting task. We conclude with a proof of concept demonstration using STAR to semi-autonomously resect pseudo-tumors in porcine tissue using visual servoing. When tasked to excise tumors with a consistent 4mm margin, STAR can semi-autonomously dissect tissue with an average margin of 3.67 mm and a standard deviation of 0.89mm.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
132	Cloud-based interactive analytics for terabytes of genomic variants data	Motivation: Large scale genomic sequencing is now widely used to decipher questions in diverse realms such as biological function, human diseases, evolution, ecosystems, and agriculture. With the quantity and diversity these data harbor, a robust and scalable data handling and analysis solution is desired. Results: We present interactive analytics using a cloud-based columnar database built on Dremel to perform information compression, comprehensive quality controls, and biological information retrieval in large volumes of genomic data. We demonstrate such Big Data computing paradigms can provide orders of magnitude faster turnaround for common genomic analyses, transforming long-running batch jobs submitted via a Linux shell into questions that can be asked from a web browser in seconds. Using this method, we assessed a study population of 475 deeply sequenced human genomes for genomic call rate, genotype and allele frequency distribution, variant density across the genome, and pharmacogenomic information.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
133	Combining Ontologies and Open Standards to Derive a Middle Layer Information Model for Interoperability of Personal and Electronic Health Records	The aim of our study was to enable better interoperability between Personal Health Record (PHR) and Electronic Health Record (EHR) systems and vice versa. A multi-layer architectural model that resides between a PHR and EHR system has been developed. The model consists of an ontology-driven information model and a set of transformation rules that work in conjunction to process data exported from a PHR or EHR system and prepare it accordingly for the receiving system. The model was evaluated by executing a set of case study scenarios containing data from both a PHR and an EHR system. This allowed various challenges to emerge and revealed gaps in current standards in use. The proposed information model offers a number of advantages. Altering only the information model can incorporate modifications to either a PHR or EHR system. The model uses classes and attributes to define how data is captured which allows greater flexibility in how data can be manipulated by receiving systems.	CII		
134	Improving maternity care with business intelligence	The aim of this paper is to develop clinical indicators for obstetrics through the use of Business Intelligence (BI) tools, since valid and reliable clinical indicators can help measuring quality of healthcare services and support decision-making processes. This paper gives an overview of concepts related to Health Information Systems (HIS) and BI, along with some related work to highlight the advantages that BI solutions can bring when applied to healthcare. In this paper is also presented the data warehousing and the ETL process, that was necessary for the development of indicators and which is usually hidden from endusers, is described. The indicators were developed using Power BI and were analysed and compared with reference values from both national and international health reports. The discussion of the developed indicators made it possible to measure the quality of the obstetrics service, to identify the problematic areas and to decide whether improvement measures should be taken.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.

135	<p>eWALL: An Open-Source Cloud-Based eHealth Platform for Creating Home-Caring Environments for Older Adults Living with Chronic Diseases or Frailty</p>	<p>Independent living of older adults is one of the main challenges linked to the ageing population. Especially those living with diseases like COPD, MCI or frailty, need more support in everyday life and this is by itself a big societal challenge with impact in multiple sectors. In this paper we present eWALL, an innovative open-source eHealth platform that aims to address these challenges by means of an advanced cloud-based infrastructure. eWALL is designed in an innovative manner and achieved technical breakthroughs in eHealth platforms, while prioritizing user and market needs that are often abandoned and are the major reason for technically sound solutions that fail. We consider this as an opportunity and we aim to change the eHealth systems' experience for older adults and break the barriers for the penetration of ICT solutions.</p>	CII		
136	<p>Design and implementation of an archetype based interoperable knowledge eco-system for data buoys</p>	<p>This paper describes the ongoing work of the authors in translating two-level system design techniques used in Health Informatics to the Earth Systems Science domain. Health informaticians have developed a sophisticated two-level systems design approach for electronic health documentation over many years, and with the use of archetypes, have shown how knowledge interoperability among heterogeneous systems can be achieved. Translating two-level modelling techniques to a new domain is a complex task. A proof-of-concept archetype enabled data buoy eco-system is presented. The concept of operational templates-as-a-service is proposed. Design recommendations and implementation experiences of re-working the proposed architecture to run on ultra-resource constrained data buoy platforms using templates-as-service are described.</p>		CE1	<p>Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.</p>
137	<p>ECG classification and prognostic approach towards personalized healthcare</p>	<p>A very important aspect of personalized healthcare is to continuously monitor an individual's health using wearable biomedical devices and essentially to analyse and if possible to predict potential health hazards that may prove fatal if not treated in time. The prediction aspect embedded in the system helps in avoiding delays in providing timely medical treatment, even before an individual reaches a critical condition. Despite of the availability of modern wearable health monitoring devices, the real-time analyses and prediction component seems to be missing with these devices. The research work illustrated in this paper, at an outset, focussed on constantly monitoring an individual's ECG readings using a wearable 3-lead ECG kit and more importantly focussed on performing real-time analyses to detect arrhythmia to be able to identify and predict heart risk. Also, current research shows extensive use of heart rate variability (HRV) analysis and machine learning for arrhythmia classification, which however depends on the morphology of the ECG waveforms and the sensitivity of the ECG equipment. Since a wearable 3-lead ECG kit was used, the accuracy of classification had to be dealt with at the machine learning phase, so a unique feature extraction method was developed to increase the accuracy of classification. As a case study a very widely used Arrhythmia database (MIT-BIH, Physionet) was used to develop learning, classification and prediction models. Neuralnet fitting models on the extracted features showed mean-squared error of as low as 0.0085 and regression value as high as 0.99. Current experiments show 99.4% accuracy using k-NN Classification models and show values of Cross-Entropy Error of 7.6 and misclassification error value of 1.2 on test data using scaled conjugate gradient pattern matching algorithms. Software components were developed for wearable devices that took ECG readings from a 3-Lead ECG data acquisition kit in real time, de-noised, filtered and relayed the sample readings to the tele health analytical server. The analytical server performed the classification and prediction tasks based on the trained classification models and could raise appropriate alarms if ECG abnormalities of V (Premature Ventricular Contraction: PVC), A (Atrial Premature Beat: APB), L (Left bundle branch block beat), R (Right bundle branch block beat) type annotations in MITDB were detected. The instruments were networked using IoT (Internet of Things) devices and abnormal ECG events related to arrhythmia, from analytical server could be logged using an FHIR web service implementation, according to a SNOMED coding system and could be accessed in Electronic Health Record by the concerned medic to take appropriate and timely decisions. The system focused on 'preventive care rather</p>		CE1	<p>Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.</p>

		than remedial cure' which has become a major focus of all the health care and cure institutions across the globe.			
138	Satisfaction with paper-based dental records and perception of electronic dental records among dental professionals in Myanmar	Objectives: To overcome challenges in the implementation of electronic dental record systems in a low-resource setting, it is crucial to know the level of users' satisfaction with the existing system of paper-based dental records and their perceptions of electronic dental records. Methods: A cross-sectional paper-based questionnaire survey was conducted among Myanmar dental professionals who worked in one of two teaching hospitals or in private dental clinics. Descriptive data were analyzed and regression analysis was carried out to identify factors influencing perceptions of electronic dental records. Results: Most dental professionals (>60%) were satisfied with just three out of six aspects of paper-based dental records (familiarity, flexibility, and portability). In addition, generalized positive perceptions were found among decision makers towards electronic dental records, and 86% of dentists indicated that they were willing to use them. Financial concerns were identified as the most important barrier to the implementation of electronic dental records among dentists who were not willing to use the proposed system. Conclusions: The first step towards implementing electronic dental records in Myanmar should be improvement of the content and structure of paper-based dental records, especially in private dental clinics. Utilization of appropriate open-source electronic dental record software in private dental clinics is recommended to address perceived issues around financial barriers. For the long term, we recommend providing further education and training in health informatics to healthcare professionals to facilitate the efficient use of electronic dental record software in Myanmar in the future.		CE6	Duplicada Pubmed
139	Ranking medical terms to support expansion of lay language resources for patient comprehension of electronic health record notes: Adapted distant supervision approach	Background: Medical terms are a major obstacle for patients to comprehend their electronic health record (EHR) notes. Clinical natural language processing (NLP) systems that link EHR terms to lay terms or definitions allow patients to easily access helpful information when reading through their EHR notes, and have shown to improve patient EHR comprehension. However, high-quality lay language resources for EHR terms are very limited in the public domain. Because expanding and curating such a resource is a costly process, it is beneficial and even necessary to identify terms important for patient EHR comprehension first. Objective: We aimed to develop an NLP system, called adapted distant supervision (ADS), to rank candidate terms mined from EHR corpora. We will give EHR terms ranked as high by ADS a higher priority for lay language annotation-that is, creating lay definitions for these terms. Methods: Adapted distant supervision uses distant supervision from consumer health vocabulary and transfer learning to adapt itself to solve the problem of ranking EHR terms in the target domain. We investigated 2 state-of-the-art transfer learning algorithms (ie, feature space augmentation and supervised distant supervision) and designed 5 types of learning features, including distributed word representations learned from large EHR data for ADS. For evaluating ADS, we asked domain experts to annotate 6038 candidate terms as important or nonimportant for EHR comprehension. We then randomly divided these data into the target-domain training data (1000 examples) and the evaluation data (5038 examples). We compared ADS with 2 strong baselines, including standard supervised learning, on the evaluation data. Results: The ADS system using feature space augmentation achieved the best average precision, 0.850, on the evaluation set when using 1000 target-domain training examples. The ADS system using supervised distant supervision achieved the best average precision, 0.819, on the evaluation set when using only 100 target-domain training examples. The 2 ADS systems both performed significantly better than the baseline systems (P<.001 for all measures and all conditions). Using a rich set of learning features contributed to ADS's performance substantially. Conclusions: ADS can effectively rank terms mined from EHRs. Transfer learning improved ADS's performance even with a small number of target-domain training examples. EHR terms prioritized by ADS were used to expand a lay language resource that supports patient EHR comprehension. The top 10,000 EHR terms ranked by ADS are available upon request.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.

140	<p>ROS-IGTL: Bridge: an open network interface for image-guided therapy using the ROS environment</p>	<p>Purpose: With the growing interest in advanced image-guidance for surgical robot systems, rapid integration and testing of robotic devices and medical image computing software are becoming essential in the research and development. Maximizing the use of existing engineering resources built on widely accepted platforms in different fields, such as robot operating system (ROS) in robotics and 3D Slicer in medical image computing could simplify these tasks. We propose a new open network bridge interface integrated in ROS to ensure seamless cross-platform data sharing. Methods: A ROS node named ROS-IGTL-Bridge was implemented. It establishes a TCP/IP network connection between the ROS environment and external medical image computing software using the OpenIGTLink protocol. The node exports ROS messages to the external software over the network and vice versa simultaneously, allowing seamless and transparent data sharing between the ROS-based devices and the medical image computing platforms. Results: Performance tests demonstrated that the bridge could stream transforms, strings, points, and images at 30 fps in both directions successfully. The data transfer latency was <1.2 ms for transforms, strings and points, and 25.2 ms for color VGA images. A separate test also demonstrated that the bridge could achieve 900 fps for transforms. Additionally, the bridge was demonstrated in two representative systems: a mock image-guided surgical robot setup consisting of 3D slicer, and Lego Mindstorms with ROS as a prototyping and educational platform for IGT research; and the smart tissue autonomous robot surgical setup with 3D Slicer. Conclusion: The study demonstrated that the bridge enabled cross-platform data sharing between ROS and medical image computing software. This will allow rapid and seamless integration of advanced image-based planning/navigation offered by the medical image computing software such as 3D Slicer into ROS-based surgical robot systems.</p>	CE1	<p>Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.</p>
141	<p>Data driven polypharmacological drug design for lung cancer: Analyses for targeting ALK, MET, and EGFR</p>	<p>Drug design of protein kinase inhibitors is now greatly enabled by thousands of publicly available X-ray structures, extensive ligand binding data, and optimized scaffolds coming off patent. The extensive data begin to enable design against a spectrum of targets (polypharmacology); however, the data also reveal heterogeneities of structure, subtleties of chemical interactions, and apparent inconsistencies between diverse data types. As a result, incorporation of all relevant data requires expert choices to combine computational and informatics methods, along with human insight. Here we consider polypharmacological targeting of protein kinases ALK, MET, and EGFR (and its drug resistant mutant T790M) in non small cell lung cancer as an example. Both EGFR and ALK represent sources of primary oncogenic lesions, while drug resistance arises from MET amplification and EGFR mutation. A drug which inhibits these targets will expand relevant patient populations and forestall drug resistance. Crizotinib co-targets ALK and MET. Analysis of the crystal structures reveals few shared interaction types, highlighting proton-arene and key CH-O hydrogen bonding interactions. These are not typically encoded into molecular mechanics force fields. Cheminformatics analyses of binding data show EGFR to be dissimilar to ALK and MET, but its structure shows how it may be co-targeted with the addition of a covalent trap. This suggests a strategy for the design of a focussed chemical library based on a pan-kinome scaffold. Tests of model compounds show these to be compatible with the goal of ALK, MET, and EGFR polypharmacology.</p>	CE1	<p>Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.</p>
142	<p>Privacy preserving electrocardiogram monitoring for intelligent arrhythmia detection</p>	<p>Long-term electrocardiogram (ECG) monitoring, as a representative application of cyber-physical systems, facilitates the early detection of arrhythmia. A considerable number of previous studies has explored monitoring techniques and the automated analysis of sensing data. However, ensuring patient privacy or confidentiality has not been a primary concern in ECG monitoring. First, we propose an intelligent heart monitoring system, which involves a patient-worn ECG sensor (e.g., a smartphone) and a remote monitoring station, as well as a decision support server that interconnects these components. The decision support server analyzes the heart activity, using the Pan-Tompkins algorithm to detect heartbeats and a decision tree to classify them. Our system protects sensing data and user privacy, which is an essential attribute of dependability, by adopting signal scrambling and anonymous identity schemes. We also employ a public key cryptosystem to enable secure communication between the entities. Simulations using data from the MIT-BIH</p>	CE1	<p>Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.</p>

		arrhythmia database demonstrate that our system achieves a 95.74% success rate in heartbeat detection and almost a 96.63% accuracy in heartbeat classification, while successfully preserving privacy and securing communications among the involved entities.			
143	Identifying opportunities to integrate digital professionalism into curriculum: A comparison of social media use by health profession students at an Australian university in 2013 and 2016	Social media has become ubiquitous to modern life. Consequently, embedding digital professionalism into undergraduate health profession courses is now imperative and augmenting learning and teaching with mobile technology and social media on and off campus is a current curriculum focus. The aim of this study was to explore whether patterns of social media use for personal or informal learning by undergraduate health profession students enrolled at an Australian university across four campuses has changed over time. A previously validated online survey was administered in 2013 to a cohort of health profession students as part of an Australian survey. In 2016, the same survey was distributed to a later cohort of health profession students. Three open-ended questions to elicit descriptive information regarding the use of social media for study purposes were added to the later survey. A comparative analysis of both cohorts was undertaken and social media acceptance and penetration was shown to increase. Health profession students are now more interactive users of Facebook and Twitter, and they have become more familiar with career development sites, such as LinkedIn. The maturation of social media platforms within a three-year period has created realistic opportunities to integrate social media for personal and study purposes into the health profession education curriculum to ensure student understanding of the necessity for maintaining digital professionalism in the workplace.		CE5	Survey
144	iGAS: A framework for using electronic intraoperative medical records for genomic discovery	Objective Design and implement a HIPAA and Integrating the Healthcare Enterprise (IHE) profile compliant automated pipeline, the integrated Genomics Anesthesia System (iGAS), linking genomic data from the Mount Sinai Health System (MSHS) BioMe biobank to electronic anesthesia records, including physiological data collected during the perioperative period. The resulting repository of multi-dimensional data can be used for precision medicine analysis of physiological readouts, acute medical conditions, and adverse events that can occur during surgery. Materials and methods A structured pipeline was developed atop our existing anesthesia data warehouse using open-source tools. The pipeline is automated using scheduled tasks. The pipeline runs weekly, and finds and identifies all new and existing anesthetic records for BioMe participants. Results The pipeline went live in June 2015 with 49.2% (n = 15,673) of BioMe participants linked to 40,947 anesthetics. The pipeline runs weekly in minimal time. After eighteen months, an additional 3671 participants were enrolled in BioMe and the number of matched anesthetic records grew 21% to 49,545. Overall percentage of BioMe patients with anesthetics remained similar at 51.1% (n = 18,128). Seven patients opted out during this time. The median number of anesthetics per participant was 2 (range 1–144). Collectively, there were over 35 million physiologic data points and 480,000 medication administrations linked to genomic data. To date, two projects are using the pipeline at MSHS. Conclusion Automated integration of biobank and anesthetic data sources is feasible and practical. This integration enables large-scale genomic analyses that might inform variable physiological response to anesthetic and surgical stress, and examine genetic factors underlying adverse outcomes during and after surgery.		CE6	Duplicado Pubmed
145	Integrating learning management system with facebook function: The effect on perception towards online project based collaborative	This study evaluates the effect on Perception towards Online Project Based Collaborative Learning (OPBCL). OPBCL was developed by integrating Moodle forum with Facebook function and using project based learning approach. A quasi-experiment was conducted with two classes of polytechnic students for three weeks which involved 54 students. Data were obtained using Perception of Online Collaborative Learning Questionnaire (POCLQ). The study was conducted to evaluate students' perceptions toward CIDOS and OPBCL platform based on Learning Environment (LE), Learning Design (LD), Learning Interaction (LI) and Soft Skills (SS) construct. All collected data were analysed using SPSS 19.0 software. Overall, the findings revealed that perception score in OPBCL platform is higher than CIDOS platform. Evaluation based on constructs showed that except for LD construct, other constructs have shown that score in OPBCL platform is higher than CIDOS platform. OPBCL has shown to be a better online learning		CE1	Não é da área da saúde.

		platform that can promote students' interaction in project based learning approach.			
146	<p>learning</p> <p>Predictive modeling of hospital readmission rates using electronic medical record-wide machine learning: A case-study using mount sinai heart failure cohort</p>	<p>Reduction of preventable hospital readmissions that result from chronic or acute conditions like stroke, heart failure, myocardial infarction and pneumonia remains a significant challenge for improving the outcomes and decreasing the cost of healthcare delivery in the United States. Patient readmission rates are relatively high for conditions like heart failure (HF) despite the implementation of high-quality healthcare delivery operation guidelines created by regulatory authorities. Multiple predictive models are currently available to evaluate potential 30-day readmission rates of patients. Most of these models are hypothesis driven and repetitively assess the predictive abilities of the same set of biomarkers as predictive features. In this manuscript, we discuss our attempt to develop a data-driven, electronic-medical record-wide (EMR-wide) feature selection approach and subsequent machine learning to predict readmission probabilities. We have assessed a large repertoire of variables from electronic medical records of heart failure patients in a single center. The cohort included 1,068 patients with 178 patients were readmitted within a 30-day interval (16.66% readmission rate). A total of 4,205 variables were extracted from EMR including diagnosis codes (n=1,763), medications (n=1,028), laboratory measurements (n=846), surgical procedures (n=564) and vital signs (n=4). We designed a multistep modeling strategy using the Naïve Bayes algorithm. In the first step, we created individual models to classify the cases (readmitted) and controls (non-readmitted). In the second step, features contributing to predictive risk from independent models were combined into a composite model using a correlation-based feature selection (CFS) method. All models were trained and tested using a 5-fold cross-validation method, with 70% of the cohort used for training and the remaining 30% for testing. Compared to existing predictive models for HF readmission rates (AUCs in the range of 0.6-0.7), results from our EMR-wide predictive model (AUC=0.78; Accuracy=83.19%) and phenome-wide feature selection strategies are encouraging and reveal the utility of such data-driven machine learning. Fine tuning of the model, replication using multi-center cohorts and prospective clinical trial to evaluate the clinical utility would help the adoption of the model as a clinical decision system for evaluating readmission status.</p>		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
147	<p>Quantifying user reputation scores, data trustworthiness, and user incentives in mobile crowd-sensing</p>	<p>Ubiquity of mobile devices with rich sensory capabilities has given rise to the mobile crowd-sensing (MCS) concept, in which a central authority (the platform) and its participants (mobile users) work collaboratively to acquire sensory data over a wide geographic area. Recent research in MCS highlights the following facts: 1) a utility metric can be defined for both the platform and the users, quantifying the value received by either side; 2) incentivizing the users to participate is a non-trivial challenge; 3) correctness and truthfulness of the acquired data must be verified, because the users might provide incorrect or inaccurate data, whether due to malicious intent or malfunctioning devices; and 4) an intricate relationship exists among platform utility, user utility, user reputation, and data trustworthiness, suggesting a co-quantification of these inter-related metrics. In this paper, we study two existing approaches that quantify crowd-sensed data trustworthiness, based on statistical and vote-based user reputation scores. We introduce a new metric - collaborative reputation scores - to expand this definition. Our simulation results show that collaborative reputation scores can provide an effective alternative to the previously proposed metrics and are able to extend crowd sensing to applications that are driven by a centralized as well as decentralized control.</p>		CE1	Não é da área da saúde.
148	<p>Leveraging the value of human relationships to improve health outcomes: Lessons learned</p>	<p>Objectives: Despite significant awareness on the value of leveraging patient relationships across the healthcare continuum, there is no research on the potential of using Electronic Health Record (EHR) systems to store structured patient relationship data, or its impact on enabling better healthcare. We sought to identify which EHR systems supported effective patient relationship data collection, and for systems that do, what types of relationship data is collected, how this data is used, and the perceived value of doing so. Materials and methods: We performed a literature search to identify EHR systems that supported patient relationship data</p>		CE5	Survey

	<p>from the OpenMRS electronic health record system</p>	<p>collection. Based on our results, we defined attributes of an effective patient relationship model. The Open Medical Record System (OpenMRS), an open source medical record platform for underserved settings met our eligibility criteria for effective patient relationship collection. We performed a survey to understand how the OpenMRS patient relationship model was used, and how it brought value to implementers. Results: The OpenMRS patient relationship model has won widespread adoption across many implementations and is perceived to be valuable in enabling better health care delivery. Patient relationship information is widely used for community health programs and enabling chronic care. Additionally, many OpenMRS implementers were using this feature to collect custom relationship types for implementation specific needs. Conclusions: We believe that flexible patient relationship data collection is critical for better healthcare, and can inform community care and chronic care initiatives across the world. Additionally, patient relationship data could also be leveraged for many other initiatives such as patient centric care and in the field of precision medicine.</p>			
149	<p>Technology-induced anxiety: Manifestations, cultural influences, and its effect on the adoption of sensor-based technology in German and Australian hospitals</p>	<p>Sensor-based systems have healthcare transformation potential but acceptance problems jeopardize their diffusion. We theorize that perceived technology threats induce anxiety and diminish usage intentions. We use data from the pre-implementation phase in German and Australian hospitals to explore the formation of three types of anxieties, their impact on usage intentions, and the relationships between them and national culture. We find negative effects of relational and work-related anxieties on usage intentions while surveillance anxieties show no association. The anxieties can be partially linked to national culture characteristics. Our findings support implementation initiatives and offer a deeper understanding of technology-induced anxieties.</p>		CE1	<p>Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.</p>
150	<p>VDJML: A file format with tools for capturing the results of inferring immune receptor rearrangements</p>	<p>Background: The genes that produce antibodies and the immune receptors expressed on lymphocytes are not germline encoded; rather, they are somatically generated in each developing lymphocyte by a process called V(D)J recombination, which assembles specific, independent gene segments into mature composite genes. The full set of composite genes in an individual at a single point in time is referred to as the immune repertoire. V(D)J recombination is the distinguishing feature of adaptive immunity and enables effective immune responses against an essentially infinite array of antigens. Characterization of immune repertoires is critical in both basic research and clinical contexts. Recent technological advances in repertoire profiling via high-throughput sequencing have resulted in an explosion of research activity in the field. This has been accompanied by a proliferation of software tools for analysis of repertoire sequencing data. Despite the widespread use of immune repertoire profiling and analysis software, there is currently no standardized format for output files from V(D)J analysis. Researchers utilize software such as IgBLAST and IMGT/High V-QUEST to perform V(D)J analysis and infer the structure of germline rearrangements. However, each of these software tools produces results in a different file format, and can annotate the same result using different labels. These differences make it challenging for users to perform additional downstream analyses. Results: To help address this problem, we propose a standardized file format for representing V(D)J analysis results. The proposed format, VDJML, provides a common standardized format for different V(D)J analysis applications to facilitate downstream processing of the results in an application-agnostic manner. The VDJML file format specification is accompanied by a support library, written in C++ and Python, for reading and writing the VDJML file format. Conclusions: The VDJML suite will allow users to streamline their V(D)J analysis and facilitate the sharing of scientific knowledge within the community. The VDJML suite and documentation are available from https://vdjserver.org/vdjml/. We welcome participation from the community in developing the file format standard, as well as code contributions.</p>	CII		

151	<p>WaveformECG: A platform for visualizing, annotating, and analyzing ECG data</p>	<p>The electrocardiogram (ECG) is the most commonly collected data in cardiovascular research because of the ease with which it can be measured and the fact that changes in ECG waveforms reflect underlying aspects of heart disease. Despite its ubiquity, there are no open, noncommercial platforms for interactive management, sharing, and analysis of these data. WaveformECG addresses this unmet need. Accessed through a browser, WaveformECG extracts ECGs from vendor files, storing them as a time series with other analysis results and annotations in an open source time-series database. It supports interactive invocation of multiple analysis algorithms on selected ECG datasets, visualization of ECG waveforms, manual annotation of time points and intervals in ECG waveforms, and automated annotation of analysis results using standard medical terminology. Integration with the I2B2 clinical data warehouse system enables bidirectional exchange of data between these two platforms.</p>	CII		
152	<p>A biologically informed method for detecting rare variant associations</p>	<p>Background: BioBin is a bioinformatics software package developed to automate the process of binning rare variants into groups for statistical association analysis using a biological knowledge-driven framework. BioBin collapses variants into biological features such as genes, pathways, evolutionary conserved regions (ECRs), protein families, regulatory regions, and others based on user-designated parameters. BioBin provides the infrastructure to create complex and interesting hypotheses in an automated fashion thereby circumventing the necessity for advanced and time consuming scripting. Purpose of the study: In this manuscript, we describe the software package for BioBin, along with type I error and power simulations to demonstrate the strengths and various customizable features and analysis options of this variant binning tool. Results: Simulation testing highlights the utility of BioBin as a fast, comprehensive and expandable tool for the biologically-inspired binning and analysis of low-frequency variants in sequence data. Conclusions and potential implications: The BioBin software package has the capability to transform and streamline the analysis pipelines for researchers analyzing rare variants. This automated bioinformatics tool minimizes the manual effort of creating genomic regions for binning such that time can be spent on the much more interesting task of statistical analyses. This software package is open source and freely available from http://ritchielab.com/software/biobin-download.</p>		CE5	Duplicate Pubmed
153	<p>The Apollo Structured Vocabulary: An OWL2 ontology of phenomena in infectious disease epidemiology and population biology for use in epidemic simulation</p>	<p>Background: We developed the Apollo Structured Vocabulary (Apollo-SV)-an OWL2 ontology of phenomena in infectious disease epidemiology and population biology-as part of a project whose goal is to increase the use of epidemic simulators in public health practice. Apollo-SV defines a terminology for use in simulator configuration. Apollo-SV is the product of an ontological analysis of the domain of infectious disease epidemiology, with particular attention to the inputs and outputs of nine simulators. Results: Apollo-SV contains 802 classes for representing the inputs and outputs of simulators, of which approximately half are new and half are imported from existing ontologies. The most important Apollo-SV class for users of simulators is infectious disease scenario, which is a representation of an ecosystem at simulator time zero that has at least one infection process (a class) affecting at least one population (also a class). Other important classes represent ecosystem elements (e.g., households), ecosystem processes (e.g., infection acquisition and infectious disease), censuses of ecosystem elements (e.g., censuses of populations), and infectious disease control measures. In the larger project, which created an end-user application that can send the same infectious disease scenario to multiple simulators, Apollo-SV serves as the controlled terminology and strongly influences the design of the message syntax used to represent an infectious disease scenario. As we added simulators for different pathogens (e.g., malaria and dengue), the core classes of Apollo-SV have remained stable, suggesting that our conceptualization of the information required by simulators is sound. Despite adhering to the OBO Foundry principle of orthogonality, we could not reuse Infectious Disease Ontology classes as the basis for infectious disease scenarios. We thus defined new classes in Apollo-SV for host, pathogen, infection, infectious disease, colonization, and infection acquisition. Unlike IDO, our ontological analysis extended to existing mathematical models of key biological phenomena studied by infectious disease epidemiology and population biology. Conclusion: Our ontological analysis as expressed in Apollo-SV was instrumental</p>	CII		

		in developing a simulator-independent representation of infectious disease scenarios that can be run on multiple epidemic simulators. Our experience suggests the importance of extending ontological analysis of a domain to include existing mathematical models of the phenomena studied by the domain. Apollo-SV is freely available at: http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/apollo_sv.owl			
154	An architecture for using commodity devices and smart phones in health systems	The potential of patient-centred care and a connected eHealth ecosystem can be developed through socially responsible innovative architectures. The purpose of this paper is to define key innovation needs. This is achieved through conceptual development of an architecture for common information spaces with emergent end-user applications by supporting intelligent processing of measurements, data and services at the Internet of Things (IoT) integration level. The scope is conceptual definition, and results include descriptions of social, legal and ethical requirements, an architecture, services and connectivity infrastructures for consumer-oriented healthcare systems linking co-existing healthcare systems and consumer devices. We conclude with recommendations based on an analysis of research challenges related to how to process the data securely and anonymously and how to interconnect participants and services with different standards and interaction protocols, and devices with heterogeneous hardware and software configurations.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
155	An ontological model of the practice transformation process	Patient-centered medical home is defined as an approach for providing comprehensive primary care that facilitates partnerships between individual patients and their personal providers. The current state of the practice transformation process is ad hoc and no methodological basis exists for transforming a practice into a patient-centered medical home. Practices and hospitals somehow accomplish the transformation and send the transformation information to a certification agency, such as the National Committee for Quality Assurance, completely ignoring the development and maintenance of the processes that keep the medical home concept alive. Many recent studies point out that such a transformation is hard as it requires an ambitious whole-practice reengineering and redesign. As a result, the practices suffer change fatigue in getting the transformation done. In this paper, we focus on the complexities of the practice transformation process and present a robust ontological model for practice transformation. The objective of the model is to create an understanding of the practice transformation process in terms of key process areas and their activities. We describe how our ontology captures the knowledge of the practice transformation process, elicited from domain experts, and also discuss how, in the future, that knowledge could be diffused across stakeholders in a healthcare organization. Our research is the first effort in practice transformation process modeling. To build an ontological model for practice transformation, we adopt the Methontology approach. Based on the literature, we first identify the key process areas essential for a practice transformation process to achieve certification status. Next, we develop the practice transformation ontology by creating key activities and precedence relationships among the key process areas using process maturity concepts. At each step, we employ a panel of domain experts to verify the intermediate representations of the ontology. Finally, we implement a prototype of the practice transformation ontology using Protégé		CII	
156	Anatomy of an Extensible Open Source PACS	The conception and deployment of cost effective Picture Archiving and Communication Systems (PACS) is a concern for small to medium medical imaging facilities, research environments, and developing countries' healthcare institutions. Financial constraints and the specificity of these scenarios contribute to a low adoption rate of PACS in those environments. Furthermore, with the advent of ubiquitous computing and new initiatives to improve healthcare information technologies and data sharing, such as IHE and XDS-i, a PACS must adapt quickly to changes. This paper describes Dicoogle, a software framework that enables developers and researchers to quickly prototype and deploy new functionality taking advantage of the embedded Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine (DICOM) services. This full-fledged implementation of a PACS archive is very amenable to extension due to its plugin-based architecture and out-of-the-box functionality, which enables the exploration of large DICOM datasets and associated metadata. These characteristics make the proposed solution very interesting for prototyping, experimentation, and bridging functionality with		CII	

		<p>deployed applications. Besides being an advanced mechanism for data discovery and retrieval based on DICOM object indexing, it enables the detection of inconsistencies in an institution's data and processes. Several use cases have benefited from this approach such as radiation dosage monitoring, Content-Based Image Retrieval (CBIR), and the use of the framework as support for classes targeting software engineering for clinical contexts.</p>			
157	<p>Impact of implementing a wiki to develop structured electronic order sets on physicians' intention to use wiki-based order sets</p>	<p>Background: Wikis have the potential to promote best practices in health systems by sharing order sets with a broad community of stakeholders. However, little is known about the impact of using a wiki on clinicians' intention to use wiki-based order sets. Objective: The aims of this study were: (1) to describe the use of a wiki to create structured order sets for a single emergency department; (2) to evaluate whether the use of this wiki changed emergency physicians' future intention to use wiki-based order sets; and (3) to understand the impact of using the wiki on the behavioral determinants for using wiki-based order sets. Methods: This was a pre/post-intervention mixed-methods study conducted in one hospital in Lévis, Quebec. The intervention was comprised of receiving access to and being motivated by the department head to use a wiki for 6 months to create electronic order sets designed to be used in a computer physician order entry system. Before and after our intervention, we asked participants to complete a previously validated questionnaire based on the Theory of Planned Behavior. Our primary outcome was the intention to use wiki-based order sets in clinical practice. We also assessed participants' attitude, perceived behavioral control, and subjective norm to use wiki-based order sets. Paired pre- and post-Likert scores were compared using Wilcoxon signed-rank tests. The post-questionnaire also included open-ended questions concerning participants' comments about the wiki, which were then classified into themes using an existing taxonomy. Results: Twenty-eight emergency physicians were enrolled in the study (response rate: 100%). Physicians' mean intention to use a wiki-based reminder was 5.42 (SD 1.04) before the intervention, and increased to 5.81 (SD 1.25) on a 7-point Likert scale (P=.03) after the intervention. Participants' attitude towards using a wiki-based order set also increased from 5.07 (SD 0.90) to 5.57 (SD 0.88) (P=.003). Perceived behavioral control and subjective norm did not change. Easier information sharing was the most frequently positive impact raised. In order of frequency, the three most important facilitators reported were: Ease of use, support from colleagues, and promotion by the departmental head. Although participants did not mention any perceived negative impacts, they raised the following barriers in order of frequency: Poor organization of information, slow computers, and difficult wiki access. Conclusions: Emergency physicians' intention and attitude to use wiki-based order sets increased after having access to and being motivated to use a wiki for 6 months. Future studies need to explore if this increased intention will translate into sustained actual use and improve patient care. Certain barriers need to be addressed before implementing a wiki for use on a larger scale.</p>		CE1	<p>Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.</p>
158	<p>Using training as a tool for cultivating communities of practice around health information systems in low and middle income countries: A longitudinal mixed method study</p>	<p>Many attempts at implementing health information systems (HISs) in Low and Middle Income Countries (LMICs) have failed to mature or scale into desirable levels due to various reasons. Among these reasons, not identifying the design reality gap, inability to form support networks and non-availability of 'hybrids' who can link between health and information systems domains can be highlighted. In organizational contexts, such challenges can be overcome by cultivating communities of practice (CoPs). However, HIS projects in LMIC contexts may not have the opportunity to create an environment similar to an organization to facilitate cultivation of CoPs. This paper argues that HIS projects in LMICs can utilize formal, informal and workplace based online and face-to-face training methods along with the networking power of free and open source software (FOSS) communities as a means of cultivating CoPs. In substantiating this argument, the paper utilizes a mixed method longitudinal study design to follow-up a group of implementers trained in a FOSS HIS in Sri Lanka. The paper presents a practical training model usable in information system implementations in LMIC settings with the added benefit of being able to facilitate cultivation of CoPs. The paper also contributes theoretically by extending the conceptualization of 'cultivating CoPs' beyond organizational contexts.</p>		CE1	<p>Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.</p>

159	Delegation of access in an information accountability framework for eHealth	Shared eHealth records systems offer promising benefits for improving healthcare through high availability of information and improved decision making; however, their uptake has been hindered by concerns over the privacy of patient information. To address these privacy concerns while balancing the requirements of healthcare professionals to have access to the information they need to provide appropriate care, the use of an Information Accountability Framework (IAF) has been proposed. For the IAF and so called Accountable-eHealth systems to become a reality, the framework must provide for a diverse range of users and use cases. The initial IAF model did not provide for more diverse use cases including the need for certain users to delegate access to another user in the system to act on their behalf while maintaining accountability. In this paper, we define the requirements for delegation of access in the IAF, how such access policies would be represented in the Framework, and implement and validate an expanded IAF model.	CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
160	Cardiac ultrasonography over 4G wireless networks using a tele-operated robot	This Letter proposes an end-to-end mobile tele-echography platform using a portable robot for remote cardiac ultrasonography. Performance evaluation investigates the capacity of long-term evolution (LTE) wireless networks to facilitate responsive robot tele-manipulation and realtime ultrasound video streaming that qualifies for clinical practice. Within this context, a thorough video coding standards comparison for cardiac ultrasound applications is performed, using a data set of ten ultrasound videos. Both objective and subjective (clinical) video quality assessment demonstrate that H.264/AVC and high efficiency video coding standards can achieve diagnostically-lossless video quality at bitrates well within the LTE supported data rates. Most importantly, reduced latencies experienced throughout the live teleechography sessions allow the medical expert to remotely operate the robot in a responsive manner, using the wirelessly communicated cardiac ultrasound video to reach a diagnosis. Based on preliminary results documented in this Letter, the proposed robotised tele-echography platform can provide for reliable, remote diagnosis, achieving comparable quality of experience levels with in-hospital ultrasound examinations.	CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
161	Dynamically evolving clinical practices and implications for predicting medical decisions	Automatically data-mining clinical practice patterns from electronic health records (EHR) can enable prediction of future practices as a form of clinical decision support (CDS). Our objective is to determine the stability of learned clinical practice patterns over time and what implication this has when using varying longitudinal historical data sources towards predicting future decisions. We trained an association rule engine for clinical orders (e.g., labs, imaging, medications) using structured inpatient data from a tertiary academic hospital. Comparing top order associations per admission diagnosis from training data in 2009 vs. 2012, we find practice variability from unstable diagnoses with rank biased overlap (RBO)<0.35 (e.g., pneumonia) to stable admissions for planned procedures (e.g., chemotherapy, surgery) with comparatively high RBO>0.6. Predicting admission orders for future (2013) patients with associations trained on recent (2012) vs. older (2009) data improved accuracy evaluated by area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (ROC-AUC) 0.89 to 0.92, precision at ten (positive predictive value of the top ten predictions against actual orders) 30% to 37%, and weighted recall (sensitivity) at ten 2.4% to 13%, (P<10 ⁻¹⁰). Training with more longitudinal data (2009-2012) was no better than only using recent (2012) data. Secular trends in practice patterns likely explain why smaller but more recent training data is more accurate at predicting future practices.	CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
162	Measuring validity and reliability of perception of online collaborative learning questionnaire using rasch model	This study aims to generate empirical evidence on the validity and reliability of Perception of Online Collaborative Learning Questionnaire (POCLQ) using Rasch model. The questionnaire was distributed to 32 (N=32) Diploma Hotel Catering students from Politeknik Ibrahim Sultan, Johor (PIS). Data obtained was analysed using WINSTEP version 3.68 software. The finding showed that POCLQ had high reliability with five categories of difficulties items. So, it can be concluded that POCLQ is reliable and strongly accepted. Meanwhile, analysis of items fit showed there were six items that are not in the specified range and based on standardised residual correlation measurement value; there were five items found to be overlapped that should be dropped. All the items that needed to be dropped based on the analysis of result had been refined and retained for the purpose of the study and based on expert's view. Therefore, all items remained after Rasch analysis. It is	CE1	Não é da área da saúde.

		<p>hoped that this study will give emphasis to other researchers about the importance of analysing items to ensure the quality of an instrument being developed.</p>			
163	<p>Integrating genomic resources with electronic health records using the HL7 infobutton standard</p>	<p>Background: The Clinical Genome Resource (ClinGen) Electronic Health Record (EHR) Workgroup aims to integrate ClinGen resources with EHRs. A promising option to enable this integration is through the Health Level Seven (HL7) Infobutton Standard. EHR systems that are certified according to the US Meaningful Use program provide HL7-compliant infobutton capabilities, which can be leveraged to support clinical decision-making in genomics. Objectives: To integrate genomic knowledge resources using the HL7 infobutton standard. Two tactics to achieve this objective were: (1) creating an HL7-compliant search interface for ClinGen, and (2) proposing guidance for genomic resources on achieving HL7 Infobutton standard accessibility and compliance. Methods: We built a search interface utilizing OpenInfobutton, an open source reference implementation of the HL7 Infobutton standard. ClinGen resources were assessed for readiness towards HL7 compliance. Finally, based upon our experiences we provide recommendations for publishers seeking to achieve HL7 compliance. Results: Eight genomic resources and two sub-resources were integrated with the ClinGen search engine via OpenInfobutton and the HL7 infobutton standard. Resources we assessed have varying levels of readiness towards HL7-compliance. Furthermore, we found that adoption of standard terminologies used by EHR systems is the main gap to achieve compliance. Conclusion: Genomic resources can be integrated with EHR systems via the HL7 Infobutton standard using OpenInfobutton. Full compliance of genomic resources with the Infobutton standard would further enhance interoperability with EHR systems.</p>	CII		
164	<p>Digital signatures workflows in alfresco</p>	<p>There are some obstacles, towards a paperless office. One of them is the collection of signatures, since nearly half of all documents are printed for the sole purpose of collecting them. Digital signatures can have the same legal evidential validity as handwritten signatures, provided they are based on certificates issued by accredited certification authorities and the associated private keys are stored on tamper proof token security devices like smart cards. In this article, we propose a platform for secure digital signature workflow management that integrates secure token based digital signatures with the Enterprise Content Management Alfresco, where each user can associate a set of smart cards to his account. The documents can then be signed with the citizen card or other smart card that has digital signatures capabilities. We have implemented an Alfresco module that allows us to explore several workflow techniques to implement real task secure digital signatures workflows, as people for example do when they pass a paper document between various departments to be signed. Since all users can see the current state of the documents being signed during the entire signage process, important security properties like system trust are preserved. We also describe an external validation web service, that provides a way for users to validate signed documents. The validation service then shows to the user important document security properties like timestamps, certificates attributes and highlights the document integrity in face of the digital signatures that have been collected in the workflows defined by our module in Alfresco.</p>		CE1	<p>Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.</p>
165	<p>Engaging older adults in the visualization of sensor data facilitated by an open platform for connected devices</p>	<p>BACKGROUND: The use of smart home sensor systems is growing primarily due to the appeal of unobtrusively monitoring older adult health and wellness. However, integrating large-scale sensor systems within residential settings can be challenging when deployment takes place across multiple environments, requiring customization of applications, connection across various devices and effective visualization of complex longitudinal data. OBJECTIVE: The objective of the study was to demonstrate the implementation of a smart home system using an open, extensible platform in a real-world setting and develop an application to visualize data real time. METHODS: We deployed the open source Lab of Things platform in a house of 11 residents as a demonstration of feasibility over the course of 3 months. The system consisted of Aeon Labs Z-wave Door/Window sensors and an Aeon Labs Multi-sensor that collected data on motion, temperature, luminosity, and humidity. We applied a Rapid Iterative Testing and Evaluation approach towards designing a visualization interface engaging gerontological</p>		CE6	<p>Duplicado Pubmed</p>

		experts. We then conducted a survey with 19 older adult and caregiver stakeholders to inform further design revisions. RESULTS: Our initial visualization mockups consisted of a bar chart representing activity level over time. Family members felt comfortable using the application. Older adults however, indicated it would be difficult to learn to use the application, and had trouble identifying utility. A key for older adults was ensuring that the data collected could be utilized by their family members, physicians, or caregivers. CONCLUSIONS: The approach described in this work is generalizable towards future smart home deployments and can be a valuable guide for researchers to scale a study across multiple homes and connected devices, and to create personalized interfaces for end users.			
166	Integrated data repository toolkit (IDRT): A suite of programs to facilitate health analytics on heterogeneous medical data	Background: In recent years, research data warehouses moved increasingly into the focus of interest of medical research. Nevertheless, there are only a few center-independent infrastructure solutions available. They aim to provide a consolidated view on medical data from various sources such as clinical trials, electronic health records, epidemiological registries or longitudinal cohorts. The i2b2 framework is a well-established solution for such repositories, but it lacks support for importing and integrating clinical data and metadata. Objectives: The goal of this project was to develop a platform for easy integration and administration of data from heterogeneous sources, to provide capabilities for linking them to medical terminologies and to allow for transforming and mapping of data streams for user-specific views. Methods: A suite of three tools has been developed: the i2b2 Wizard for simplifying administration of i2b2, the IDRT Import and Mapping Tool for loading clinical data from various formats like CSV, SQL, CDISC ODM or biobanks and the IDRT i2b2 Web Client Plugin for advanced export options. The Import and Mapping Tool also includes an ontology editor for rearranging and mapping patient data and structures as well as annotating clinical data with medical terminologies, primarily those used in Germany (ICD-10-GM, OPS, ICD-O, etc.). Results: With the three tools functional, new i2b2-based research projects can be created, populated and customized to researcher's needs in a few hours. Amalgamating data and metadata from different databases can be managed easily. With regards to data privacy a pseudonymization service can be plugged in. Using common ontologies and reference terminologies rather than project specific ones leads to a consistent understanding of the data semantics. Conclusions: i2b2's promise is to enable clinical researchers to devise and test new hypothesis even without a deep knowledge in statistical programming. The approach pre-sented here has been tested in a number of scenarios with millions of observations and tens of thousands of patients. Initially mostly observant, trained researchers were able to construct new analyses on their own. Early feedback indicates that timely and extensive access to their "own" data is appreciated most, but it is also lowering the barrier for other tasks, for instance checking data quality and completeness (missing data, wrong coding).		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
167	Is mHealth disrupting the status quo? Evidence from implementations highlighting network Vs. hierarchical institutional logics	Health Management Information Systems (HMIS) in developing countries have yet to live up to expectations because of the significant proportion of implementation failures. Mobile health (mHealth) technologies are being adopted increasingly in Ministries of Health (MoHs) to address aspects of HMIS implementation failure, such as the timeliness and ease of data collection from the lowest levels of healthcare. However, networked technologies such as mobile technologies used in mHealth data collection can introduce a network logic into the organization. This network logic, which often favors open, non-hierarchical modes of communication, must work with the traditional hierarchical bureaucratic logic of the HMIS and the MoH in which they become embedded. This paper conceptualizes the interaction between these two logics. It draws on succinct, empirical vignettes from two action-research projects involving the use of mHealth technology to improve data collection for the HMIS in Nigeria. Based on these findings and an institutional logics lens, this paper argues that the interaction between these logics potentially leads to a conflict where the logic embedded in networked technologies (such as mHealth) disrupts and challenges the existing hierarchical logic in the bureaucracy (such as in the MoH). It threatens not only to unsettle existing practices and norms in the organization, but also to restructure (flatten) the organization, due to resistance, loss, or changes in some pre-existing roles. Practitioners and		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.

		implementation researchers need to be sensitive to potential hierarchical and network-centric forces that are involved in implementing mHealth in traditional hierarchical settings, particularly with regards to the unintended side effects that may arise in the process.			
168	Adaptive emergency scenery video communications using HEVC for responsive decision support in disaster incidents	This study proposes a unifying framework for m-Health video communication systems that provides for the joint optimization of video quality, bitrate demands, and encoding time. The framework is video modality and infrastructure independent and facilitates adaptation to the best available encoding mode that satisfies underlying technology and application imposed constraints. The scalability of the proposed algorithm is demonstrated using different HEVC encoding configurations and realistic modelling of 802.11x wireless infrastructure for emergency scenery and response videos. Extensive experimentation shows that a jointly optimal solution in the encoding time, bitrate, and video quality space is feasible.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
169	Analysis of the acceptance process of district health information systems (DHIS) for vertical health programmes: A case study of TB, HIV/AIDS and malaria programmes in Tanzania	District Health Information System (DHIS) is used in many parts of the world to report aggregated data at the district level. Tanzania is one of the countries where the ministry of health endorsed DHIS for such use. Although the system has been rolled out recently throughout the country, Vertical Health Programmes (VHPs) are on their way to fully adopting the system. The objective of this study was to analyse the acceptance process of DHIS by three VHPs so as to examine the facilitating conditions and the challenges that they face. Data was collected through interviews, document review and observation. Analysis of the data showed the facilitating conditions to be having a consensus on which VHP indicators to include in the DHIS, existence of infrastructure including the routine Health Information System (HIS), and support from development partners. Challenges of acceptance process of DHIS include inadequate human resource for HIS, data quality and information flow issues, and existence of separate monitoring and evaluation systems for the VHPs. The study recommends integration or interoperation of DHIS with VHP systems, creating a pool of resources for HIS, training and motivating human resource for HIS.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
170	Inter-organizational knowledge sharing system in the health sector: Physicians' perspective	This study aimed to investigate the physicians' attitude toward inter-organizational knowledge sharing system (IOKSS) deployment in the health sector in Oman. IOKSS in the health sector can be very crucial and results in several operational, strategic, social and economic benefits for healthcare providers and physicians. Previous research on inter-organizational systems (IOS) has focused on organizational adoption, particularly on vertically-linked organizations. Identifying major issues that are critical to physicians, the end users and key stakeholders, is crucial for IOKSS deployment. Based on data collected from physicians in Oman, results indicated that peers, the sector and knowledge workers, are critical factors to physicians' attitudes toward IOKSS. The study also indicated that physicians' attitudes were positively associated with their intention to share implicit, explicit, exploratory and exploitive knowledge. These results are valuable for organizational designing, planning and decision-making regarding their adoption of IOKSS in the health sector.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
171	An adaptive case management system to support integrated care services: Lessons learned from the NEXES project	Background: Extensive deployment and sustainability of integrated care services (ICS) constitute an unmet need to reduce the burden of chronic conditions. The European Union project NEXES (2008-2013) assessed the deployment of four ICS encompassing the spectrum of severity of chronic patients. Objective: The current study aims to (i) describe the open source Adaptive Case Management (ACM) system (Linkcare®) developed to support the deployment of ICS at the level of healthcare district; (ii) to evaluate its performance; and, (iii) to identify key challenges for regional deployment of ICS. Methods: We first defined a conceptual model for ICS management and execution composed of five main stages. We then specified an associated logical model considering the dynamic runtime of ACM. Finally, we implemented the four ICS as a physical model with an ICS editor to allow professionals (case managers) to play active roles in adapting the system to their needs. Instances of ICS were then run in Linkcare®. Four ICS provided a framework for evaluating the system: Wellness and Rehabilitation (W&R) (number		CII	

		of patients enrolled in the study (n. =. 173); Enhanced Care (EC) in frail chronic patients to prevent hospital admissions, (n=. 848); Home Hospitalization and Early Discharge (HH/ED) (n=. 2314); and, Support to remote diagnosis (Support) (n=. 7793). The method for assessment of telemedicine applications (MAST) was used for iterative evaluation. Results: Linkcare® supports ACM with shared-care plans across healthcare tiers and offers integration with provider-specific electronic health records. Linkcare® successfully contributed to the deployment of the four ICS: W&R facilitated long-term sustainability of training effects (p<. 0.01) and active life style (p<. 0.03); EC showed significant positive outcomes (p<. 0.05); HH/ED reduced on average 5 in-hospital days per patient with a 30-d re-admission rate of 10%; and, Support, enhanced community-based quality forced spirometry testing (p<. 0.01). Key challenges for regional deployment of personalized care were identified. Conclusions: Linkcare® provided the required functionalities to support integrated care adopting an ACM model, and it showed adaptive potential for its implementation in different health scenarios. The research generated strategies that contributed to face the challenges of the transition toward personalized medicine for chronic patients.			
172	LuciPHOr2: Site localization of generic post-translational modifications from tandem mass spectrometry data	We present LuciPHOr2, a site localization tool for generic post-translational modifications (PTMs) using tandem mass spectrometry data. As an extension of the original LuciPHOr (version 1) for phosphorylation site localization, the new software provides a site-level localization score for generic PTMs and associated false discovery rate called the false localization rate. We describe several novel features such as operating system independence and reduced computation time through multiple threading. We also discuss optimal parameters for different types of data and illustrate the new tool on a human skeletal muscle dataset for lysine-acetylation.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
173	Device Nimbus: An Intelligent Middleware for Smarter Services for Health and Fitness	The world is experiencing an unprecedented explosion in the number of smart devices and mobile apps that are available to users. In the health and fitness domains, many of the devices and technologies in the market place are restricted to proprietary platforms, typically working in isolation with fixed hardware settings. Consequently, an important challenge is to investigate techniques for combining and analyzing data encapsulated by these ubiquitous technologies. In this paper, we introduce an intelligent middleware - Device Nimbus - to meet this challenge. The middleware supports the integration of distributed and heterogeneous mobile sensor data, enabling both context and predictive analysis. We describe a minimum viable product of Device Nimbus and report the results of preliminary tests spanning multiple data sources focused on fitness apps, illustrating the efficacy of the middleware.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
174	Information model for radiology performance indicators based on DICOM	The paper presents the information model of the DICOM - Radiology Performance Indicator (DICOM-RPI). This model can be used to aggregate information related to the characterization of medical imaging health care services, namely information incorporated in the studies according to the format of the Digital Imaging and Communication in Medicine (DICOM). The model comprises several components including the ones required to define the context of medical imaging health care services (e.g. the entities involved) and the context of use of the indicator (e.g. Quality Dimensions). For the validation of the proposed information model 51,277 Digital Radiography (DX) studies performed on 27,559 patients from a single health care facility were considered. The results of this validation within the scope of DX modality make possible to anticipate the DICOM-RPI relevance in other imaging modalities and its contribution for comprehensive analysis of medical imaging health care services.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
175	Ontological modeling of electronic health information exchange	Introduction: Investments of resources to purposively improve the movement of information between health system providers are currently made with imperfect information. No inventories of system-level electronic health information flows currently exist, nor do measures of inter-organizational electronic information exchange. Methods: Using Protégé 4, an open-source OWL Web ontology language editor and knowledge-based framework, we formalized a model that decomposes inter-organizational electronic health information flow into derivative		CI1	

		<p>concepts such as diversity, breadth, volume, structure, standardization and connectivity. Results: The ontology was populated with data from a regional health system and the flows were measured. Individual instance's properties were inferred from their class associations as determined by their data and object property rules. It was also possible to visualize interoperability activity for regional analysis and planning purposes. A property called Impact was created from the total number of patients or clients that a health entity in the region served in a year, and the total number of health service providers or organizations with whom it exchanged information in support of clinical decision-making, diagnosis or treatment. Identifying providers with a high Impact but low Interoperability score could assist planners and policy-makers to optimize technology investments intended to electronically share patient information across the continuum of care. Finally, we demonstrated how linked ontologies were used to identify logical inconsistencies in self-reported data for the study.</p>			
176	<p>KenVACS: Improving vaccination of children through cellular network technology in developing countries</p>	<p>Health Data collection is one of the major components of public health systems. Decision makers, policy makers, and medical service providers need accurate and timely data in order to improve the quality of health services. The rapid growth and use of mobile technologies has exerted pressure on the demand for mobile-based data collection solutions to bridge the information gaps in the health sector. We propose a prototype using open source data collection frameworks to test its feasibility in improving the vaccination data collection in Kenya. KenVACS, the proposed prototype, offers ways of collecting vaccination data through mobile phones and visualizes the collected data in a web application; the system also sends reminder short messages service (SMS) to remind parents on the date of the next vaccination. Early evaluation demonstrates the benefits of such a system in supporting and improving vaccination of children. Finally, we conducted a qualitative study to assess challenges in remote health data collection and evaluated usability and functionality of KenVACS.</p>	CII		
177	<p>Role of OpenEHR as an open source solution for the regional modelling of patient data in obstetrics</p>	<p>This work investigates, whether openEHR with its reference model, archetypes and templates is suitable for the digital representation of demographic as well as clinical data. Moreover, it elaborates openEHR as a tool for modelling Hospital Information Systems on a regional level based on a national logical infrastructure. OpenEHR is a dual model approach developed for the modelling of Hospital Information Systems enabling semantic interoperability. A holistic solution to this represents the use of dual model based Electronic Healthcare Record systems. Modelling data in the field of obstetrics is a challenge, since different regions demand locally specific information for the process of treatment. Smaller health units in developing countries like Brazil or Malaysia, which until recently handled automatable processes like the storage of sensitive patient data in paper form, start organizational reconstruction processes. This archetype proof-of-concept investigation has tried out some elements of the openEHR methodology in cooperation with a health unit in Colombo, Brazil. Two legal forms provided by the Brazilian Ministry of Health have been analyzed and classified into demographic and clinical data. LinKEHR-Ed editor was used to read, edit and create archetypes. Results show that 33 clinical and demographic concepts, which are necessary to cover data demanded by the Unified National Health System, were identified. Out of the concepts 61% were reused and 39% modified to cover domain requirements. The detailed process of reuse, modification and creation of archetypes is shown. We conclude that, although a major part of demographic and clinical patient data were already represented by existing archetypes, a significant part required major modifications. In this study openEHR proved to be a highly suitable tool in the modelling of complex health data. In combination with LinKEHR-Ed software it offers user-friendly and highly applicable tools, although the complexity built by the vast specifications requires expert networks to define generally expected clinical models. Finally, this project has pointed out main benefits enclosing high coverage of obstetrics data on the Clinical Knowledge Manager, simple modelling, and wide network and support using openEHR. Moreover, barriers described are enclosing the allocation of clinical content to respective archetypes, as well as stagnant adaption of changes on the Clinical Knowledge Manager leading to redundant efforts in data contribution that need to be addressed in future works.</p>		CE6	Duplicate Pubmed

178	Strategic information system planning in healthcare organizations	The healthcare industry is a critical and growing part of economies worldwide. To provide better quality of care, and value for money, billions of dollars are being spent on bettering information systems in healthcare organizations. Strategic Information System Planning (SISP) is instrumental in making informed decisions to achieve the health organizations' goals and objectives. This paper undertakes a systematic review to gain insight into existing studies on SISP in healthcare organizations. Our systematic review of papers on SISP from 1985 to 2011 examines the background and trend of research into SISP in the healthcare industry, classification of topics in SISP, as well as sets of tools and guidelines to aid practitioners and the research community alike.	CE5	Revisão sistemática da literatura
179	Core interoperability ontology for research using primary care data	Introduction: This article is part of the Focus Theme of Methods of Information in Medicine on “Managing Interoperability and Complexity in Health Systems”. Background: Primary care data is the single richest source of routine health care data. However its use, both in research and clinical work, often requires data from multiple clinical sites, clinical trials databases and registries. Data integration and interoperability are therefore of utmost importance. Objectives: TRANSFoRm’s general approach relies on a unified interoperability framework described in a previous paper. We developed a core ontology for an interoperability framework based on data mediation. This article presents how such an ontology, the Clinical Data Integration Model (CDIM), can be designed to support, in conjunction with appropriate terminologies, biomedical data federation within TRANSFoRm, an EU FP7 project that aims to develop the digital infrastructure for a learning healthcare system in European Primary Care. Methods: TRANSFoRm utilizes a unified structural/terminological interoperability frame work, based on the local-as-view media - tion paradigm. Such an approach mandates the global information model to describe the domain of interest independently of the data sources to be explored. Following a requirement analysis process, no ontology focusing on primary care research was identified and, thus we designed a realist ontology based on Basic Formal Ontology to support our framework in collaboration with various terminologies used in primary care. Results: The resulting ontology has 549 classes and 82 object properties and is used to support data integration for TRANSFoRm’s use cases. Concepts identified by researchers were successfully expressed in queries using CDIM and pertinent terminologies. As an example, we illustrate how, in TRANSFoRm, the Query Formulation Workbench can cap - ture eligibility criteria in a computable rep - resentation, which is based on CDIM. Conclusion: A unified mediation approach to semantic interoperability provides a flexible and extensible framework for all types of interaction between health record systems and research systems. CDIM, as core ontology of such an approach, enables simplicity and consistency of design across the heterogeneous software landscape and can support the specific needs of EHR-driven phenotyping research using primary care data.	CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
180	Automatically Recognizing Medication and Adverse Event Information from Food and Drug Administration's Adverse Event Reporting System Narratives	Background: The Food and Drug Administration's (FDA) Adverse Event Reporting System (FAERS) is a repository of spontaneously-reported adverse drug events (ADEs) for FDA-approved prescription drugs. FAERS reports include both structured reports and unstructured narratives. The narratives often include essential information for evaluation of the severity, causality, and description of ADEs that are not present in the structured data. The timely identification of unknown toxicities of prescription drugs is an important, unsolved problem. Objective: The objective of this study was to develop an annotated corpus of FAERS narratives and biomedical named entity tagger to automatically identify ADE related information in the FAERS narratives. Methods: We developed an annotation guideline and annotate medication information and adverse event related entities on 122 FAERS narratives comprising approximately 23,000 word tokens. A named entity tagger using supervised machine learning approaches was built for detecting medication information and adverse event entities using various categories of features. Results: The annotated corpus had an agreement of over .9 Cohen's kappa for medication and adverse event entities. The best performing tagger achieves an overall performance of 0.73 F1 score for detection of medication, adverse event and other named entities. Conclusions: In this study, we developed an annotated corpus of FAERS narratives and machine learning based models for automatically	CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.

		extracting medication and adverse event information from the FAERS narratives. Our study is an important step towards enriching the FAERS data for postmarketing pharmacovigilance.			
181	Modern framework for distributed healthcare data analytics based on hadoop	Evolution in the field of IT, electronics and networking resulted in enhancements in connectivity and in computation capabilities. Proliferation of miniaturized devices paved way for Body Area Network. Healthcare systems have been going through cycles of modernization as the advent of IT system in the field of medical sciences. Body Area Network is a network of lightweight wearable sensor nodes that sense human body functions. Modern healthcare informatics systems produce lots of data that emerge from sensors. Even though many healthcare informatics systems exist and produce volume of data, such solutions exist in silos. Existing Healthcare IT systems intend to gather multivariate medical data about the patients by the means of electronic format. They capture multi variant types of data, process and store them in a RDBMS. Inferring knowledge from such systems is tedious. This paper aims at proposing a framework for modernizing the healthcare informatics systems. Proposed framework is based on Apache Hadoop platform which is open source and its implementation is distributed in nature as it is deployable at various healthcare centers in different geographic locations.	CII		
182	Community-based early warning and adaptive response system (EWARS) for mosquito borne diseases: An open source/open community approach	A variety of studies around the world have evaluated the use of remote sensing with and without GIS in communicable diseases. The ongoing Ebola epidemic has highlighted the risks that can arise for the global community from rapidly spreading diseases which may outpace attempts at control and eradication. This paper presents an approach to the development, deployment, validation and wide-spread adoption of a GIS-based temporo-spatial decision support system which is being collaboratively developed in open source/open community mode by an international group that came together under UN auspices. The group believes in an open source/open community approach to make the fruits of knowledge as widely accessible as possible. A core initiative of the groups is the EWARS project. It proposes to strengthen existing public health systems by the development and validation a model for a community based surveillance and response system which will initially address mosquito borne diseases in the developing world. At present mathematical modeling to support EWARS is at an advanced state, and it planned to embark on a pilot project.	CII		
183	Analysis and design of software ecosystem architectures: Towards the 4S telemedicine ecosystem	Context Telemedicine, the provision of health care at a distance, is arguably an effective way of increasing access to, reducing cost of, and improving quality of care. However, the deployment of telemedicine is faced with standards that are hard to use, application-specific data models, and application stove-pipes that inhibit the adoption of telemedical solutions. To which extent can a software ecosystem approach to telemedicine alleviate this? Objective In this article, we define the concept of software ecosystem architecture as the structure(s) of a software ecosystem comprising elements, relations among them, and properties of both. Our objective is to show how this concept can be used (i) in the analysis of existing software ecosystems and (ii) in the design of new software ecosystems. Method We performed a mixed-method study that consisted of a case study and an experiment. For (i), we performed a descriptive, revelatory case study of the Danish telemedicine ecosystem and for (ii), we experimentally designed, implemented, and evaluated the architecture of 4S. Results We contribute in three areas. First, we define the software ecosystem architecture concept that captures organization, business, and software aspects of software ecosystems. Secondly, we apply this concept in our case study and demonstrate that it is a viable concept for software ecosystem analysis. Finally, based on our experiments, we discuss the practice of software engineering for software ecosystems drawn from experience in creating and evolving the 4S telemedicine ecosystem. Conclusion The concept of software ecosystem architecture can be used analytically and constructively in respectively the analysis and design of software ecosystems.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
184	The impact of business intelligence on	The challenges of how to manage healthcare and achieve clinical integration in today's payment setting has become a national concern. The use of technology to help ensure healthcare quality and control cost is an ongoing research subject. Business intelligence solutions are used in many industries to garner insight from financial and operational data to make more informed decisions towards the		CE5	Revisão da literatura.

	healthcare delivery in the USA	ultimate goal of achieving efficiency and effectiveness. This paper aims to bring the reader up-to-date with the current literature on two basic topics; business intelligence and healthcare delivery and form the basis for the justification of research on the impact of business intelligence on healthcare delivery in the U.S.A. To achieve that goal we examine BI deployment in the healthcare industry, address relevant issues and challenges, and explore the role of BI to foster certain organizational capabilities. Examples of how BI capabilities have supported organizational capabilities impacting the problems of accessibility, cost, and quality of healthcare are presented. Scholars and professionals, alike, could benefit from this study where BI is presented as a mechanism to ensure a robust and systematic approach to health-care management with an ultimate goal of enduring impact on quality improvement and cost control.			
185	A rigorous algorithm to detect and clean inaccurate adult height records within EHR systems	Background: Height is a critical variable for many biomedical analyses because it is an important component of Body Mass Index (BMI). Transforming EHR height measures into meaningful research-ready values is challenging and there is limited information available on methods for "cleaning" these data. Objectives: We sought to develop an algorithm to clean adult height data extracted from EHR using only height values and associated ages. Results: The algorithm we developed is sensitive to normal decreases in adult height associated with aging, is implemented using an open-source software tool and is thus easily modifiable, and is freely available. We checked the performance of our algorithm using data from the Northwestern biobank and a replication sample from the Marshfield Clinic biobank obtained through our participation in the eMERGE consortium. The algorithm identified 1262 erroneous values from a total of 33937 records in the Northwestern sample. Replacing erroneous height values with those identified as correct by the algorithm resulted in meaningful changes in height and BMI records; median change in recorded height after cleaning was 7.6 cm and median change in BMI was 2.9 kg/m2. Comparison of cleaned EHR height values to observer measured values showed that 94.5% (95% C.I 93.8-% - 95.2%) of cleaned values were within 3.5 cm of observer measured values. Conclusions: Our freely available height algorithm cleans EHR height data with only height and age inputs. Use of this algorithm will benefit groups trying to perform research with height and BMI data extracted from EHR.		CE6	Duplicado Pubmed
186	Critical success factors for the implementation of integrated healthcare information systems projects: An organizational fit perspective	Many healthcare reforms are to digitalize and integrate healthcare information systems. However, the disparity of business benefits in having an integrated healthcare information system (IHIS) varies with organizational fit factors. Critical success factors (CSFs) exist for hospitals to implement an IHIS successfully. This study investigated the relationship between the organizational fit and the system success. In addition, we examined the moderating effect of five CSFs -- information systems adjustment, business process adjustment, organizational resistance, top management support, and the capability of key team members - in an IHIS implementation. Fifty-three hospitals that have successfully undertaken IHIS projects participated in this study. We used regression analysis to assess the relationships. The findings of this study provide a roadmap for hospitals to capitalize on the organizational fit and the five critical success factors in order to implement successful IHIS projects.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
187	Building a drug ontology based on RxNorm and other sources	Background: We built the Drug Ontology (DrOn) because we required correct and consistent drug information in a format for use in semantic web applications, and no existing resource met this requirement or could be altered to meet it. One of the obstacles we faced when creating DrOn was the difficulty in reusing drug information from existing sources. The primary external source we have used at this stage in DrOn's development is RxNorm, a standard drug terminology curated by the National Library of Medicine (NLM). To build DrOn, we (1) mined data from historical releases of RxNorm and (2) mapped many RxNorm entities to Chemical Entities of Biological Interest (ChEBI) classes, pulling relevant information from ChEBI while doing so. Results: We built DrOn in a modular fashion to facilitate simpler extension and development of the ontology and to allow reasoning and construction to scale. Classes derived from each source are serialized in separate modules. For example, the classes in DrOn that are programmatically derived from RxNorm are stored in a separate module and		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código aberto.

		subsumed by classes in a manually-curated, realist, upper-level module of DrOn with terms such as 'clinical drug role', 'tablet', 'capsule', etc. Conclusions: DrOn is a modular, extensible ontology of drug products, their ingredients, and their biological activity that avoids many of the fundamental flaws found in other, similar artifacts and meets the requirements of our comparative-effectiveness research use-case.			
188	An innovative portal for rare genetic diseases research: The semantics Diseasecard	Advances in "omics" hardware and software technologies are bringing rare diseases research back from the sidelines. Whereas in the past these disorders were seldom considered relevant, in the era of whole genome sequencing the direct connections between rare phenotypes and a reduced set of genes are of vital relevance. This increased interest in rare genetic diseases research is pushing forward investment and effort towards the creation of software in the field, and leveraging the wealth of available life sciences data. Alas, most of these tools target one or more rare diseases, are focused solely on a single type of user, or are limited to the most relevant scientific breakthroughs for a specific niche. Furthermore, despite some high quality efforts, the ever-growing number of resources, databases, services and applications is still a burden to this area. Hence, there is a clear interest in new strategies to deliver a holistic perspective over the entire rare genetic diseases research domain. This is Diseasecard's reasoning, to build a true lightweight knowledge base covering rare genetic diseases. Developed with the latest semantic web technologies, this portal delivers unified access to a comprehensive network for researchers, clinicians, patients and bioinformatics developers. With in-context access covering over 20 distinct heterogeneous resources, Diseasecard's workspace provides access to the most relevant scientific knowledge regarding a given disorder, whether through direct common identifiers or through full-text search over all connected resources. In addition to its user-oriented features, Diseasecard's semantic knowledge base is also available for direct querying, enabling everyone to include rare genetic diseases knowledge in new or existing information systems. Diseasecard is publicly available at http://bioinformatics.ua.pt/diseasecard/ .		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
189	New ELIN systems using CMOS transistors in weak inversion operation	Abstract-In this paper new ELIN systems implemented by using CMOS transistors in weak inversion operation are presented. The proposed systems exploit the exponential-law characteristics of the subthreshold CMOS transistors. New operational transconductance amplifiers in CMOS technology, providing elementary "tanh" and "sinh/cosh" functions with high accuracy are proposed. These elementary cells are used to design first order CMOS ELIN filters. For a bias current of 1μA, the dynamic range of the predistorted input voltage is 220mVpp and the current consumption is about 20μA from a 3.3V supply voltage. The simulations performed in 0.18μm CMOS technology confirm the theoretically obtained results.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
190	Open source Patient-Controlled Analgesic pump requirements documentation	The dynamic nature of the medical domain is driving a need for continuous innovation and improvement in techniques for developing and assuring medical devices. Unfortunately, research in academia and communication between academics, industrial engineers, and regulatory authorities is hampered by the lack of realistic non-proprietary development artifacts for medical devices. In this paper, we give an overview of a detailed requirements document for a Patient-Controlled Analgesic (PCA) pump developed under the US NSF's Food and Drug Administration (FDA) Scholar-in-Residence (SIR) program. This 60+ page document follows the methodology outlined in the US Federal Aviation Administrations (FAA) Requirements Engineering Management Handbook (REMH) and includes a domain overview, use cases, statements of safety & security requirements, and formal top-level system architectural description. Based on previous experience with release of a requirements document for a cardiac pacemaker that spawned a number of research and pedagogical activities, we believe that the described PCA requirements document can be an important research enabler within the formal methods and software engineering communities.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
191	Big data analytics for developing countries using	The multi-layered view of digital divide suggests there is inequality of access to ICT, inequality of capability to exploit ICT and inequality of outcomes after exploiting ICT. This is evidently clear in the health systems of developing countries. In this paper, we look at cloud computing being able to provide computing as a utility service that might bridge this digital divide for Health		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.

	the cloud for operational bi in health	Information Systems in developing countries. We highlight the role of Operational Business Intelligence (BI) tools to be able to make better decisions in health service provisioning. Through the case of DHIS2 software and its Analytics-as-a-Service (AaaS) model, we look at how tools can exploit Cloud computing capabilities to perform analytics on Big Data that is resulting from integration of health data from multiple sources. Beyond looking at purely warehousing techniques, we suggest understanding Big Data from Organizational Capabilities and expanding organizational capabilities by offloading computing as a utility to vendors through cloud computing.			
192	Composition and combination-based object trust evaluation for knowledge management in virtual organizations	Purpose: This paper aims to develop a framework for object trust evaluation and related object trust principles to facilitate knowledge management in a virtual organization. It proposes systematic methods to quantify the trust of an object and defines the concept of object trust management. The study aims to expand the domain of subject trust to object trust evaluation in terms of whether an object is correct and accurate in expressing a topic or issue and whether the object is secure and safe to execute (in the case of an executable program). By providing theoretical and empirical insights about object trust composition and combination, this research facilitates better knowledge identification, creation, evaluation, and distribution. Design/methodology/approach: This paper presents two object trust principles - trust composition and trust combination. These principles provide formal methodologies and guidelines to assess whether an object has the required level of quality and security features (hence it is trustworthy). The paper uses a component-based approach to evaluate the quality and security of an object. Formal approaches and algorithms have been developed to assess the trustworthiness of an object in different cases. Findings: The paper provides qualitative and quantitative analysis about how object trust can be composed and combined. Novel mechanisms have been developed to help users evaluate the quality and security features of available objects. Originality/value: This effort fulfills an identified need to address the challenging issue of evaluating the trustworthiness of an object (e.g. a software program, a file, or other type of knowledge element) in a loosely-coupled system such as a virtual organization. It is the first of its kind to formally define object trust management and study object trust evaluation.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
193	Advanced medical imaging protocol workflow - A flexible electronic solution to optimize process efficiency, care quality and patient safety in the national VA enterprise	Radiologists routinely make decisions with only limited information when assigning protocol instructions for the performance of advanced medical imaging examinations. Opportunity exists to simultaneously improve the safety, quality and efficiency of this workflow through the application of an electronic solution leveraging health system resources to provide concise, tailored information and decision support in real-time. Such a system has been developed using an open source, open standards design for use within the Veterans Health Administration. The Radiology Protocol Tool Recorder (RAPTOR) project identified key process attributes as well as inherent weaknesses of paper processes and electronic emulators of paper processes to guide the development of its optimized electronic solution. The design provides a kernel that can be expanded to create an integrated radiology environment. RAPTOR has implications relevant to the greater health care community, and serves as a case model for modernization of legacy government health information systems.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
194	The Analytic Information Warehouse (AIW): A platform for analytics using electronic health record data	Objective: To create an analytics platform for specifying and detecting clinical phenotypes and other derived variables in electronic health record (EHR) data for quality improvement investigations. Materials and methods: We have developed an architecture for an Analytic Information Warehouse (AIW). It supports transforming data represented in different physical schemas into a common data model, specifying derived variables in terms of the common model to enable their reuse, computing derived variables while enforcing invariants and ensuring correctness and consistency of data transformations, long-term curation of derived data, and export of derived data into standard analysis tools. It includes software that implements these features and a computing environment that enables secure high-performance access to and processing of large datasets extracted from EHRs. Results: We have implemented and deployed the architecture in production locally. The software is available as open source. We have used it as part of hospital operations in a project to reduce rates of hospital readmission within 30. days. The		CII	

		project examined the association of over 100 derived variables representing disease and co-morbidity phenotypes with readmissions in 5. years of data from our institution's clinical data warehouse and the UHC Clinical Database (CDB). The CDB contains administrative data from over 200 hospitals that are in academic medical centers or affiliated with such centers. Discussion and conclusion: A widely available platform for managing and detecting phenotypes in EHR data could accelerate the use of such data in quality improvement and comparative effectiveness studies.			
195	Integrated system based on wireless sensors network for cardiac arrhythmia monitoring	This paper describes the research carried out for designing and producing an integrated system for monitoring patients suffering from cardiac arrhythmias. Our system is based on a wireless sensors network (WSN) and can be used in hospital or at home. It is able to measure and transmit the patient's heart rate (HR) by radio to a central telemonitoring station. The HR is continuously computed from the electrocardiographic signals using custom developed devices. These devices are attached to the patient and are based on low power microcontrollers and wireless transceivers. The data is uploaded through WSN on the central telemonitoring station. The software running on the telemonitoring station receives the HRs from monitored patients through WSN, displays them as temporal waveforms and activates the alerts when HR arrhythmia is detected. An experimental system for cardiac arrhythmia has been designed, implemented and tested.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
196	Designing sustainable open source systems: The cuban national health care network and portal (INFOMED)	Integrating research, education and evidence-based medical practice requires complex network linkages among these critical activities. This study examines the Cuban National Health Care Network and Portal (INFOMED) in the context of the regional Virtual Health Library of the Latin American and Caribbean Health Sciences System (BIREME) led by Brazil. INFOMED is a virtual infrastructure for integration of scientific research with education and expert intervention in evidence-based medicine. Virtual infrastructures refer to an environment characterized by overlapping distribution networks accessible through Internet portals and websites designed to facilitate integrated use of available resources. The objective of this paper is to examine system design at the regional and national levels of analysis using theoretical perspectives from complexity theory, institutional economics and knowledge ecology. In conclusion model transferability to other national health care systems is considered.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
197	A qualitative research approach to obtain insight in business process modelling methods in practice	In this paper we are concerned with the development of an observational research approach to gain insights into the performance of Business Process Modelling Methods (BPMs) in practice. In developing this observational approach, we have adopted an interpretive research approach. More specifically, this involved the design of a questionnaire to conduct semi-structured interviews to collect qualitative research data about the performance of BPMs. Since a BPM is a designed artefact, we also investigated Design Science Research literature to identify criteria to appreciate the performance of BPMs in practice. As a result, the questionnaire that was used to guide the interview is based on a subset of criteria of progress for information systems theories, while the observational research approach we adopted involves the collection of qualitative data from multiple stakeholder types. As a next step, the resulting questionnaire was used to evaluate the performance an actual BPM in practical use; the DEMO method. Though the analysis of the collected qualitative data of the DEMO case has not been fully performed yet, we already foresee that part of the information we collected provides new insights compared to existing studies about DEMO, as is the fact that a variety of types of stakeholders have been approached to observe the use of DEMO.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
198	Computer-based training system for cataract surgery	This paper describes a single simulation framework to perform interactive cataract surgery simulations. Contributions includes advanced bio-mechanical models and intensive use of modern graphics hardware to provide fast computation times. Surgical devices are replicated and located in a real-time thanks to infrared tracking. Combination of a high-fidelity simulation and actual surgical tools are able to improve surgeon immersion while training. Preliminary tests have been performed by experienced ophthalmologists to qualitatively assess the face-validity of the simulator and the faithfulness of the behavior of the anatomical structures as well as the interactions with the surgical tools.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.

199	The contradictory influence of social media affordances on online communal knowledge sharing	The use of social media creates the opportunity to turn organization-wide knowledge sharing in the workplace from an intermittent, centralized knowledge management process to a continuous online knowledge conversation of strangers, unexpected interpretations and re-uses, and dynamic emergence. We theorize four affordances of social media representing different ways to engage in this publicly visible knowledge conversations: metavoicing, triggered attending, network-informed associating, and generative role-taking. We further theorize mechanisms that affect how people engage in the knowledge conversation, finding that some mechanisms, when activated, will have positive effects on moving the knowledge conversation forward, but others will have adverse consequences not intended by the organization. These emergent tensions become the basis for the implications we draw.		CE1	Não é da área da saúde.
200	A software tool for large-scale sharing and querying of clinical documents modeled using HL7 version 3 standard	We present a novel software tool called CDN (Collaborative Data Network) for large-scale sharing and querying of clinical documents modeled using HL7 v3 standard (e.g., Clinical Document Architecture (CDA), Continuity of Care Document (CCD)). Similar to the caBIG initiative, CDN aims to foster innovations in cancer treatment and diagnosis through large-scale, sharing of clinical data. We focus on cancer because it is the second leading cause of deaths in the US. CDN is based on the synergistic combination of peer-to-peer technology and the extensible markup language XML and XQuery. Using CDN, a user can pose both structured queries and keyword queries on the HL7 v3 documents hosted by data providers. CDN is unique in its design - it supports location oblivious queries in a large-scale, network wherein a user does not explicitly provide the location of the data for a query. A location service in CDN discovers data of interest in the network at query time. CDN uses standard cryptographic techniques to provide security to data providers and protect the privacy of patients. Using CDN, a user can pose clinical queries pertaining to cancer containing aggregations and joins across data hosted by multiple data providers. CDN is implemented with open-source software for web application development and XML query processing. We report the evaluation of CDN in a distributed environment (LAN) using a real dataset of discharge summaries available from the i2b2 project.	CII		
201	Data integrity module for data quality assurance within an e-health system in sub-Saharan Africa	Objective: Ensuring good data quality within telemedicine and e-health systems in developing countries is resource intensive. We set out to evaluate an approach where in-built functionality within an electronic record system could identify data quality and integrity problems with little human input. Materials and Methods: We developed a robust data integrity module to identify, enumerate, and facilitate correction of errors within an e-health system that is in wide use in sub-Saharan Africa. Results: The data integrity module was successfully implemented within an electronic medical record system in Western Kenya. Queries were set to fail if one of more records did not meet defined criteria for data integrity. Only one of 14 data integrity checks implemented uncovered no errors. The other queries had errors or questionable results ranging from 51 records to 30,301 records. However, as a proportion of all patients and all observation, the identified records with likely data integrity problems only constituted a small percentage of all records (mean 0.96%, range 0-4.1%). Twelve of the 14 queries (86%) were executed in <15 s, with the longest query lasting 2 min and 18 s. Conclusion: A tool that allows for automatic data integrity and quality checks was successfully implemented within an e-health system in sub-Saharan Africa. The tool potentially reduces the burden of maintaining data quality by limiting the scale of manual reviews needed to identify electronic records with errors.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
202	Healthcare information systems to assess influenza outbreaks: An analysis of the 2009 H1N1 epidemic in	Objective: To determine whether a private HIS could have detected the influenza epidemic outbreaks earlier through changes in morbidity and mortality patterns. Methods: Data Source included a health information system (HIS) from an academic tertiary health care center integrating administrative and clinical applications. It used a local interface terminology server which provides support through data autocoding of clinical documentation. Specific data subsets were created to compare the burden of influenza during the epidemiological week (EW) 21 to 26 for years 2007 to 2009 among 150,000 Health Maintenance Organization members in Argentina. The threshold for identifying an epidemic was considered met when the weekly influenza-like illness (ILI) rate exceeded 200 per 100,000		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.

	Buenos Aires	visits. Case fatality rates and mortality rates of severe acute respiratory infection (SARI) from 2007 to 2009 were retrospectively compared. Case fatality rates and mortality rates for A/H1N1 influenza 2009 also were estimated. Results: The HIS detected the outbreak in EW 23 while the government Ministry of Health (MoH) gave a national epidemic alert during EW 25. The number of visits for ILI increased more than fourfold when comparing 2009 to the period 2007-2008. The SARI mortality rate in 2009 was higher than in 2008 (RR 2.8; 95%CI 1.18-6.63) and similar to that of 2007 (RR 1.05; 95%CI 0.56-1.49). 2009 was the first year with mortalities younger than 65 years attributable to SARI. The estimated A/H1N1 case fatality rate for SARI was 6.2% (95%CI 2.5 to 15.5) and A/H1N1 mortality rate was 6 per 100,000 (95%CI 0 to 11.6). Conclusion: Our HIS detected the outbreak two weeks before than the MoH gave a national alert. The information system was useful in assessing morbidity and mortality during the 2009 influenza epidemic H1N1 outbreak suggesting that with a private-public integration a more real-time outbreak and disease surveillance system could be implemented.			
203	Scenario-based design: A method for connecting information system design with public health operations and emergency management	Responding to public health emergencies requires rapid and accurate assessment of workforce availability under adverse and changing circumstances. However, public health information systems to support resource management during both routine and emergency operations are currently lacking. We applied scenario-based design as an approach to engage public health practitioners in the creation and validation of an information design to support routine and emergency public health activities. Methods: Using semi-structured interviews we identified the information needs and activities of senior public health managers of a large municipal health department during routine and emergency operations. Results: Interview analysis identified 25 information needs for public health operations management. The identified information needs were used in conjunction with scenario-based design to create 25 scenarios of use and a public health manager persona. Scenarios of use and persona were validated and modified based on follow-up surveys with study participants. Scenarios were used to test and gain feedback on a pilot information system. Conclusion: The method of scenario-based design was applied to represent the resource management needs of senior-level public health managers under routine and disaster settings. Scenario-based design can be a useful tool for engaging public health practitioners in the design process and to validate an information system design.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
204	The DEDUCE Guided Query tool: Providing simplified access to clinical data for research and quality improvement	In many healthcare organizations, comparative effectiveness research and quality improvement (QI) investigations are hampered by a lack of access to data created as a byproduct of patient care. Data collection often hinges upon either manual chart review or ad hoc requests to technical experts who support legacy clinical systems. In order to facilitate this needed capacity for data exploration at our institution (Duke University Health System), we have designed and deployed a robust Web application for cohort identification and data extraction-the Duke Enterprise Data Unified Content Explorer (DEDUCE). DEDUCE is envisioned as a simple, web-based environment that allows investigators access to administrative, financial, and clinical information generated during patient care. By using business intelligence tools to create a view into Duke Medicine's enterprise data warehouse, DEDUCE provides a Guided Query functionality using a wizard-like interface that lets users filter through millions of clinical records, explore aggregate reports, and, export extracts. Researchers and QI specialists can obtain detailed patient- and observation-level extracts without needing to understand structured query language or the underlying database model. Developers designing such tools must devote sufficient training and develop application safeguards to ensure that patient-centered clinical researchers understand when observation-level extracts should be used. This may mitigate the risk of data being misunderstood and consequently used in an improper fashion.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
205	Virtual health information infrastructures: A scalable regional	Integrating research, education and evidence-based medical practice requires complex infrastructures and network linkages among these critical activities. This research examines communities of practice and open source software tools in development of scalable virtual infrastructures for the regional Virtual Health Library of the Latin American and Caribbean Health Sciences System (Bireme) and embedded national cases. Virtual infrastructures refer to an environment		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um

	modo	characterized by overlapping distribution networks accessible through Internet portals and websites designed to facilitate integrated use of available resources. Case analysis shows engagement of interdisciplinary communities of practice for scalable virtual infrastructure design. This research program considers theory and methods for study of transferability of the Latin American model to large health care systems in other cultures.			sistema.
206	Development of a chemotherapy regimen interaction database for the mobile internet: Detecting interactions with psychotropics through OncoRx-MI	Introduction.Cancer patients are at high risks of drugdrug interactions (DDIs). Clinicians need to know the magnitude of DDIs so as to better manage their patients' drug therapies. We have previously created a novel interaction database for oncology prescriptions (OncoRx). In this project, we leverage on 3G networks to further develop this database into an iPhone-specific application for the mobile internet (OncoRx-MI). Methodology.Data on anticancer drugs (ACDs), chemotherapy regimens (CRegs) and DDIs with psychotropics were compiled from various hardcopy and online resources, and published articles from PubMed, Scopus and Science Direct. The database and iPhone web documents were designed using Adobe Dreamweaver CS4 and associated with a combination of open-source programming scripts. Results.OncoRx-MI currently detects over 5000 DDIs (69.3% pharmacokinetic, 30.7% pharmacodynamic) between 256 single-agent and combination CRegs with 51 psychotropic drugs. OncoRx-MI fits the iPhone screen configuration, and displays information regarding the regimen, pharmacokinetics of the drugs and detected DDIs in tabular format for improved usability. Conclusion.OncoRx-MI is the first mobile DDI application of its kind which detects interactions for combination CRegs. Future versions will include DDIs with other drug categories. Usability studies on its impact in clinical practice will also be carried out.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
207	Workflow support for mobile data collection	Mobile devices are increasingly being used for electronic data collection in low resource setting, where Internet-based solutions are infeasible. The data collection effort often requires the underlying processes, represented as data flows and workflows to be adhered. Workflow Management Systems (WFMS) could enable Mobile Data Collection (MDC) with workflow support as it is in Process Aware Information Systems. However, the use of WFMS for MDC designed for low resource settings needs to address challenges of mobile computing such as disconnections, slow connection links, limited computing power, etc. We present a framework that has been developed to integrate generic Data Collection tools with Workflow Management Systems (WFMS) to enable MDC in such resource-constrained environments. Furthermore we implement a tool based on this framework and provide an example of a vaccination registry project that uses mobile phones to record and track child immunisations.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
208	Medical cyber physical systems	We discuss current trends in the development and use of high-confidence medical cyber-physical systems (MCPS). These trends, including increased reliance on software to deliver new functionality, wider use of network connectivity in MCPS, and demand for continuous patient monitoring, bring new challenges into the process of MCPS development and at the same time create new opportunities for research and development.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
209	Prototyping closed loop physiologic control with the medical device coordination framework	Medical devices historically have been monolithic units - developed, validated, and approved by regulatory authorities as standalone entities. Despite the fact that modern medical devices increasingly incorporate connectivity mechanisms that enable device data to be streamed to electronic health records and displays that aggregate data from multiple devices, connectivity is not being leveraged to allow an integrated collection of devices to work together as a single system to automate clinical work flows. This is due, in part, to current regulatory policies which prohibit such interactions due to safety concerns. In previous work, we proposed an open source middleware framework and an accompanying model-based development environment that could be used to quickly implement medical device coordination applications - enabling a "systems of systems" paradigm for medical devices. Such a paradigm shows great promise for supporting many applications that increase both the safety and effectiveness of medical care as well as the efficiency of clinical workflows. In this paper, we report on our experience using our Medical Device Coordination Framework (MDCF) to carry out a rapid		CII	

		prototyping of one such application - a multi-device medical system that uses closed loop physiologic control to affect better patient outcomes for Patient Controlled Anelgesic (PCA) pumps.			
210	Evaluation of a flowchart-based EHR query system: A case study of RetroGuide	Provision of query systems which are intuitive for non-experts has been recognized as an important informatics challenge. We developed a prototype of a flowchart-based analytical framework called RetroGuide that enables non-experts to formulate query tasks using a step-based, patient-centered paradigm inspired by workflow technology. We present results of the evaluation of RetroGuide in comparison to Structured Query Language (SQL) in laboratory settings using a mixed method design. We asked 18 human subjects with limited database experience to solve query tasks in RetroGuide and SQL, and quantitatively compared their test scores. A follow-up questionnaire was designed to compare both technologies qualitatively and investigate RetroGuide technology acceptance. The quantitative comparison of test scores showed that the study subjects achieved significantly higher scores using the RetroGuide technology. Qualitative study results indicated that 94% of subjects preferred RetroGuide to SQL because RetroGuide was easier to learn, it better supported temporal tasks, and it seemed to be a more logical modeling paradigm. Additional qualitative evaluation results, based on a technology acceptance model, suggested that a fully developed RetroGuide-like technology would be well accepted by users. Our study is an example of a structure validation study of a prototype query system, results of which provided significant guidance in further development of a novel query paradigm for EHR data. We discuss the strengths and weakness of our study design and results, and their implication for future evaluations of query systems in general.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
211	Medicare-grid: New trends on the development of E-health system based on grid technology	The evolution of information technology over the last decade has brought opportunities to improvements in the state of art of medical services. One scenario is that a patient's digital health record can easily be shared among hospitals and medical centers via internet, enabling the examination performed in one location while clinical diagnosis be done by physicians in another. In this paper, we propose a Medicare-Grid — a novel grid-based E-health system proposed to ease the process of retrieving and exchanging personal health data among hospitals and medical centers. Grid and peer-to-peer technologies have been used to integrate computing and storage resources provided by hospitals, as also to develop an Electronic Health Record (EHR) center to store and share EHRs among these locations. We have also developed a system prototype using ultimate hardware resources and open source software systems to simulate a real scenario as described above. We demonstrate that the idea proposed in the project is feasible, possible to be implemented and applicable to real world.		CI1	
212	Alert based disaster notification and resource allocation	When a disaster occurs, timely actions in response to urgent requests conveyed by critical messages (known as alerts) constitute a vital key to effectiveness. These actions include notifying potentially affected parties so that they can take precautionary measures, gathering additional information, and requesting remedial actions and resource allocation. However, there are different types of disasters such as epidemic outbreaks, natural disasters, major accidents, and terrorist attacks. At the same time, there are also many different parties involved such as governments, healthcare institutions, businesses, and individuals. To address these problems, we introduce a Disaster Notification and Resource Allocation System (DNRAS) based on an Alert Management System (AMS) implemented through Web services. This unified platform supports timely interactions among various parties, focusing on notification and monitoring, resource enquiry and allocation, as well as the mobility of information. We detail the mechanisms of these functions in our system, illustrating the Web services interface parameters for communications and interoperability. We illustrate the applicability of our approach with an example of an epidemic outbreak and discuss the advantage of our approach with respect to various stakeholders of our system.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
213	Personal and external determinants of	No abstract available.		CE4	Resumo não disponível para análise.

	<p>medical bloggers knowledge sharing behavior</p>			
214	<p>Interactive simulation of surgical needle insertion and steering</p>	<p>We present algorithms for simulating and visualizing the insertion and steering of needles through deformable tissues for surgical training and planning. Needle insertion is an essential component of many clinical procedures such as biopsies, injections, neurosurgery, and brachytherapy cancer treatment. The success of these procedures depends on accurate guidance of the needle tip to a clinical target while avoiding vital tissues. Needle insertion deforms body tissues, making accurate placement difficult. Our interactive needle insertion simulator models the coupling between a steerable needle and deformable tissue. We introduce (1) a novel algorithm for local remeshing that quickly enforces the conformity of a tetrahedral mesh to a curvilinear needle path, enabling accurate computation of contact forces, (2) an efficient method for coupling a 3D finite element simulation with a 1D inextensible rod with stick-slip friction, and (3) optimizations that reduce the computation time for physically based simulations. We can realistically and interactively simulate needle insertion into a prostate mesh of 13,375 tetrahedra and 2,763 vertices at a 25 Hz frame rate on an 8-core 3.0 GHz Intel Xeon PC. The simulation models prostate brachytherapy with needles of varying stiffness, steering needles around obstacles, and supports motion planning for robotic needle insertion. We evaluate the accuracy of the simulation by comparing against real-world experiments in which flexible, steerable needles were inserted into gel tissue phantoms.</p>		<p>CE1</p> <p>Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.</p>
215	<p>A spatial national health facility database for public health sector planning in Kenya in 2008</p>	<p>Background: Efforts to tackle the enormous burden of ill-health in low-income countries are hampered by weak health information infrastructures that do not support appropriate planning and resource allocation. For health information systems to function well, a reliable inventory of health service providers is critical. The spatial referencing of service providers to allow their representation in a geographic information system is vital if the full planning potential of such data is to be realized. Methods: A disparate series of contemporary lists of health service providers were used to update a public health facility database of Kenya last compiled in 2003. These new lists were derived primarily through the national distribution of antimalarial and antiretroviral commodities since 2006. A combination of methods, including global positioning systems, was used to map service providers. These spatially-referenced data were combined with high-resolution population maps to analyze disparity in geographic access to public health care. Findings: The updated 2008 database contained 5,334 public health facilities (67% ministry of health; 28% mission and nongovernmental organizations; 2% local authorities; and 3% employers and other ministries). This represented an overall increase of 1,862 facilities compared to 2003. Most of the additional facilities belonged to the ministry of health (79%) and the majority were dispensaries (91%). 93% of the health facilities were spatially referenced, 38% using global positioning systems compared to 21% in 2003. 89% of the population was within 5 km Euclidean distance to a public health facility in 2008 compared to 71% in 2003. Over 80% of the population outside 5 km of public health service providers was in the sparsely settled pastoralist areas of the country. Conclusion: We have shown that, with concerted effort, a relatively complete inventory of mapped health services is possible with enormous potential for improving planning. Expansion in public health care in Kenya has resulted in significant increases in geographic access although several areas of the country need further improvements. This information is key to future planning and with this paper we have released the digital spatial database in the public domain to assist the Kenyan Government and its partners in the health sector.</p>		<p>CE1</p> <p>Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.</p>
216	<p>Configurable politics and</p>	<p>Information Infrastructures typically evolve in an incremental fashion, through partly planned and unplanned processes. A significant mechanism of growth is when previously unconnected systems are integrated, facilitating the transition from networking to inter-networking. Conversely, failure to integrate systems contributes</p>		<p>CE1</p> <p>Não apresenta o desenvolvimento</p>

	<p>asymmetric integration: Health e-infrastructure in India</p>	<p>to the lack of evolution of the infrastructure. Integration seems crucial for evolving infrastructures; however, there is little consensus on what it entails, as can be seen when different connotations of "integration" are unpacked. In contrast to the dominant view of integration as a largely technical concern, our focus is on how political and institutional interests are embedded in efforts to achieve integration. More specifically, we explore strategies for institutional integration that take into account uneven distribution of political influence. The paper builds on empirical material from our ongoing (2001 - 2008) involvement with the problem of fragmented information systems in the health care sector in India. The case is seen from the perspective of one small actor offering free, open-source software that is already being used in several other developing countries. Choosing to focus on a small actor highlights the asymmetric power relations among the actors; our actor has no other option than to seek to align with bigger and more influential actors. We analyse the strategies, the configurable politics, and the outcomes of the distinct configurations that emerge from this form of asymmetric integration.</p>			<p>imento de um sistema.</p>
<p>217</p>	<p>Open source GIS for HIV/AIDS management</p>	<p>Background: Reliable access to basic services can improve a community's resilience to HIV/AIDS. Accordingly, work is being done to upgrade the physical infrastructure in affected areas, often employing a strategy of decentralised service provision. Spatial characteristics are one of the major determinants in implementing services, even in the smaller municipal areas, and good quality spatial information is needed to inform decision making processes. However, limited funds, technical infrastructure and human resource capacity result in little or no access to spatial information for crucial infrastructure development decisions at local level. This research investigated whether it would be possible to develop a GIS for basic infrastructure planning and management at local level. Given the resource constraints of the local government context, particularly in small municipalities, it was decided that open source software should be used for the prototype system. Results: The design and development of a prototype system illustrated that it is possible to develop an open source GIS system that can be used within the context of local information management. Usability tests show a high degree of usability for the system, which is important considering the heavy workload and high staff turnover that characterises local government in South Africa. Local infrastructure management stakeholders interviewed in a case study of a South African municipality see the potential for the use of GIS as a communication tool and are generally positive about the use of GIS for these purposes. They note security issues that may arise through the sharing of information, lack of skills and resource constraints as the major barriers to adoption. Conclusion: The case study shows that spatial information is an identified need at local level. Open source GIS software can be used to develop a system to provide local-level stakeholders with spatial information. However, the suitability of the technology is only a part of the system - there are wider information and management issues which need to be addressed before the implementation of a local-level GIS for infrastructure management can be successful.</p>	<p>CII</p>		
<p>218</p>	<p>Work in progress: Exploring security and privacy concepts through the development and testing of the iTrust medical records system</p>	<p>University computer science and software engineering students must build reliability and security into their software applications from the start of development. A graduate-level Software Testing and Reliability course at North Carolina State University has a learning objective of using appropriate testing techniques for the development of a reliable and secure system. Beginning in Fall 2005, the semester project has involved the development and testing of the open source and freely-available iTrust Medical Records system prototype. Our vision is to build a community of educators, students, and medical professionals that can collaborate and use the iTrust project as a development platform and testbed for secure and reliable application development.</p>	<p>CII</p>		